
THE ROLE OF LEADERSHIP STYLES IN SERVICE
QUALITY DELIVERY AMONG SMALL
INDIGENOUS HOSPITALITY ENTERPRISES IN
NIGERIA

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Declaration

I, Henry Agozie Nwude, declare that this Thesis is a product of my own work and has not been submitted for any other academic degree. Any information collected from other sources have been explicitly acknowledged.

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ABSTRACT

Recent studies have stressed the need for scholars to examine the influence of leadership styles such as transformational, transactional and servant leadership on employee service behaviour and the ultimate effect on service quality delivery. However, some scholars emphasised the need to study leadership styles based on country's cultural characteristics since other countries have clearly different cultural characteristics from the west that may influence styles of leadership. In this light, this research aims to examine the role paternalistic leadership style has on employee service behaviour and ultimately service quality in small indigenous hotels in Nigeria.

A conceptual model linking paternalistic leadership to customer contact employee service behaviours underpinned by both theories of social exchange and reasoned action was formulated, which was then tested upon a sample of 95 customer contact hotel employees and 104 customers in Nigeria using structural equation modelling.

The results indicate that paternalistic leadership, which is the predominant leadership style in Nigerian organisations based on cultural characteristics of Nigeria has no effect on the customer contact employees service behaviour and ultimately, service quality. This opposes the arguments aligning leadership styles with cultural norms and values of a society (Iwowo, 2015; Jackson, 2016; Dikko, 2017; Bonsu and Bulley, 2017; Hassan and Lituchy, 2017; Evans, 2018). Globalisation is gradually changing the cultural dynamics of Nigerian societies from a purely traditional one to modernity and thus affects the way people expect to be led. Furthermore, the findings communicate to Nigerian Hoteliers that sticking to traditional leadership styles based on cultural norms and values is becoming obsolete and unfavourable, which is likely ineffectual in influencing positive behaviour and attitudes in employees during service encounters and in turn on the organisations service performance

DEDICATION

To my parents, Mr John Iliemena Nwude and Mrs Florence Nkechi Nwude for your steadfast belief in me and setting me on the path towards this accomplishment. I also dedicate this study to my darling wife, Amy. Thank you for your support and encouragement.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the research with a comprehensive explanation of the conceptual background of the study whilst also setting out the definition of the terms to be used in the study. The chapter proceeds with a section discussing the contextual background of the tourism and hospitality sector in Nigerian. It also outlined the personal background and motivation of the researcher in addition to the essential components that builds up to the research such as the research questions, aims, research objectives, research rationale, the problem statement, the significance of the research and the proposed contributions. The chapter ends with an outline of how the rest of the study is organised.

1.1 Conceptual Background of the Study

The research area focuses on investigating the influence of hotel owners/managers leadership styles on customer contact employee behaviour in service encounter to enhance customers' perception of service quality. Small indigenous hospitality businesses have received limited attention from literature on service quality compared to major service industries such as banks, retail firms, hospitals and the large multi-national hotels (Evans, 2018; Rauch et al, 2015). The lack of attention in this field could be pinned on the dearth of interest from the scholars that led the way in service quality theories (Evans, 2018). The lack of research in this field of service quality delivery in the small indigenous hospitality sector has motivated the researcher to undertake this research, focusing on small indigenous hotel establishments in Anambra state of Nigeria as a means of contributing towards closing the gap in the literature.

The key elements for the success of every organisations rest majorly on customer perceptions of service experiences (Dabholkar, 2014; Cao and Kim, 2014; Laming and Mason, 2014; Wu et al, 2015; Kondasami and Panda, 2015). Customer perceptions are formed through customers' assessment of the quality of service provided by a service organisation. Thus, **customer**

perceptions of service quality are subjective evaluations of a service experience during service encounters (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2003; Cao and Kim, 2014; Rauch et al, 2015; Norton et al, 2016; Lee et al, 2016; Awana and Khan, 2016; Moon and Armstrong, 2019). It is the customer's beliefs concerning the received or experienced service (Parasuraman et al, 1991; Paul et al, 2016; Khoo et al, 2017; Brida et al, 2016). The degree in which customers perceive every service's attributes directly affect their attitude when making an overall judgement about their experience of the quality of service delivered (Brida et al, 2016). Thus, customer contact employees should endeavour to behave and express attitudes conducive to service performance during interactions with customers as they are the face of the organisation for the customer. The interaction between the two is part of the service encounter and is therefore likely to affect customers overall experience of a service. **Customer contact employees** are those employees that are in primary or direct contact with customers (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Clark et al, 2009; Nart et al, 2018; Preez et al, 2017). In the hospitality sector, customer contact employees could be receptionist, concierge, bell person, food/room service and waiter. They are those employees on the frontline, directly accountable for face-to-face customer service, service quality and customer satisfaction (Bowen, 2016). Their attitudes and behaviour towards customers during service encounters has a significant effect on the customers evaluation of service quality (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Lee et al, 2006; Clark et al, 2009). It could be short term effects such as likeability and perceived quality or long-term effects such as trust and loyalty. Hence their importance to excellent service performance cannot be overstated. Leaders have the ultimate goal to positively influence these vital set of employees through appropriate behaviour to ensure they deliver excellent performance during service encounters.

Most studies on leadership style and behaviour in Nigeria are rooted in leadership models applicable in the western world, with a very limited studies on country-specific leadership styles based on cultural influences in Nigeria (Kuada, 2010; Wanasika, 2011; Jackson, 2016;

Iwowo, 2015). Therefore, this study also aims to close the gaps in the literature by highlighting the significance of understanding the influence of cultural characteristics of the Nigerian society on leadership styles of indigenous hotel owners and managers. In general, the research covered hotel customers' perception of service quality, the customer-oriented behaviour of employees during service encounters and hotel leadership.

1.2 The Tourism and Hospitality Industry in Nigeria

In the face of financial and political instability, the impact of droughts and other new regulations, tourism in Nigeria has proved to be resilient. The prospects for this industry to enjoy further development are abundant, although at a more moderate rate. However, we continue to see a range of problems facing this country as well. With the Nigerian economy heavily dependent on oil, dropping oil prices in 2015 led to a decline in economic growth, accompanied by a decrease of 1.6 percent in 2016 that continued through the first quarter of 2017 (PWC, 2018). The naira's deteriorating value has led to the establishment of foreign exchange restrictions by the Nigerian central bank that have discouraged foreign travel. The Nigerian economy was also afflicted by rising inflation due to a drop in the value of the naira, the value of which dropped by a cumulative 45% against the US dollar between the year 2015 and 2017. The fall in the naira has made imports more costly, leading to an inflation leap. Inflation in consumer prices increased from 9.0 percent in 2015 to 16.4 percent in 2017. However, inflation is projected to slow over the next two years, according to PWC (2018), and to fall to single digits starting in 2020, averaging 9.7 percent.

The domestic economy is the main driver of tourism in Nigeria. 97 percent of tourist spending comes from domestic travelers (BusinessDay, 2017), according to the Nigerian hospitality study launched by Jumia Travel. Despite the country's security problems and the decline in the exchange rate of dollars, many Nigerians opted to fly to exciting tourist resorts within the

country to spend their holidays. Also, most Nigerians don't have sufficient income that could necessitate spending holidays abroad. Hence, the hospitality industry is being majorly patronized from domestic tourists and travelers than international tourists.

While Nigeria still remains an important location for international hotel brands due to its large economy, international travel accounted for about 3 percent of tourist spending. Among the big international and South African companies that have hotels in Nigeria are Best Western, Sheraton, Radisson, Hilton, City Lodge, Tsogo Sun and Sun International. Although several brands have postponed or abandoned openings because of the tough economic situation in Nigeria. For example, South Africa's City Lodge is planning a major expansion in Africa, but plans do not include Nigeria for now, the largest economy on the continent, where it has suffered setbacks before (Reuters, 2017).

The Nigerian tourist industry has been suffering from little awareness and poorly packaged and advertised tourism opportunities. The industry was being drawn down by poor physical infrastructures, very bad communication systems, insufficient security and healthcare, as well as unclear tourism visions. These myriads of complexities have been worsened even further by the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. The present government is trying to expand the tourist industry. As part of a strategy to make Nigeria a world tourist destination, the National Council of Arts and Culture is taking measures to promote local culture. The government also offers incentives for constructing new facilities. If the money is being used to build new hotels, a quarter of hotel income created from tourists in foreign currencies is now tax-exempt (PWC, 2018). However, despite these incentives, hotel operators still face multiple taxation from federal, state and local governments (Orekoya, 2018). The burden of multiplicity of taxes weighing down the hospitality and tourism industry specifically hotels operators include company income tax (CIT), tertiary education trust fund tax (TET Fund tax), value added tax

(VAT), industrial training fund (ITF) contribution and hotel occupancy & restaurants consumption tax.

Staying competitive in this uncertain economic environment and increased competition from new entrants is a huge challenge for managers/owners of small indigenous hotels. Hence, to stay competitive and win more market share, Hotels need to focus on the delivery of superior service quality and the managers have an active and significant role to play in making sure that employees are performing well in-service encounters.

The Hotel Sector in Nigeria

There is a general consensus about the lack of reliable statistics and market information about the Nigerian hotel industry as a whole (Nwosu, 2016; Bankole, 2002, UNWTO, 2006). Even the regulatory body, the Nigerian tourism development corporation (NTDC) doesn't have a complete statistic for the number of hotels in Nigeria. International and regional hotel brands are clustered in the major states (in terms of economic output) such as Lagos, Abuja and Rivers states. Arguably, Anambra state, which is a state in the south eastern part of Nigeria, has one of the fastest growing hospitality industries in Nigeria. This could be partly because of its leading position as one of the largest markets in West Africa, hence, the influx of people in and out of the state on a daily basis and also in addition to being a home to a lot of caves and monuments such as Ogbunike caves, Agulu crocodile lake and Osomari forest reserves which makes for a host of interesting places to visit. Hence, that is the reason it's selected as the research focus.

With the proliferation of hotels in virtually all corners of the state, excellent service quality becomes a critical element for hotels to reach and sustain higher competitive standards. The state capital, Awka, is growing rapidly by the day and has hotels of different classes scattered all over the city as a result of the growing number of customers and rising population of people

that engage in one business activity or the other. A good percentage of people that use hotel services in the state are business travellers who are in the state for business purposes, followed by domestic tourists.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

In the last few years, Nigeria has experienced a tremendous growth in economic development which has attracted a significant rise in the number of hotels. Despite this growth the country still faces difficulties in health and hygiene, overall infrastructure, safety and security, the effective selling of cultural and business travel and the management of human resources and labour market. In the face of these difficulties, Nigeria still shows great untapped potential for natural tourism.

According to the travel and tourism competitiveness index developed by the world economic forum that benchmarks the travel and tourism competitiveness of 40 economies and measures the set of factors and policies that enables the sustainable development of the travel and tourism sector Nigeria scores very high on price competitiveness and very low on human resources and labour market (WEF, 2019). It is the largest economy in Africa however it ranks just below the middle of the pack regarding human resources and labour market and has the worst safety and security ranking in the entire sub-Saharan African region. Under the human resources and labour market pillar, Nigeria scores very low on degree of customer orientation which measures how well companies in each country treats customers (WEF, 2019).

According to Jana and Chandra (2016) service quality, customer orientation and satisfaction are important aspects of the hotel industry which only through them that a hotel can retain its customers and attract more customers. Because of the increased competition in the Nigerian hospitality sector resulting from the influx of the big multinational brands, small indigenous khotels are poised with the provision of excellence service to be able to stay competitive. The

hotel industry in Nigeria is booming, hence, everyone with sufficient capital is investing into the sector with little or no knowledge of the expert skills needed to successfully run a hotel business and compete favourably in the sector. However, the poor level of service quality due to inadequate customer orientation in the sector is mind blowing. Though the managers/owners of these small indigenous hotels are not on the frontline of service encounters, however, they have a key role to play in achieving positive customer perceived service quality. The poor level of quality service in this sector is one of the factors that hinders the growth of these small hotel enterprises. Customers want to receive the value of what they are paying for. Complaints are flooding in from all corners about the level of services these hotels provide. Daily complaints are recorded regarding poor facilities, untrained and rude staff with no hospitable character and so on. There is wide area of under satisfied and unsatisfied demand in the provision of quality services most especially in the research focus, Anambra state capital, Awka where most small hotels are forced to close down due to the inability to attract, retain customers and stay competitive.

In addition, countries all over the world are placing travel restrictions and enforcing border closures to movement to and from other countries as a result of the current outbreak and spread of covid-19 disease. Inter-state travel is also restricted to curb the spread of the infection from one state to another in Nigeria. These restrictions are greatly affecting the travel and tourism sector. Hotels and airlines are continually experiencing plummeting demand and patronage from international tourists with high expectations of cancellations. The travel and tourism sector to include hospitality have been greatly hit by the coronavirus pandemic and it's not going to be business as usual when these restrictions are eventually lifted. Firms will be forced to come up with innovative solutions to ensure maximum delivery of quality service to match the expectations and needs of customers restricted in their homes for months. Decision makers plays a crucial role in delivering top quality service to their customers especially in a period of

uncertainty. Recognising customer needs and the importance of excellent service quality delivery rests hugely on how decision makers in organisations perceive and evaluates it (Lopez-Gamero et al, 2010). Decision makers in this context could be said to be hotel managers. Hence from Lopez -Gamero et al (2010) assumptions, a leader has a significant and influential role to play in an organisation to ensure customer contact employees are delivering excellent service to customers. The leadership style of a manager has a key role in influencing frontline employees or customer contact employees towards being customer oriented and the delivery of excellent services in any service organisation. This phenomenon gave rise to the need to examine service quality issues faced by hotels in Anambra State, Nigeria and how the management's leadership styles can influence customer contact employees towards providing top quality services.

1.4 Rationale of the Study

After years of experience working in the Nigerian hospitality sector specifically in various indigenously owned hotels in Anambra State, the researcher is motivated with an interest in achieving customer service performance excellence in small hospitality enterprises in Nigeria through effective management practices. After a thorough review of literature, knowledge regarding leadership and service quality was uncovered. Some researchers have made an attempt at linking leadership to service quality delivery in various sectors such as Banking (Asgari, 2014), Hotel (Clark et al, 2009; Linuesa-Langreo et al, 2017; Ling et al, 2016; Koyuncu et al, 2014), Hospital (Pahl and Hamid, 2015) and in the B2B context (Pantouvakis and Patsiouras, 2016). One major limitation with the study of Clark et al (2009) is the failure to measure leadership styles from the employees' perspective. Measuring leadership style from both employees and managers perspective would have been extremely beneficial with regard to cross validation. Hence one of their suggestions for future research is to measure leadership styles from both managers and employees' perspectives to examine consistency. Secondly their

research was out in a single echelon of hotels, all having similar price-quality relationship. In order to eliminate concern for generalizability, it would be more appropriate to include all tiers of the hotel sector. Linuesa-Langreo et al (2017) also failed to fill in the gap left by Clark et al (2009) studies. Also, Customers were not surveyed to examine the dependent variable in their study, customer service performance, and other important aspects such as service quality and customer satisfaction. Koyuncu et al (2014) like other researchers acknowledged the importance of including customer perceptions of service quality and their satisfaction with service provided. Also, all these studies focused on leadership styles that are rarely applicable in the African settings such as servant leadership, transactional leadership, transformational leadership, democratic leadership, empowerment leadership, however it would be good to look at leadership styles that are more applicable in a cultural setting very much different from the western societies such as paternalistic leadership style. Past researchers have argued that current western notions of leadership are not widely applicable in Africa and east Asia (Jones et al, 1996; Jackson, 2011; Doorfman et al, 2012; Kabasakal et al, 2012; Rowley and Ulrich, 2012; Jackson, 2016). The major reasons have to do with significant differences in values concerning authority, group loyalties and interpersonal harmony. Hence there is a growing body of empirical evidence which exposes the mistaken assumption that western management practice invalidates all indigenous management practice (Blunt and Jones, 1997; Doorfman et al, 2012, Hofstede, 2016; Jackson, 2016). Therefore, to fill the identified gap, the researcher aim to investigate paternalistic leadership style in addition to the transformational leadership style and their impact on customer perceived service quality, as it has been widely supported that paternalistic style of leadership or paternalism is common in national cultures that score high in uncertainty avoidance, masculinity, collectivism, power distance, and societies whose members are hesitant to jump the formal chain of command in order to avoid an array of

consequences and have huge respect for hierarchical order (Aycan et al, 2000; Li and Sun; 2015; Jackson, 2016).

Also, there is currently no study linking the leadership styles to service quality in the Nigerian hospitality sector. The search was conducted in various journal databases, UWS library and other online sources. The main search keywords include leadership styles, service quality, Hotel service performance in Nigeria, transactional leadership, transformational leadership, laissez faire leadership, leadership styles and service quality, organisational commitment, paternalistic leadership. Thus, this study will be of paramount importance to the Nigerian hospitality sector in areas of organisational behaviour, human resource management and service quality.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The Nigerian hospitality industry has been massively expanding due to an increase in economic activities. The number of international tourists arriving Nigeria is expected to increase as the federal government is flooding out initiatives geared at making Nigeria an attractive tourist destination through the Nigerian tourism development corporation, an agency of the Nigerian ministry of information and culture responsible for tourism in Nigeria. NTDC promotes the country as a domestic and international tourist destination for leisure, business, religion, festivals and commerce. According to the Nigerian minister of information and culture, Alhaji Lai Mohammed Nigerian government have spent 2.7 billion naira in the last two years on various projects such as roads, railways and other infrastructures that has direct or indirect linkages with tourist sites in the country. NTDC was allocated a further 1.5 billion naira in the recently signed 2020 appropriation. This is expected to skyrocket competition in the hospitality sector. Hence the sector has seen an influx of international brands like Sheraton hotels and Hilton. This is still not, however, expressed in the quality of services in this sector. By disregarding the fact that business thrives on service, and thus leaning towards increasing

profits, they seem to have sunk into the pit of an ideological dilemma. Excellent service quality is very valuable to the hospitality industry that countries such as Japan have already seen the injection of robots into customer service roles. For example, Henn-na hotel in Japan have a staff team entirely made of robots (Rajesh, 2015). However, it's been argued by practitioners if these humanoids will be as intelligent as humans in service delivery. Although hotels in Nigeria offer different services to all classes of customers, nevertheless they still suffer from a culture that is opposed to supporting and promoting excellent service quality delivery to guests. Thus, customer / client service quality is one area that requires urgent attention in this field.

The study results will raise some vital substantive issues surrounding management of service quality in the Nigerian hospitality sector and subsequently should provide some values to both **academics** and **practitioners** alike. Determining the extent to which leadership styles strengthens service quality will be of paramount importance to hotels and likewise other players in this sector such as Bars, Nightclubs and Restaurants. It might interest the managers to find out how their behaviour influences the service quality delivery process. With respect to service marketing and organisational behaviour in the academic field, the findings of this study will further enrich the limited literature on the role leadership styles play in the service quality deliver process.

Academic Contributions

Though the researcher is fully aware of the existence of literature conceptualising and operationalising service quality in lots of service industries, however, the study of leadership effects in the enhancement of service quality is still very much needed. To the researcher's best knowledge, limited study has to date attempted to study leadership style in the field of service provision, however, none at all has tried to link paternalistic leadership style to service quality delivery in Nigeria. Given the importance of leadership behaviour in service quality delivery

based on evidence from several literature, such research is very much overdue. In addition, this study contributes to the call for African researchers to incorporate African concepts and cultural values in investigating leadership effectiveness in African organisations (Appiah et al, 2016; Jackson, 2016; Iwowo, 2015; Iguisi, 2012; Wanasika, 2011; Kuada, 2010). These researchers contends that leadership in African organisations should be linked with norms and values of African cultures. Arguing that western theories of leadership such as transformational and transactional leadership are ineffectual in these cultures. However, these authors seemed to ignore the gradual effects of globalisation and westernisation on cultural dynamics. Hence, the results of this study will contribute to these arguments advocating the adoption of African cultural specific leadership style such as paternalism in Nigerian organisations specifically in Nigerian hotels.

Management Contributions

This study provides valuable information to hoteliers by showing how attitudes and behaviours of customer contact employees can influence hotel guest perceptions of service quality and how negative behaviour in service encounters can be mitigated through appropriate leadership styles by the manager to achieve staff performance in service encounters. It will specifically inform hoteliers to lead in ways that are more likely to strengthen the service-oriented culture of their hotels, highlighting leadership styles more suitable to influence employee into performing customer-oriented behaviour to enhance guests perception of the quality of service. Thus, this study will be of interest to the hospitality organisations and practitioners in Nigeria as it reveals the significance of leadership style in promoting service climate and staff behaviours conducive to excellent service quality. Moreover, the findings of this study communicates to practitioners that sticking to traditional leadership styles based on cultural norms and values is becoming obsolete and unfavourable in hospitality settings which is likely ineffectual in influencing positive behaviour and attitudes in employees during service

encounters and in turn on the organisations service performance. These findings can guide broader organisational development strategies of implementing leadership training programmes for managers and supervisors aimed at creating a positive service climate.

1.6 Research Purpose

As previously mentioned, there is a scarcity of knowledge regarding this phenomenon in the Nigerian context. hence, the main objective of this research is to evaluate the level of influence leadership styles have on customer contact employees service behaviours in service encounters conducive for the delivery of excellent service quality.

1.7 Research Objectives

Identifying the research gaps paved the way for the development of the study's specific objectives. These specific objectives essentially pay particular attention to procuring academic and practical evidence with regard to the norms, values, assumptions, attitudes and behaviours conducive to the delivery of quality services and leadership in the Nigerian hospitality sector.

- To assess the customers' perceptions of service quality in the Nigerian hospitality sector.
- To examine the influence of leadership styles on customer contact employees' service behaviour.
- To examine the effect of customer contact employees' service behaviour on customer's perceptions of service quality.
- To provide recommendations for the managers on improving customer contact employees service performance for a superior service quality delivery.

1.8 Research Questions

To identify areas relating to service quality shortfalls for possible intervention by the managers as well as investigating the relationships identified in the literature review, which are the

relationships between service quality in the Nigerian hospitality sector and leadership styles of the managers/owners, the study aims to provide answers to the following questions.

- What perceptions do customers have about the service quality in the Nigerian hospitality sector?
- How does leadership style affect customer contact employees service behavior?
- How does customer contact employee service behavior affect customer's perception of service quality?

1.9 Organisation of the study

This dissertation is structured into five chapters. The first, Chapter one sets out the introduction of the dissertation. The chapter presents the industry background, demonstrates the clear expression of the research problem and elucidate the rationale and significance of the study. In addition, this chapter clearly explains the research purpose, questions and objectives, and finally ends with an explicitly specified organisation of the whole dissertation.

Chapter two presents the review of the literature relating to small enterprises, service quality and leadership concepts. The chapter is divided into four parts. Part one is concerned with small enterprises. Part two discusses services and the concepts of services such as characteristics of services, external service quality and its measurements, internal service quality, service encounters, service employees' behaviours, and management commitment to service quality. Part three reviews the development of leadership theories and leadership styles. To understand how culture impacts leadership behaviour, part four discusses national culture. An understanding of the influence of culture on leadership behaviour then leads to a review of leadership in Africa, in part five. Part six then reviews the effects of leadership on service employees' behaviours. Finally, the last part of the chapter, part seven presents the conceptual

framework for this study which has been developed by synthesizing concepts from leadership theory, service employee behaviours and customer perceived service quality.

Chapter three discusses the research methodology which adopts the research layers of Saunders et al (2019) as a methodological framework. This chapter explores several research philosophies and propounds the rationale for adopting the preferred one for the current research. The research approach, methods, strategy, techniques and procedures for data collection and analysis for this study are also highlighted. This chapter also, illustrates the study population and sample.

Chapter four presents the research analysis and results for collected data. This chapter has two parts. The first part deals with the descriptive analysis which is divided into three sections. The first section illustrates customer perception of service quality in the hotel industry. The second part presents the analysis on customer contact employees altitudinal and behavioural responses. The third section presents the analysis on customer contact employees' perception of managers/owners' leadership style. The second part of this chapter deals with testing of the hypothetical relationships using Pearson correlation analysis and structural equation modelling.

Chapter five presents the discussion of the findings. This chapter started with a summary of the research questions and followed with a presentation of the findings in non-technical detail to aid in understanding the answers to the research questions. Following the discussion of the findings, the next chapter, Chapter Six, then concludes by summarising the study and findings and illustrating the academic and managerial implications of the study, highlighting also the limitations and suggestions for future research, academic researchers may wish to explore.

Figure 1.1: Organisation of the study. (Created by the researcher)

1.10 Conclusion

This chapter has laid the foundation for the research which primarily investigates the influence of leadership styles on customer perceived service quality. This chapter discussed the research background and sets out the statement of the research problem. The rationale for conducting this research and the research's significance were also duly explained. This chapter further highlighted the research purpose, questions and objectives. Finally, the chapter ends with a clearly defined organisation of the study which helps the person reading the study to follow and comprehend the course of the ensuing chapters.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

This section of the thesis provides a critical review of academic journals and textbooks with valuable information on leadership styles, service quality and the relationship that exist between leadership styles and service quality. Initially, a brief discussion on small enterprises is provided for the purpose of this study.

2.1 Small enterprises

The SMEs are responsible for net job creation in OECD countries and make important contributions to innovation, productivity and economic growth (OECD, 2019). The organisation for economic co-operation and development (OECD) strongly asserts the significant role SMEs play in countries all over the world through employment and innovation. In developing and developed countries around the world, small enterprises are the largest employer of labour more than the bigger ones (Gonzalez et al, 2014; Abor and Quartey, 2010; Kongolo, 2010). As a key employer of labour in economies, small enterprises play huge role in poverty reduction most especially in developing countries (Buttar and Kocak, 2011; Mohammed et al, 2019; Okpara, 2011).

The European commission's (EC) (2015) categorise small enterprises to be those enterprises that employs less than 50 people and whose annual income is below 10 million euros. In relation to developing countries, the United Nations industrial development organisation (UNIDO) (1999) categorised small firms according to the number of staff. UNIDO defined small enterprises in developing nations as enterprises with 5 to 19 employees. However, in Nigeria, the small and medium enterprises agency of Nigeria, SMEDAN, classifies small enterprises as the ones employing 10 to 49 people with assets (excluding land and buildings) worth over 5 million naira but less than 50 million naira (SMEDAN, 2012). Most hotels in Nigeria have less than 49 employees, therefore, could be categorised as small enterprises.

These small enterprise hotels are in the budget class of the hotel industry in Nigeria and are mainly family owned and managed.

Size category	Employment	Assets (N million) excluding land and buildings
Micro enterprises	Less than 10	Less than 5
Small enterprises	10-49	5 – less than 50
Medium enterprises	50-199	50 – less than 500

Table 0.1: SMEDAN categorisation of SMEs in Nigeria. (SMEDAN, 2012)

2.2 Service

A service is any activity or benefit that is essentially not tangible and doesn't lead to the ownership of anything which is offered to one party by the other (Kotler, 2016). Defining service has been difficult partly because of its diversity (Wirtz and Lovelock, 2016). For instance, there is customer services which can be found in airlines, banking, insurance, health and then we have business services to include accountancy, engineering, architecture, legal, private security and management consulting. It was simply defined as “work done for someone else” (Juran and Gryna, 1993, p.53). Smith and Peters (1998) defines service as “any activity offered to a customer which is produced and consumed simultaneously” (p.119). While Gronrous (1990) defines service as “an activity of a more or less intangible nature that normally takes place in interaction between the customer and service employees and /or physical resources or goods and /or systems of the service provider, which are provided as solutions to customer problems” (p.6). All these definitions points to one major characteristic which is intangibility. Hence, a discussion on the characteristics of a service is necessarily required to extensively understand the concept.

Service Characteristics

Midway through the 20th century, service operations become more important than product manufacturing shifting the debate on quality from product quality to service quality. Regan (1963, p.58) was one of the first to delineate services from products. He argued that intangibility, perishability, heterogeneity and ubiquity made the total comprehension of service difficult (Regan, 1963). Zeithaml et al (1985), Sasser et al (1978), Fisk et al (1993) cited intangibility, simultaneity, heterogeneity and perishability as the four key characteristics of a service. Berry et al (1985) and Zeithaml (1985) contend that these four characteristics of a service differentiate a service from a product. However, over the last few years the debate against the delineation of services from products has intensified. The authors on the opposing side argued that the four well demonstrated characteristics used to differentiate services from products are inaccurate (Vargo and Lusch, 2004; Lovelock and Gummesson 2004). In order to fully understand service quality, these four characteristics must be well acknowledged (Fisk et al (1993). These four characteristics will be discussed in turn.

Inseparability

Production and consumption of services is inseparable. A service provider or marketer creates or performs a service during the moment of a complete or incomplete consumption of that service. During this concurrent process of creation and consumption, errors and quality issues are easily identified because of the highly visible activity of this simultaneous process. The service delivery process factor of consumer involvement has little or no direct control for the management. Because of this process factor of consumer involvement there should be minimal or no room for errors or quality issues as consumers interact with each other and a particular set of consumers can have a strong influence on other customers perception of service quality (Timothy, 2012). Gummesson (2007) has questioned the generalisation of the inseparable characteristic to all services. He argued that some services are performed without the presence

of customers hence the characteristics of inseparability is non-applicable to this subgroup of services (e.g., road maintenance, car repair and dry cleaning).

Heterogeneity

Edgett and Parkinson (1993) describes the heterogeneity of services as the difficulty in standardizing services. The process factor of consumers adds variability. Several factors affect the heterogeneity of service provisions. These includes the behaviour of the service provider, service providers awareness of customer needs, priorities and expectations in any given service encounter process. The liability of a service to vary or change from one period in time to another, and from one consumer to another complicates the service provider's task to reproduce the same service consistently. Service managers have to rely profoundly on the competence and capability of the customer contact employees to understand customer expectations and needs, and to react accordingly (Berry et al, 1985). According to Edvardsson et al (2005:12) "causes of heterogeneity can be explained from two perspectives, the first being the ever-changing nature of the service providers and service processes, while the second being variability in customers' needs and expectations".

Intangibility

Services have been declared to be immaterial and intangible. Intangibility of a service refers to the lack of physical attributes (Polyakova et al, 2015). This implies the existence of a set of difficulties for both the service provider and the consumer. It is difficult for the service provider to determine the service while the consumer find it difficult to assess the potential advantages of the service. Consumers hence scan for information through word of mouth (WOM, accessibility, reputation and quality assessment in making a judgement (Polyakova et al, 2015). Word of mouth and reputation have a strong influence on purchasing decisions. With the consideration of this influence, which is arguably greater than tangible product specifications,

service organisations are placed with greater responsibility of delivering what they promise (Ghobadian et al, 1994). Services are not always intangible (Edvardsson et al, 2005). In some situations, intangibility of a service might be perceived as a tangible impact. This is always the case in consultancy services for example whereby a professional advice might be effective in keeping a firm productive and performing for a very long time. Hence, creating the value of the intangible service in the long run. Thus, it could be perceived as tangible (Edvardsson et al, 2005).

Perishability

Services do not have shelf life because of their intangibility. Hence perishability relates to the unavailable option of storing or stockpiling services (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). The attribute of perishability allocates extra responsibility on the provider of the service to get the service right the first time and always. Unlike in manufacturing of goods with the luxury of a final quality checks, final quality checks of services are near impossible to execute (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). Gummesson (2000) argues that attributing perishability to services is nonsense as services are stored in people, knowledge, machines, buildings and systems. He supported this argument with examples such as a cash machine (ATM) being used as a store of standardised cash withdrawals and the emergency clinics as a store of skilled people, equipment's and procedures. Criticising perishability as a characteristic of service, Edwardson et al (2005) argues that memories of service provision can be kept for years, implying the possibilities of storage of services. For example, after eating a meal in a restaurant, the outcome of the food service perishes however the service can have long-term effects in the memory of the consumer. This perceived utility can be sustainable. As such it can be agreed, as claimed by Edvardsson et al (2005) that perishability is not a fitting reference object to characterise a service.

Service Encounter

For an organisation to be globally competitive employees need to be continuously educated, motivated, empowered to be fully productive as they are the backbone of any business success (Mishra, 2010). This applies especially to the hospitality industry where customers satisfaction begins from the employees. Since frontline employees in the hotel service sector are in direct contact with customers their role is very crucial to the performance of their hotels. Hence, service encounters or “moments of truth” (Jayawardhena et al, 2007) taking place between frontline employees and customers during the point of service delivery should reflect the philosophy, values and objectives of the organisations. Services are created, dispensed and consumed simultaneously in an interactive process between the provider of the service (the firm) and the receiver (the customer) (Svenson, 2006). Such interactive process in service encounters involve both human and non-human interaction. Hence, service encounter is defined by Bitner et al (1994) as “a period of time during which a consumer directly interacts with a service” (p.95). All aspects of the service firm with which the customer may interact with a service is covered by this definition. These might include the employee, the firm’s physical facilities (such as cash machines, websites, self-service checkouts), and other tangible element within a set period of time. Because of the intangible nature of service, customers often rely on cues to help them determine the capability of the firm in delivering quality service. Service encounter is significant part of the service delivery process in which customers make vital decisions regarding a firm’s level of service quality. Service encounter encompasses face to face interactions, phone call interactions and interaction with the physical elements of the service such as a customer interaction with a website. A firm’s contact employees and its physical facilities are often the only cues available for customers. Hence, in service settings customer satisfaction is often influenced by the quality of interactions between the customers and the contact employees and/or the physical facilities of the service firm. From the

customer's perspective, the most immediate evidence of service occurs in the service encounter when the customer interacts with the firm. The cost of not attaining an excellent performance during the service encounter is the cost of quality. This cost of quality covers the cost associated with compensating for the poor service or redoing the service, lost customers, negative word of mouth and decreased employee's self-efficacy, morale and confidence. Just as customers look for cues to help them determine a firm's capability in delivering good service quality, employees also look frequently for cues to help them facilitate their interaction with customers and also to be used by the firm in making decisions. From the cues the employees get, they are able to adjust their behaviour in order to improve customer satisfaction.

Service encounter often is the focal point in consumer evaluation of a firm's service. The truth of the assumption has been widely proven in service quality literature where service encounters influence customers' service quality perception (Bitner, 1994; Wong, 2004). Service encounter has been found to be an important factor in high levels of service quality delivery (Seiders et al, 2007; Wangenheim et al. 2007). Since customer contact employees have frequent contact with customers, they are always in the best position to understand customers' needs than others in the firm. Hence, open communication should be encouraged between customer contact employees and managers as the information gathered by customer contact employees during the service encounter will be utilised in making strategic decisions especially decision to do with new service development and service modification. Furthermore, many researchers report a positive relationship between the perceptions of customer contact employees and customers service quality perceptions (Burke et al, 1992; Schneider et al. 1998; Schneider and Bowen, 2009). However, firms should caution against over reliance on contact employees' interpretations of customer satisfaction. Brown and Swartz (1989) argue that contact employees may not be as accurate in their assessment of customer expectations and satisfaction. Supporting the argument of Brown and Swartz (1989), Rhee and Rha (2009) also

claim that employees often fail to accurately assess customers perceptions of specific quality attributes.

2.2.1 Service quality

To maximise customer satisfaction, Service providers provide consumers with a service and customers, in return, make decisions about the service offered that are likely to impact their overall service quality assessment. The quality of the service is then the overall perception by the customer of the relative inferiority / superiority of the service offered (Muala, 2016). It is the overall evaluation of a service by the customer (Eshghi et al, 2008) and it is a valuable tool for sustaining competitive advantage. Whereas the perceived quality of service is defined as a consequence of the contrast between the expectations of a service delivery process and the actual outcome of the service (Lovelock and Wirtz, 2011). In the services marketing literature, some definitions equate this notion to that of an attitude. Parasuraman et al (1988) define the perceived quality of service as a global decision or attitude relating to its supremacy. Similarly, it is defined by Castleberry and McIntyre (2011) as a belief or attitude about the extent of excellence of a service.

The importance of providing excellent service is steadily increasing. Hence, in order to achieve competitive advantage, customer satisfaction and loyalty, service providers strive to enhance the quality of their services. The main goal of each service provider should be to please customers by offering quality services, as research has shown that unhappy customers of a service spread their experiences to friends and families and even to strangers by leaving reviews online.

2.2.2 Measuring Service Quality (Service Quality Models)

The inherent characteristics of service have made it difficult to accurately measure service quality leading to marketing researchers debating on the preferred and most appropriate way of measurement. Some of the notable marketing researchers that have made a significant attempt to quantify this complex issue with the development of different measurable scales includes Cronin and Taylor (1992), Parasuraman et al (1985, 1988), Gronroos (1984) and so many others.

Gronroos Model (1984)

Gronroos identifies three components of service quality namely, functional, technical, and image. The technical quality refers to what the customers actually receive as a result of their interaction with the service provider and is vital to their assessment of the quality of services. functional quality refers to how the technical quality is delivered while image is built up mainly by technical and functional quality of a service in addition to other important factors such as public relation, pricing, culture and others.

Figure 2.1: Gronroos model of service quality. Gronroos (1984)

Though Gronroos model was first developed ahead of SEVQUAL and SERVPERF however, it has not been widely adopted by marketing practitioners. It has been subjected to series of criticism based on assumed difficulties faced in evaluating the technical quality component (Fiala, 2012). In the health sector for instance, patients may face difficulties in evaluating “what” service has been delivered (technical quality component) and only relying on “how” it’s delivered (functional). In this case the relationship with the nurse and the nurse’s empathy.

SERVQUAL

SERVQUAL model was introduced by Parasuraman et al (1985) to address the weaknesses of the Gronroos model which fails to consider customer expectations in measuring service quality. This model is based on a comparison of customer expectations and customer perceptions of actual service performance (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2003). That is finding the gaps that exist between what the customer expects and what was perceived of the actual service performance.

ServQual

Source: Zeithaml, Parasuraman & Berry, *Delivering Quality Service*

Figure 2.2: SERVQUAL model of service quality. Parasuraman et (1988)

The customer expectation-management perception gap (knowledge gap) is represented by Gap 1. Gap 2 reflects the perception of management - service quality specifications gap (the policy gap). Gap 3 reflects the specifications for service quality - service delivery gap (the delivery gap). The service delivery-external communication gap (the communications gap) is represented by Gap 4. Gap 5 reflects the expected service-perceived performance gaps (the service quality gap). This model was developed through the findings of exploratory research consisting of in-depth executive interviews and interviews with focus groups. The results showed that the high and low quality of service depends on how customers perceive the actual performance in terms of their expectations, and gap 5 reflects this expected service – perceived service gap.

The SERVQUAL model identifies five dimensions of service quality – tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy (Parasuraman et al, 1988). Tangibles represents the physical evidence of the service such as facilities, equipment tools, and physical appearance of employees. Reliability concerns employee's ability to properly perform a service and also provide the exact service promised to customers. Responsiveness refers to the employee's willingness and courtesy in helping customers, and their ability to perform services quickly. Assurance relates to the ability of the staff to inspire or create customer confidence in the service offered. The professionalism and capabilities of the employee influences customers' attitudes toward this factor (Zeithaml et al, 2006). Empathy deals with showing care and providing individualised attention to customers (Abubakar, 2016). Empathy plays a key role especially in the health and hospitality sector but less role in sectors such as telecommunication and Pay Tv due to the less customer-service provider contact.

Though SERVQUAL model has been widely applied in so many sectors such as banking, education, telecommunication and many others to measure service quality (Bahia and Nantel, 2000; Ramseook-Munhurrum et al, 2010; Abubakar, 2016). However, it has been widely

criticised. Richard and Allaway (1993) criticised the SERVQUAL for not considering the outcome quality of a service as done by Gronroos model. The authors argued that process and outcome predict service quality better than outcome or process alone (Richard and Allaway, 1993). However, in a response to this criticism, Zeithaml et al (2006) argued that the reliability dimension incorporates the outcome quality. It has also been criticised based on its methodology of measuring expectations and perceptions separately (Cronin and Taylor, 1992; Buttle, 1996). They argue that there is no need of measuring the expectation of consumers as the perception measures are more than appropriate (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). Evaluating the gap between perception and expectation is not psychometrically able to attain greater assessment of the quality of a service (Seth et al, 2005; Brady and Cronin, 2001). Others argue that this model is unsuitable for service areas such as retail store environment (Dabholkar et al, 1996). As a response to the limitations identified in SERVQUAL, Cronin and Taylor (1992) developed a perception only model, SERVPERF for measuring service quality while Dabholkar et al (1996) developed a model for measuring service quality in retail store environment.

Some critics also disputes the generalizability of the SERVQUAL dimensions across industries (Sohn and Tadisina, 2008). They argue that since industry characteristics also affects service quality, the SERVQUAL model must be adjusted to suit the various sectors. In response to this, some researchers have gone ahead to identify industry specific dimensions (Mei et al, 1999; Dabholkar et al, 1996; Saleh and Ryan; 1991; Knustone et al, 1990). Despite these numerous criticisms, the SERVQUAL is still increasingly adopted by researchers and practitioners.

SERVPERF

In response to the limitations of the SERVQUAL scale, Cronin and Taylor (1992) developed the SERVPERF scale as a performance only model for service quality measurement. Cronin

and Taylor (1992) refined the SERVQUAL model by getting rid of the expectation factor and retaining the performance factor as the only factor that needs to be measured for service quality. In response to the limitations of the SERVQUAL scale, Cronin and Taylor (1992) developed the SERVPERF scale as a performance only model for service quality measurement. Cronin and Taylor (1992) refined the SERVQUAL model by getting rid of the expectation factor and retaining the performance factor as the only factor that needs to be measured for service quality. The conceptualization of the SERVQUAL scale and its association with consumer satisfaction and purchasing intentions were explored by these researchers. They argued that service quality is a form of customer attitude and that only service quality measurement of performance is a better method of measuring service quality than performance measurement of expectation. Their results dispute SERVQUAL for confounding customer satisfaction with the attitude of the customer. They argued that the measure of satisfaction and service quality, which is viewed as an attitude, was complicated by the expectation variable included in SERVQUAL (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). Oliver (1981) was the first person to distinguish the essence of satisfaction from attitude by pointing out that attitude is the comparatively lasting affective orientation of the customer towards a product, shop, or procedure, while satisfaction is the emotional reaction following an experience of disconfirmation that acts on the lowest attitude level at the level of the base attitude and is unique to individual transactions. Therefore, the distinction between satisfaction and attitude is the same as the distinction between perceived quality of service and satisfaction, as an attitude is characterized as perceived quality of service (Oliver and Linda, 1981). Since the consumer's attitude is the center of service quality, the perception-only product attributes to measuring service quality is more suitable than the expectation-perception model. Cronin and Taylor (1992) argued that service quality is a consumer's attitude and the performance of the service is the only measurement for the quality of service. Even Zeithaml (one of the proponents of the SERVQUAL model) and her colleagues found that service quality

is affected by perceptions only (Boulding et al, 1993). Their findings strengthened the popularity of the SERVPERF scale in the service literature. The 22 items and 5 dimensions of SERVQUAL (tangibility, responsiveness, reliability, empathy and assurance) are retained in the SERVPERF scale. The only difference being that only perception scores are considered instead of expectation – perception difference.

Service Quality in the Hotel industry and the industry-Specific Measures

For the success of hotels, service quality is important. Service quality perception and guest satisfaction and loyalty is highly correlated. The greater a visitor's opinion of the standard of service, the greater the possibility of that visitor returning to the hotel and spreading favorable word of mouth. Service quality is often evaluated in the hotel industry to assess consumer perceptions of the guest experience. It must be able to offer great service for a hotel to stay competitive and profitable as this creates customer satisfaction and repeats use. In order to maintain the standard of service delivery, hotels should continuously track guest perceptions of the quality of service.

Though most hotel managers adopt comment cards as a way to determine their guest perception of service quality, researchers have developed methods for measuring service quality that are validated to be more efficient and appropriate in evaluating the dimensions of service quality in both the hotel and other service industries (Keith and Simmers, 2013). Nonetheless, by presenting appropriate information at the time of the service interaction required to measure guest satisfaction with their hotel experience, comment cards also fit well into the hotel managers' analysis strategy (Keith and Simmers 2013; Borle et al, 2007).

While some of the proposed models are highly relevant and appropriate in many service industries to measure service quality, researchers have found that most of them cannot be generalized across all businesses (Seth et al, 2005). These researchers conclude that

organizations need to use a context-specific assessment of service quality to better grasp the perception of service quality by customers (Dagger et al, 2007). hence, some researchers have concentrated on developing service quality measurement scales specifically for assessing service quality in hotels.

Some of these studies also established dimensions of service quality that are different from SERVQUAL's five dimensions. Akan (1999) identified seven dimensions titled, accuracy of hotel reservations, solutions to problems, accuracy and speed of service, knowing and understanding the customer tangibles, communication and transactions, competence of personnel and courtesy while analyzing service quality dimensions in turkey four and five-star hotels. Mei et al (1999) analyzed the dimensions of service quality in the Australian hotel industry using the SERVQUAL instrument as a basis, after developing a new instrument called HOLSERV. Three service quality dimensions were identified by the researchers, namely reliability, tangibles and employees. In a research carried out in the US hotel market, Saleh and Ryan (1991) established five dimensions of service quality. These dimensions were different from those on the scale of SERVQUAL. They are empathy, avoid sarcasm, reassurance, tangibles and conviviality. Using SERVQUAL as the base, Knuston et al (1990) created LODGSERV. As the five dimensions in SERVQUAL are all preserved, it shares similarity with the SERVQUAL scale. In their study of service quality measurement in conference hotels in the UK, Oberoi and Hales (1990) established a two-dimensional understanding of service quality comprising of tangibles and intangibles. Ekinici et al (1998) also established a comparable two-dimensional structure, tangibles and intangibles while evaluating the SERVQUAL instrument in two seaside Turkish resorts. Eight dimensions of service quality were defined by Webster and Hung (1994), namely convenience, understanding, security, responsiveness, communication, reliability and tangibles. Using SERVQUAL as a base, Akbaba (2006) established five dimensions of service quality that represent the evaluative

criteria used by guests to evaluate the service quality of Turkish hotels called convenience, assurance, understanding and caring, adequacy in service supply and tangibles. The discrepancies found in the different studies in the dimensions of service quality suggest that great care must be taken in efforts to improve the quality of service in the hotel industry.

Justification of the Service Quality Model to be Adopted

The SERVQUAL scale would be the preferred scale because of its superior diagnostic power in implementing strategies relating to service quality deficiencies for potential intervention by managers (Jain and Gupta, 2004). One would assume that the inclusion of expectation scores offers richer knowledge than that given by the perception-only scores (SERVPERF), thereby contributing to the diagnostic capacity of the quality of the service scale (SERVQUAL). In addition, Cronin and Taylor (1992), who created the performance-only scale, never indicated that measuring customer expectations in service quality research is unnecessary. Therefore, SERVQUAL is a better option for SERVPERF from a diagnostic point of view, as it requires a clear comparison of service performance with customer expectation and thus offers a more realistic diagnosis of shortcomings in service quality.

However, because of its psychometric robustness and greater instrument parsimoniousness, SERVPERF is the preferred alternative, unlike SERVQUAL scale, which involves gigantic data collection tasks where the researcher is required to collect data on customer expectations and perceptions of the performance of an organization on each of the 22 service quality scale attitudes which is time consuming and adds no additional information beyond that which is obtained from performance perceptions alone (Brady et al, 2002). SERVPERF has also been shown to be superior to SERVQUAL for its ability to describe a greater proportion of variation in the overall service quality across a single-item scale, in addition to being more effective in minimizing the number of items to be assessed by half (Jain and Gupta, 2004). Some of the

researchers who compared the two scales of service quality found that the SERVPERF scale exceeded the SERVQUAL scale (Brady and Cronin, 2001; Babakus and Boller, 1992; Dabholkar et al, 2000) and Zeithaml (with her colleagues), one of SERVQUAL's members, reported that only perceptions directly affect perceived service quality (Boulding et al, 1993).

SERVQUAL's superior diagnostic capacity allows the identification of areas of a company's service quality deficiencies for managerial interventions. However, because of its psychometric robustness and instrument parsimoniousness, the SERVPERF scale is used in this study as the researcher is simply interested in determining the overall quality of services offered in the hotel industry.

The Link Between Employee and Customer Perceptions of Service Quality

Customer perceptions of service quality are subjective evaluations of a service experience during service encounters (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2003). It is the customer's beliefs concerning the received or experienced service (Parasuraman et al, 1991). The degree in which customers perceive every service's attributes directly affect their attitude when making an overall judgement about their experience of the quality of service delivered (Brida et al, 2016). Service employees are the most important factor in consumer perceptions of service quality (Hooper et al, 2013). Service employees have a dual role, they are service providers to external customers, but they are often internal customers who purchase internal services rendered in the service company by other individuals or divisions. The skills, attitudes and behaviors of employees are all decisive precursors to the retention and loyalty of future customers (Evans, 2018). In the hotel industry, the sustainability of a hotel depends heavily on the hotel staff providing excellent quality of service to internal and external customers. The quality of internal services provided will inspire employees to provide outstanding external customer services that could

increase the level of satisfaction of external customers and ultimately lead to a company's profitability and growth (Jung and Yoon, 2014).

Employees are considered critical components of external customers service because it has been accepted that happy employees appear to be more efficient (Chiang and Wu, 2014; Chen, 2016). Because of the growing competition in the service industries, firms are starting to realize the importance of building service and quality from within. Most of these organizations are now introducing service and quality initiatives aimed at improving their employees' skills and expertise to increase the quality of internal service, contributing to the satisfaction and loyalty of employees (Nazeer, Zahid and Azeem, 2014). Competition is becoming fierce in the hospitality industry. Hence businesses rely so much on their contact staff to provide high quality of service to external customers. Companies tend to treat their workers well for them to reciprocate by treating customers positively as a strategic tool aimed at achieving a competitive edge in the industry (Pfeffer, 2005).

Similarly, employees engage in several service encounters with customers to fulfil the various needs they have in the process of doing their work. These internal service encounters include relationship between customer-contact staff and back-room staff, relationship between managers and customer-contact staff, relationship between managers and back-room staff, and relationship between the head office and each division for large organizations (Evans, 2018). In a company, any employee or department serves as an internal supplier within the company to customers (i.e., other parties) who receive products or services from them. In the hospitality industry, for instance, the kitchen department cooks food to be sent to the restaurant. For food processing, the maintenance staffs repair equipment in the kitchen. Staff from one unit may also depend on peers from other units to provide inputs and data for the provision of reliable and effective customer service (Chiu et al, 2014). A kitchen staff may be seen as the waiters' supplier; in essence, a waiter may be considered the kitchen staff's internal customer. Similarly,

the kitchen staff is considered to be an internal customer for the procurement staff. If everyone in the service chain aims to provide outstanding service to their internal customers, then great service will also be provided to external customers. If the expectation of a participant within the chain has not been met, then issues often arise at one stage in the service chain. For example, a waiter will not serve people lined up for their food in the hotel restaurant if the kitchen staff are not quick enough to prepare food. Similarly, in the banking sector, a bank teller cannot service customers easily and effectively in his or her line if information technology workers fail to give excellent computer system support to the teller.

A prerequisite for effective encounters with external customers is the relationships between workers within an organization (Schlesinger and Heskett, 1994). High standards of internal service quality from colleagues are expected and demanded by employees, just as with external customers. Similarly, when their expectations are not properly addressed, they appear to be dissatisfied and this could eventually lead to job dissatisfaction for employees. The needs and desires of the employees must first be met for the needs and desires of the customers to be fulfilled. Employees must be happy with the internal service quality they obtain from their employer in order for them to be able to provide high quality service to customers (Chiang and Wu, 2014). Thus, satisfied employees are a crucial requirement for satisfying customers.

2.2.5 Customer Oriented boundary Spanning Behaviours (COBSBs)

The significance of customer contact employees for organisational effectiveness is uncontested by managers and researchers alike (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Larkin and Larkin, 1996). Firms are beginning to recognise that eliciting more customer-oriented behaviours from employees is critical in the delivery of high-quality customer services (Schneider and White, 2004). Service quality rests heavily on the effectiveness with which customer contact employees interact with customers in service encounters. Hence, customer contact employees are caught

in the middle of a “three cornered fight” in which the customer (demanding attention and service quality) and the organisation (demanding efficiency and productivity) are at the two ends (Singh, 2000).

The importance of customer contact employees in service delivery implies that organisation must carefully manage the types of behaviours that these employees display to ensure they engage in behaviours that will derive high customer service quality and satisfaction (Morrison, 1996). However, due to the non-standardization and intangibility of service, it is difficult to formally specify all these behaviours. Researchers have argued that empirical studies in service marketing need to focus more on customer and service-oriented behaviours of customer contact employees (Mackenzie, 1997; Borman and Motowidlo, 1993). They further maintained that service firms have special requirements or dimensions specifically related to dealing with customers (Borman and Motowidlo, 1993; Podsakoff and Mackenzie, 1997).

As Zeithaml et al (1996) acknowledged, “service quality heavily depends on the performance of customer contact employees” (p.35). hence, the role the customer contact employees play in linking the organisation to its customers should not be understated (Bettencourt and Brown, 2003). In light of this, researchers in the service marketing literature suggested three key dimensions of customer-oriented boundary spanning behaviours (COBSBs) of customer contact employees that contributes to the growth of market driven organisational capabilities (Bettencourt et al, 2001).

First, customer contact employees play an important role in being a good representative of the organisation to outsiders (including customers) and improving the organisation’s image and legitimacy through their advocacy of the organisation (including their products and services) this is referred to as external representation. Secondly, due to the boundary spanning position of customer contact employees, more opportunities are provided to them to internally share

information about the ever-evolving customer needs and possible improvements in service quality delivery. This is referred to as internal influence behaviours. Finally, service quality perceptions and customer satisfaction largely depend on customer contact employees service delivery behaviours such as courtesy, personal attentiveness, responsiveness and keeping promises. Referred to as service delivery behaviours which is the key focus of this study.

Service delivery behaviours are relatively more role prescribed due to their frequent specification in job descriptions, training materials and performance review forms. While external representation and internal influence behaviours are more likely to be relatively extra-role or discretionary (Bettencourt and Brown, 2003). Nevertheless, the gap between the role prescribed/ extra-role behaviours is likely to be blurred for customer contact employees and organisations due to difficulty in precisely specifying customer contact employees' behaviours as they interact with customers (Hartline et al, 2000).

External representation:

Customer contact employees exhibit external representation by being vocal advocates of the organisation's image, products and services to outsiders (Bettencourt and brown, 2003; Bettencourt et al, 2001). By exhibiting these behaviours, they tend to speak in favour of the organisation to people outside of the organisation with the intention of creating a positive image (Bettencourt and brown, 1997). Other researchers such as Sun et al (2007) and Maxham, et al (2008) have applied the measures developed by Bettencourt et al (2001) in their studies which have demonstrated good statistical performance.

Internal influence:

Employees display internal influence behaviours by individually taking initiatives in communicating to both the management and colleagues to enhance service performance and

delivery by everybody in the firm including themselves (Bettencourt and Brown, 2003). They suggest creative ideas for improving the firm's services. Such employees cooperate with their colleagues or teams by sharing ideas among themselves that will improve the firm's services. Just like external representation, the measures developed by Bettencourt et al (2003) for internal influence have been used and shown to perform well in a limited number of studies (Sun et al, 2007; Maxham et al, 2008).

Service delivery behaviours:

Service delivery behaviours refers to customer contact employees serving customers in a conscientious, attentive, responsive, courteous and adaptive manner. Service marketing researchers have argued adaptive employee behaviours results in higher levels of customer service quality perceptions (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Gwinner et al, 2005). Another set of researchers have argued that quality of customer contact employees' behaviour can result to higher levels of customer service quality perceptions (Singh, 2000; Bettencourt and Brown, 1997). Similarly, to the other two dimensions, some researchers have also applied the measures developed by Bettencourt et al (2001) for service delivery behaviours in their studies and the performance have been good (Sun et al, 2007; Netameyer and Maxham, 2007; Maxham et al, 2008).

Arguably, customer-oriented boundary spanning behaviours (COBSBs) include both in-role (service delivery) and extra role behaviours (external representation and internal influence) of service employees. However, for the purpose of this study, focus will be directed specifically at in-role behaviours as they are more critical for customer contact employees especially concerning behaviours that directly impact customers (Farrell, 2008). With regards to customer customer-contact employees service delivery behaviours, researchers have investigated the

following antecedents: role ambiguity and role conflict (Bettencourt and brown, 2003), job satisfaction (Bettencourt et al, 2001) and organisational support practices (Sun et al, 2007).

2.2.6 Customer Orientation of Service Employees

Due to the interactive nature of services, customers often rely on service employee's behaviour when judging a service quality. Service firm's economic performance partly depends on the employee's level of customer orientation (Bove & Johnson, 2000). Customer orientation is defined as an employee's propensity or tendency to fulfil or satisfy customer needs (Brown et al, 2002). Brown et al (2002) conceptualize customer orientation as two-dimensional model composed of (a) a needs dimension covering the employee's belief that he or she can fulfil customers' needs and requests, and (b) an enjoyment dimension representing the extent to which the employee enjoys interactions with customers. A three-dimensional conceptualization was introduced by Hennig-Thurau and Thurau (2003). This model consists of (a) an employee's customer-oriented skills (b) an employee's motivation to serve customers, and (c) an employee's self-perceived decision-making authority. This three-dimensional structure is based on the requirements that must be met by service employees to satisfy the needs of the customers during service encounter. Though Donovan et al (2004) adopts Brown et al (2002) definition of customer orientation, they however contradict Brown et al (2002) two-dimensional conceptualization of customer orientation with a five-dimensional model which encompasses (a) need to pamper (b) need to read the customer (c) need for personal relationship (d) need to deliver and (e) need to communicate. Regrettably these researchers couldn't provide an in-depth information on the process of the derivation of the dimensional structure. It has long been agreed that firms focusing on their customers' needs are better positioned to achieve long term success than firms wholly focusing on profits. Firms that have a more customer centric approach tend to be more profitable as they keep their existing customers satisfied and attracts new customers. However, for a firm's service employees to be effectively customer-

oriented, managers must display commitment to ensuring the delivery of service quality and customer satisfaction.

2.2.7 Different Factors that Affect Customer Service Quality in the Nigerian Hospitality Sector and the Importance of Leadership.

Leadership behaviour of hotel owners/managers play a key role in influencing positive service behaviours among customer contact employees in service encounters by minimising or maximising the effects of some salient factors that affect customer service quality in the Nigerian hospitality. These factors include empowerment, service training, service reward and availability of adequate facilities.

Empowerment is vital in the hospitality sector as contact employees require the freedom and flexibility to make immediate and instant independent decisions in service encounters to totally satisfy hotels guests and positively influence their perception (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Clark et al, 2009, Ayupp and Chung, 2010; Bello & Bello, 2017). In the Nigerian hospitality, hotel staff are infamous for their significant delays in promptly responding to hotel guests requests such as change of rooms, cancellation or refund requests, changes in reservations and so much more. This might be due to lack of self-determination, confidence and excessive control and authority from the manger. The failure to respond quickly to customer requests results to negative perception of the service quality (Parasuraman et al, 1988, Gill et al, 2010; Jauhari et al, 2017). Customer contact employees should be given the power or authority to adapt their behaviours to the demands of each and every service encounter. Hartline and Ferrell (1996) affirm that empowerment removes the constraints imposed on customer contact employees and gives them the room to manoeuvre as they attempt to serve customer needs. However, Lee (1989) argues against granting contact employees the freedom of adapting their role in service encounters to meet customers' needs as the role may be very demanding on contact employees, especially the less experienced ones; the more flexible the role, the more ambiguous the role,

and consequently, the more anxious one can become which might affect performance in service encounters. Nevertheless, empowerment coupled with the right training can mitigate this concern (Bello and Bello, 2017; Gill et al, 2010). Thus, a hotel owner/manager has a key role to play to ensure that his/her staff are empowered. He/she should adopt a leadership style that is suitable in empowering employees to confidently respond to all customer requests as quickly as possible.

Service Training: as the primary products in the travel and hospitality sector are intangibles, the role that human element perform in service delivery becomes even more critical for growth and profitability (Nwosu, 2016). A major key point in Nigeria's tourism master plan that relates to human capital emphasizes the lack of quality, standards and skills (UNWTO, 2006). Though the unemployment is increasing on a daily basis, the number of skilled people suitable for the industry is very insufficient. According to Fajana (2009) "Nigeria has abundant labour and scarce talent". There are more than enough people to take up the jobs but these people have the insufficient knowledge and skills needed to deliver efficient and effective service. The abundance of superior knowledge and skills in any organisation leads to higher productivity and performance (Cook et al, 2011; Powell, 2002).

Due to the chronic shortage of qualified people in the hospitality sector in Nigeria, big brands and international hotels have resort to expatriate recruitment particularly in executive management and in the food & beverage department (Ogunyemi and Nwosu, 2015; Bello and Bello, 2017). An effective service training program is necessary to improve the staff behaviour and contribute to positive behaviour in service encounters (Aguinis and Kraiger, 2009; Dhar, 2015; Wang et al, 2016; Casal et al, 2019). Cheap labour characterised by unqualified employees is common among small indigenous hotel enterprises in Nigeria. Some of the customer contact employees possess ugly unfriendly behaviour such as discourteousness, irascibility and repugnance. Such behaviour negatively affects a hotel guest service experience

in service encounters. As the leader, a hotel owner/manager has a key role to play in making sure that the staff are properly trained to improve their behaviour in service encounters for a positive customer service experience. Nwosu (2016) has provided a descriptive profile of the human capital in the travel and hospitality sector in Nigeria using data collected from a hospitality training provider (Wavecrest College of Hospitality) which is shown in table below. Given the significant characteristics of each group of people in this profile, it could aid hotel owners in developing effective recruitment and development strategies.

Profile	Key characteristics
The owner/manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Little or no professional knowledge of the industry and best practices Seen as a business venture or personal hobby Profit-gains impact more on business decisions Prone to owner interference when the management function has been delegated
The expatriate manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More often than not, comes from a brand tradition Possess specialist skills and international experience Mainly from Western Europe, the Middle East and South Africa
The repatriate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hospitality-related qualifications obtained overseas International exposure
The graduate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heightened sense of professionalism Obtained tourism or hospitality qualifications locally Little or no exposure to best practices Lacks any skill specialisation Disinclined to take up first line positions Needs a reorientation and motivation
The career changer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moving in from other professions Enthusiastic about the industry No requisite knowledge or experience but motivated to learn Very high expectations about their ability to perform
The job seeker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Young and unemployed Transient and in search of a university admission Has only received on-the-job training Frequent job hopping for better opportunities

Figure 2.3: Descriptive model of human capital profile in the Nigerian hospitality sector (Nwosu, 2016)

Service Reward: a good service reward system that promotes appreciation and recognition of excellent performances motivates employee's commitment to organisational goals (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Clark et al, 2009; Chang and Birtch, 2011). Nigerian hotel workers are often badly rewarded, badly paid, made to work long hours and not offered much scope for pay or career progression (Nwosu, 2016; Bello and Bello, 2017). These hotel owners forgot that when

employees are rewarded accordingly, they reciprocate by treating the customers well. Financial and non-financial rewards such as recognitions and respect at the workplace can increase the employee behaviour and attitude in service encounters to provide higher quality services (Sun et al, 2011; Ueno, 2012; Kim and Lee, 2013). Appreciation and recognition of excellent performances motivates employees' commitment to organisational goals. Rewarding and recognising excellent service are highly related to customer satisfaction with service quality (Johnson, 1996; Nitu and Papori, 2014; Shahzad and Jehanzeb, 2013). Rewarding service employees for excellence tend to increase their productivity (Kaufman, 1992; Karami et al, 2013). Clear, specific reward programs such as promotion and bonus influence service-oriented behaviour of customer contact employees. Rewards generates reciprocity or equity thriving behaviours by recipients according to social exchange theory (Lee, 2006)

Adequate facilities: there is a negative impact on the delivery of service if working conditions are bad. Employees and work environment is interrelated. They will work hard and enhance performance given that they have adequate facilities. The unavailability of adequate facilities common with the Nigerian hospitality sector such as unreliable power supply, poor communication and internet system and irregular water supply can also affect a hotel staff performance in service encounters.

As the leader, the hotel manager is ultimately in charge of all aspects of the running of the hotel and has a big role to play to ensure that employees are empowered, receive the necessary trainings, get recognised for achievements and have adequate facilities. Hence, these factors are still linked to the leader's attitude and commitment to delivering service quality to customers. This then led to the next section that provides a comprehensive and in depth understanding of leadership, highlighting various leadership behaviours and the importance of these behaviours in the productivity and performance of service employees.

2.3 The Development of Leadership Research

Leadership has been of immense significant in recent years, however there is no agreed definition for the term (Bush, 2003; Li and Sun, 2015; Adanri and Thakkar, 2016; Northouse, 2016). Leadership has been defined differently by different scholars. While some scholars conceptualize leadership from the trait perspective where a leader is seen to possess some certain distinctive characteristics or traits that enables him/her to lead effectively to achieve the desired goal other scholars argues that the behaviour of a leader is the key factor for accomplishing the desired goals (Northouse, 2016). Leadership is defined as a process whereby followers are influenced by a leader towards accomplishing a shared goal (Walker and Dimmock, 2005; Northouse, 2016). The above definition clearly shows that leadership is centred on three key elements which includes, influencing followers, team working and shared objectivities.

Leadership scholars have been developing theories to explain a leader's role in managing organisational change within the past two decades (Balkundi and Kilduff, 2005; Hannah et al, 2011). Early researchers on leadership focused upon the traits and personality of leaders (Bolden et al 2012). Later on, theorists shifted their focus towards the behaviour of leaders (Northouse, 2016). More recently, a lot of focus have been geared towards understanding the contextual nature of leadership and the role of the followers (Bolden et al 2012).

Despite the growing diversity in leadership theories developed by these scholars, we cannot deny the existence of significant challenges that comes with this intense emergence of new theoretical perspectives in leadership. New theories are being churned out with little or no attempt at comparing the validity of the existing ones (Al-Matari et al, 2016). There is lack of an integrated understanding of leadership and this can be attributed to the disparity of the approaches (Lee et al, 2011). Most of these leadership approaches are classified according to

the primary focus which could be on power-influence, traits, behaviour or situational factors interacting with power, traits or behaviour (Northouse, 2016).

The Power-Influence Approach

Studies investigating the power approach marks the beginning of the research into leadership. These studies attempt to give an explanation of leadership effectiveness based on the magnitude of power possessed by a leader, the type of power possessed and how such power is exercised (Northouse, 2016). One cannot underestimate the importance of power in influencing not only subordinates but also peers, supervisors and other organisation's stakeholders such as clients and suppliers. Some of these researchers also argued that there are some heritable attributes associated with some leaders (Shaw and Stogdill 1974; Kirkpatrick and Locke, 1991; Boyce et al, 2010). Hence sparking off the search for heritable attributes that differentiates leaders from non-leaders (Abdalla and Al-Homoud, 2001; Judge et al, 2002; Bono and Judge, 2004). These set of theorists believe that leaders are born but not made and they possess certain extraordinary abilities such as irresistible persuasive power and tireless energy.

The Trait Approach

Most leadership scholars established that individual features such as abilities, skills, personality traits and even demographics predicts individual's effectiveness as a leader (Mumford et al, 2007; Bono and Judge, 2004; Judge et al, 2002). The following traits were listed by Stogdill (1948) in his first research on leadership traits; sociability, self-confidence, persistence, initiative, responsibility, insight, alertness and intelligence. In his second research, Stogdill added achievement, tolerance and cooperativeness to the list (Stogdill, 1974). The traits that differentiate leaders from non-leaders revealed by Mann (1959) differs from those of Stogdill (1974). These traits include intelligence, masculinity, adjustment, dominance, extraversion and conservation. After a thorough review of Mann (1959) research findings on leadership traits,

Lord et al (1986) concluded that only intelligence, masculinity and dominance are the three most effective traits distinguishing leaders from non-leaders. This is also at variance with the findings of Kirkpatrick and Locke (1991), which revealed that drive, the desire to lead, honesty/integrity, self-confidence, cognitive ability, and knowledge of business are the distinctive traits. 13 years later, Zaccaro et al (2004) demonstrated that social capacities, motivation, cognitive abilities, personality & disposition, and leader expertise and tacit knowledge are the key distinctive characteristics of successful leaders.

One key criticism of the trait approach is that determination of traits or characteristics which defines a leader is subjective. Findings of the numerous studies are generally inconsistent (Bolden et al 2012; Northouse, 2016; Yukl and Van Fleet, 1982). Despite the large amount of research on this topic there is still no agreed universal set of leadership characteristics that defines a leader (Bolden et al, 2012; Morhart et al, 2011; Northouse, 2016). There is no established or generally accepted list of characteristics or traits identified that could be common to all leaders. Some characteristics found by some researchers may be lacking in some leaders however the absence of these characteristics doesn't mean such individual is not anymore, a leader (Bolden et al, 2012). In addition, Northouse (2016) argues that the trait approach doesn't take situation into approach and cannot be utilised in the training and development of leaders.

The Behavioural Approach

Research into behavioural approach emerged due to the increasing critiques of the trait paradigm (Burns, 2012), which prompted academics to look beyond the individual characteristics of leaders and explore how leaders' behaviours predicts effectiveness. These studies attempt to explain what leaders actually do on their job and the relationship between the leader's behaviour and leadership effectiveness (Northouse, 2016). It is hugely concerned with the activities that are synonymic with the works of managers (Mann, 2006). Some of these

activities involves oral interactions with the stakeholders which provides opportunity for the collection of relevant up to date information, discussion of problems and influencing people for plan implementation (Bolden et al, 2009). The behavioural paradigm has provided the basis for the emergence of new theories such as transformational and transactional leadership theories (Antonakis et al, 2003; Avolio et al, 1999) which place emphases on the importance of recognition and appropriate rewards (Transactional) and empowerment of subordinates (Transformational). However, some other researchers are focused on understanding the role of the contextual nature of the leadership. This led to development of the contingency theories of leadership (Hollander et al, 1973; Hersey and Blanchard 1988).

The Situational/Contingency Approach

These researchers argued that leadership behaviour and styles cannot be uniformly effective in every situation as those styles and behaviours vary according to the tasks, the environment or context or individuals or followers (Northouse, 2016). The behavioural leadership theory fails to take into consideration various situational factors that may affect a leader's behaviour (Yun et al, 2006). These contingency theories such as Fiedler, 1967 contingency theory and Hersey and Blanchard, 1988 leadership theory focuses on developing leaders through the provision of effective training in addition to fostering an organisational environment that provides a smooth-running ground for the trained leaders to perform (Bolden et al, 2009). This approach emphasizes on the importance of factors such as nature of the external environment, nature of the work carried out by the leader's unit and the leader's activity. However, Despite being positioned as a generalizable solution, the contingency theory cannot be applied constantly across varied situations. A leader that is effective in one situation due to the development of the organisational environment to enable his performance may fail to effectively perform in a different situation (Yun et al, 2006).

2.3.1 The New Leadership Approaches

In the 1970s, the work on charismatic leadership (House, 1997) and on transactional and transformational leadership (Burns, 1978) fuelled a paradigm shift in leadership research giving rise to what is now known as the “New leadership” approaches (Bryman, 1992). This shift in paradigm spurred an increase in empirical research and the development of more comprehensive theories (Conger, 1999). Leadership entails developing a vision along with strategies necessary to produce the desired changes required to achieve a goal (Pahl and Hamid, 2015). Leadership style/approach is a leader’s manner and approach of providing direction, implementing plans and motivating people (Babalola, 2016). It has been generally accepted that employee’s behaviour and attitudes can be affected by leadership styles (Zeithaml and Bitner, 1996; Clark et al, 2009). Some of these new leadership approaches are very much common and effective in western organisations. These include transformational leadership transactional, laissez fare, democratic, and servant leadership styles.

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is one of the most current and popular approaches of leadership. It is part of the “New leadership” theories focusing more on the charismatic and the affective elements of leadership (Bryman, 1992) and has attracted a lot attention from leadership researchers since the beginning of the 1980s (Northouse, 2016). The research on transformational leadership theory is increasingly growing not only in business and management but also in a wide range of fields such as nursing, engineering, education and psychology (Antonakis, 2012).

Transformational leadership is where a leader works with subordinates to identify needed change, creating a vision to guide the change through inspiration, and executing the change in tandem with committed members of a group (Bass, 1998). Transformational leaders utilise four

factors in leading their subordinates. These factors include idealised influence or charisma, inspiration, intellectual stimulation and individualised consideration (Bass et al, 2009). Idealised influence relates to where the leader displays appealing and admirable behaviour that influences followers to identify with the leaders. These leaders are charismatic and are well respected. Inspiration relates to the extent to which the leader put forward a vision that is inspiring to the followers. Intellectual stimulation is the extent to which these leaders' challenges assumptions, engage in risk taking and solicits subordinates' ideas. They tend to stimulate and encourage subordinates to be creative and innovative thinkers. Individualised consideration is when the leader acts as a mentor, paying attention to the needs and concerns of each follower. Though it has been empirically supported that transformational leadership positively influences followers and organisational performance (Northouse, 2016). However, it has some notable limitations. Yukl (1999) noted an overlap between the constructs of idealised influence and inspiration. The critics argues that these two dimensions are highly correlated and not clearly differentiated from each other (Li and Shi, 2008). Furthermore, transformational leadership can also be abused by leaders especially those taking advantage of the charisma factor hence influencing their followers towards immoral visions. Example of leaders that have abused this factor include Adolf Hitler and Osama bin Laden.

Dow and Downton (1974) first introduced the concept of transformational leadership. Later, Burns (1978) contributed hugely in the study of transformational leadership (Burns, 2012). Transformational leadership is a process which transforms followers, involves emotions, values, ethics, standards and long-term goals, and uplifts the morale and motivation level among the leader and the followers (Northouse, 2016). It is a process whereby the leader engages with his subordinates to form a mutual connection that increases the level of motivation and morality among the leader and the followers (Avolio et al, 1999). Therefore, transformational style of leadership is associated with change whereby the leader comes up

with ground-breaking initiatives/activities and transmutes the status quo to the desired level. Such leader has the ability of transforming an organisation's vision, strategy and culture while also promoting innovation (Antonakis and House, 2014). Such leaders transform organisations from the status quo to the desired future state (Pantouvakis and Patsiouras, 2016) and they don't offer any tangible incentives to followers in order to influence them towards committing to the change process (Jabnoun and Juma, 2005). They look beyond the single exchange process with their followers common with transactional leaders rather they set off the change process based on their personal values, beliefs and qualities (Park,2016). They tend to convince their followers through extraordinary effort, motivation and self-sacrifice to attain a significant higher personal performance level doing more than they originally thought they could do (Park, 2016). Bringing such changes in their followers and the organisation is made possible through idealised influence (charisma), inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation or individualised consideration. These four behaviours make up the four dimensions of transformational leadership (Bass, 1998; Avolio et al 1999; Northouse, 2016). Idealised influence relates to the extent to which the leader engages in behaviours that encourages followers to identify with him/her (Leithwood and Jantzi, 2005). Inspiration relates to the degree to which a leader put forward a vision meant to inspire the followers (Mitchell and Boyle, 2009). Intellectual stimulation relates to the extent a leader challenges existing assumption and encourages others to take risks while individual consideration deals with the extent to which a leader seeks to meet the individual needs of his/her subordinates (Pahl and Hamid, 2015; Northouse, 2016). Transformational leadership empowers, motivates and elevate their subordinates through the use of these four dimensions.

One good example of a transformational leader is Steve Jobs. Steve Jobs vision, creativity, drive and determination transformed apple Inc on his second return as the CEO in 1997, twelve years after he was ousted in 1985. During this second tenure, Steve Jobs transformed Apple

Inc from a loss-making company to one of the most profitable companies of our time. Jobs changed the company's vision, strategy and corporate culture. His vision for Apple was to offer customers a better version of an already existing product (Isaacson and Baker, 2011). Though, this sounds practically impossible as at then however, he was able to influence his employees towards the achievement of the vision. He had immense charisma and was respected and admired by both peers and subordinates. Furthermore, Jobs also adapted his leadership style to fit certain situations, which in most cases turns out good as Fieldler (1967) contends, "the effectiveness of a leader depends on the fit match between his leadership style and the situation" (Northouse, 2016. p30). Jobs mixed his transformational leadership style with autocratic style of leadership because of his passion for perfection and his determination to bring forth a turnaround at Apple Inc (Isaacson and Baker, 2011).

Bass Model of Transformational Leadership

Bass (1985) further expanded and refined Burns (1978) transformational leadership approach by focusing more on the needs of followers rather than leader's needs, suggesting a possible application of transformational leadership in situations that presents negative outcomes and elaborating transformational and transactional leadership as a single continuum (Northouse, 2016). Bass model of leadership incorporates seven different factors or dimensions under transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership theories. Due to the scope of this literature, the focus will be on the 4 components of transformational leadership (individual consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation and Idealised influence). Transactional and laissez faire leader behaviours are not discussed.

Figure 0.4: Bass model of leadership. (Created by the researcher)

Idealised Influence (Charisma)

Known as the emotional component of leadership (Antonakis, 2012), idealised influence encompasses influence over ideology, influence over ideals and influence over “bigger than life issues” (Northouse, 2016). Idealised influence was conceived by Bass to replace charisma which Klein and House (1995) argues to be an all-inclusive term for transformational leadership. Since charisma can be linked to a wide variety of meanings such as flamboyant, celebrated, awe-inspiring and also hugely associated with dictatorial leaders such as Adolf Hitler, Idi Amin and Osama bin Laden, recent researchers contend to substitute charisma with idealised influence for a clearer understanding of the linkage to transformational leadership (Bass, 1999). Nevertheless, some scholars still use the term interchangeably.

Idealised influence behaviour makes transformational leaders role models for their followers (Hamad, 2015). These leaders are well appreciated, recognised and believed to be trustworthy due to their exceptional competence, persistence and will power (Avolio et al, 1999). They are seen as being always correct in decision making and very effective in communicating the vision

and mission (Northouse, 2016). The followers develop tremendous love and admiration for them, look up to them, copy their style and always tend to identify with them. This dimension is measured on two components\; a behavioural component that relates to followers' observations of leader behaviour and an attributional component associated to the characteristics that are ascribed to the leader by his/her followers (Bass and Riggio, 2014). Basically, this dimension describes special individuals who influence others to follow their vision. One individual that clearly exemplifies the idealised influence is Nelson Mandela, the first black president of South Africa. Nelson Mandela is viewed as a revolutionary leader with high moral standards and a vision for the eradication of racism and for the establishment of a constitutional democracy in which all citizens of South Africa had equal rights and where every adult would have the right to vote for the government of his or her choice. People responded well to his charismatic qualities and that helped transformed a whole nation. He was loved and admired all over the world for bringing an end to apartheid and healing the scars of a divided nation.

Inspirational Motivation

This dimension describes leaders that communicates high expectations to subordinates or followers, inspiring and motivating them to fully commit to the shared vision. They utilise emotional appeals and symbols to evoke the spirit of group in order to make them achieve more than expected (Northouse, 2016). A charismatic leader might be inspirational however an inspirational leader might not be charismatic (Bass and Riggio, 2014). Nevertheless, both dimensions focus on the personal development of subordinates or followers.

Intellectual Stimulation

This dimension relates to leadership that sparks creativity and innovative thinking in followers. It also encourages followers to challenge their own beliefs and values, that of the leader and

the organisation. It promotes creativity and innovative approaches to problem solving. Creative and innovative ideas from the followers are encouraged even if they contradict that of the leader (Bass and Riggio, 2014).

Individualised Consideration

A transformational leader plays the role of a mentor, acknowledging the differences in the followers' requirements and aspirations, and focusing upon their development and success (Antonakis et al, 2003). The behaviour such leaders develop for a particular follower might be at variance with another follower. This kind of leader-follower relationship fosters learning and growth of the followers through the maintenance of a two-way communication that binds leaders contact with followers, pay attention to their needs, delegate tasks with a follow up assessment and provide the necessary support when needed (Northouse, 2016). These leaders act as coaches and advisers while trying to assist subordinates in attaining their fullest potential (Li and Sun, 2015). This kind of transformational leadership behaviour is common with football coaches. Sir Alex Ferguson, the former manager of Manchester United is widely admired for his individualised consideration qualities which played a key role in assisting players such as David Beckham, Roy Keane, Ryan Giggs, Wayne Rooney and Cristiano Ronaldo to attain the highest level of their potential and become highly recognised superstars.

Strengths of the Transformational Leadership Approach

The strengths of the transformational leadership theory are discussed in detail below.

Broadly Researched

In the last 20 years transformational leadership has been the subject of research interests and empirical examinations (Jung, 2001; Lowe and Gardner, 2000; Rafferty and Griffin, 2004; Navickaite and Janiunaite, 2012; Anderson and Sun, 2015; Qu et al, 2015; Deinert et al, 2015; Bush, 2017; Kilinc et al, 2020). Lowe and Gardner (2000) points that over 34% of the articles

published in leadership quarterly from 1990 to 2000 were about transformational or charismatic leadership. From 1999 most of these studies focused on linking transformational leadership to numerous organisational factors such as organisational commitment (Alghusin and Ajlouni, 2020), organisational innovation (Qu et al, 2015; Garcia-morales et al, 2012; Jung et al, 2008) customer satisfaction (Weller et al, 2019), job satisfaction (Griffith, 2004; Leithwood and Jantzi 2008; Walumbwa et al, 2005; Braun et al, 2013), staff retention (Green et al, 2011), professional growth (Krujer et al, 2007), organisational health (Leithwood and Jantzi, 2000) and service quality (Jabnoun and Juma, 2005; Lee et al, 2011).

Intuitive Appeal

Another strength of transformational leadership is that it has intuitive appeal. People gets attracted to this kind of leadership because they found it reasonable. People find it appealing that a leader will put forward a vision for the future. Its visionary and creativity factors coupled with its relevance for change for people made it well accepted by people (Northouse, 2016).

Process focused

Leadership under the transformational theory is treated as process occurring between leaders and followers. Because this process takes into account the needs of both the followers and the leaders, the leader doesn't take the sole responsibility of the leadership but rather the leadership evolves as a result of the reciprocity between the followers and the leader. The benefit is that followers become prominent in the decision-making process because of the key role they play in the gradual progress of the transformational process (Bryman, 1992).

Expansive Leadership view

The transformational leadership theory provides a comprehensive view of leadership that expands other leadership models (Li and Shi, 2008). The primary focus of many leadership models has been on how leaders exchange rewards for performance. The transformational

leadership provides an extensive view of leadership that incorporates both the exchange of rewards and also leaders' attention to the followers needs and growth (Avolio, 1999)

Emphasizes followers

Transformational leadership instils a sense of purpose into followers (Conger and Hunt, 1999). This theory suggests that leadership has a moral facet hence it places strong emphasis on the needs, values and morals of followers. This sets it apart from all other leadership approaches. Transformational leadership seeks to encourage followers to be morally responsible to the highest standards (Northouse,2016). Hence, it includes motivating subordinates to go beyond their personal interests to achieve the shared vision or interests of the team or organisation (Howell and Avolio, 1993).

Effectiveness

The effectiveness of transformational leadership in a range of settings and contexts has widely been supported in a variety of empirical studies (Yukl, 1999; Shamir et al, 1993). However, despite these numerous findings exalting its effectiveness in most fields, questions are still raised about whether it is the most effective leadership style in all contexts (Northouse, 2016).

Criticisms of the Transformational Leadership Theory

Despite the wide application of transformational leadership theory and the huge pile of empirical research findings supporting it as an effective type of leadership in organisations, there remains a lot of shortcomings with transformational leadership.

Conceptual clarity

One major concern raised by the critics is the high correlation that exist among the four dimensions of transformational leadership (Suresh and Rajini, 2013). Yukl (1999) points out that the dimensions have diverse contents that is not clearly differentiated from each other and

a considerable overlapping exists among them. Due to the high correlation existing among the dimensions, Bycio et al (1995) points out that Bass model lacks discriminate validity and suggested the trimming down of the four dimensions into one single dimension. Tepper and Percy (1994) also found out a non-evidence of discriminate validity between idealised influence and inspirational motivation. While, Li and Shi (2008) suggested that the four dimensions should be replaced by charisma and vision, which have become the most dominant factors in “new leadership” research (Khatri, 2005). Also, the boundaries are not well defined and determined as it overlaps with other theoretical concepts such as empowering and charismatic leadership which have been taken to be synonymous with transformational leadership (Bryman, 1992; Khaki, 2005) even though in Bass (1985) model, charisma is considered a dimension of the transformational leadership theory. Also, few transformational facets correlate with those of laissez faire and transactional leadership. Tejada et al (2001) argues that the presence of entrusting in laissez faire, management by exception and intellectual stimulation indicates the non-distinctive aspect of such dimensions to transformational leadership. However, this criticism has been countered by Antonakis et al, (2003) who argues that the factor structure of the bass model may vary across different settings and leaders may operationalise or enact their behaviours differently depending on context. Hence implying that the inter factor structure is variant in different contexts.

Traits Oriented

Some researchers have criticised the transformational leadership approach arguing that the approach is oriented towards the trait paradigm instead of the behavioural paradigm as claimed by Bass (1985) and House (1972). These researchers argue that a transformational leader is an individual with exceptional capabilities that can be able to transform followers to the level need to achieve a shared vision (Yukl, 1999; Li and Shi, 2008). Others argues that since the leader provides the vision, he alone takes the role of leading (Leithwood and Jantzi, 2005; Mitchel et

al, 2010). Thus, generating the perception that such leader performs alone without engaging subordinates hence, portraying elitism and anti-democratism (Northouse, 2016).

Suitability of the Leader's Vision

As this leadership theory focuses on the provision of a new vision to the subordinates and changing their morals and ethics, questions have been raised about who makes that decision that the proposed vision and values are better than the old or present (Khatri, 2005; Avolio et al, 1999). In a situation whereby, the changed values appear to be less an improvement or redeeming than the old, the possibility of the leadership being challenged arises (Yukl, 1999). Though these critics failed to expatiate more about how followers could question the leader's vision and challenge the leader. This is more difficult in collective societies like china or Pakistan. Challenging the leaders and questioning their vision in collective societies is considered to be against sobriety. Such societies discourage debate and discussion (Shah, 2009) and considers participative leaders who engages colleagues in decision making processes and implementation as being less effective than self-centred autocratic leaders.

Dark side of Charisma

The charismatic facet of this leadership approach has been used for negative purposes. Hence researchers view it as a huge peril to institutions (Burns, 2005). Charismatic leaders such as Hitler, Osama bin Laden and Sadam Hussein have negatively misused their charismatic factor to influence their followers towards immoral directions. Due to the admiration and respect followers have for such leaders, they are willing to even put their lives in the line in order to actualize the cruel vision put forward by their leaders. The charisma aspect presents the potential for an abuse of power and influence (Conger and Kanungo, 1987). It poses risks for organisations because of its potential to be abused and utilised for destructive purposes (Conger and Hunt, 1999). Such leaders are manipulative, exploitative, deceptive, narcissistic, and are

attributed with Machiavellianism and flawed vision (Northouse, 2016; Bass and Riggio, 2006). Because of these characteristics they are seen more as pseudo-transformational than transformational leaders (Bass and Steidlmeier, 1999). Pseudo-transformational leaders are transformational leaders that tend to make short term gains that ultimately result in long term costs (Bass, 2008).

Heroic Leadership Bias

Yukl (1999) argues that transformational leadership suffers from heroic leadership bias whereby the leader takes all the glory for a successful transformation. He stressed that by focusing on the leaders influence on the followers to do extraordinary things, the researchers ignored the significance of shared leadership or reciprocal influence (Yukl, 1999). Not only leaders that influence followers, followers also influence leaders in one way or the other. Researchers should focus their attention towards how leaders can inspire their followers in challenging the leader's decisions and scrutinising his/her vision. Doing such encourages the subordinates to be part of the leadership process. Instead of being glory hounds, transformational leaders need to applaud those in the trenches for helping to achieve the vision. When followers don't feel appreciated for what they do, it will seriously impact morale.

Transactional leadership

Transactional leadership is where a leader encourages subordinates to achieve goals by offering rewards and /or sometimes punishments in exchange for performance (Bass, 1998). The transaction usually involves the leader paying team members in return for their effort and compliance. The leader has a right to punish team members if their work doesn't meet an appropriate standard (Bass, 2008). Bass (1985) identified two dimensions of the transactional leadership style, contingency rewards and Management by exception (passive and active). Contingency rewards relate to contract exchange of rewards for effort, rewarding subordinates

for performing well and recognition of accomplishments. Management by exception (active) relates to the leader watching and searching for any possible deviations from the rules and standards and taking of corrective actions while management by exception (passive) is when the leader intervenes if standards are not met. The success of transactional style of leadership in organisations has been hugely documented. However, some critics point out that the relationship that exists between leaders and followers tend toward shallow, temporary exchanges of gratification and often amount to resentments (Adanri and Thakkar, 2016). Other critics point out that rewards motivate only for a short term and poorer results are produced where there is need for higher level thinking (Bass, 2008). Northouse (2016) argues that it disregards situational and contextual factors related to organisational challenges.

Criticisms of transactional leadership

Universality and adaptability

A good amount of leadership scholars has criticised transactional leadership because of its one-size fits all universal approach to leadership that disregards situational and contextual factors related to organisational challenges (Yukl and Mahsud, 2010; Yukl, 2013). Transactional leadership has an over-reliance on a single approach, and unwillingness to discuss or even consider the ideas of others, which limits a leader's creativity and his/her ability to adjust if things go wrong (Benjamin, 2016). Without adaptability, transactional leadership is not very effective in handling complex organisational situations. Leaders need to be adaptable to tackle different organisational challenges. Transactional leaders need to adjust their style to meet the ever-changing employee or organisational needs.

Clarity

Scholars have also emphasized the need for clarity in transactional leadership style (Whittington et al, 2009). Transactional style is based on an exchange process of rewards for job done. Such exchange process requires clarification in explanations, directions and specifications, getting subordinates in discussions to avoid confusions and role ambiguities (Van Vart, 2013). Leaders and their subordinates should be clear about their responsibilities and expectations as this is needed to imitate and implement an exchange.

Short-term goals

Transactional leadership is ideal for short term goals that produce quick results (Nahavandi, 2015). It is not vital in helping employees achieve sustained performance (Nahavandi, 2015). It lacks any real inspirational power that drives intrinsic motivation and therefore not effective in helping subordinate achieve a long-sustained performance.

Laissez faire leadership

Laissez faire leadership is a type of leadership where a leader is hands off and give employees the freedom to make independent decision (Northouse, 2016). Laissez faire leaders engages more in paperwork than influencing subordinate and often avoids situations that precludes any possibility of confrontation (Bolden et al, 2009). Robbins (2007, p.475) and Luthans (2002) defined laissez faire style as “abdicates responsibilities and avoids making decisions”. There is lack of involvement from the laissez faire leader in the work of the unit. Laissez faire leaders gives complete freedom to subordinates, provide necessary materials to support them and avoids giving feedback. Such leaders don’t normally want to interfere in decision making process. They give subordinates all the freedom they need in making the necessary decisions. Their major aim is to be in good terms with everybody. However, this backfires most of the times. Though Laissez faire comes with many advantages such as freedom and independency

of subordinates which has been argued by some to lead to creativity, it has quite a lot of limitations.

Criticisms of Laissez faire leadership

Laissez faire leadership is described as the absence of leadership, the avoidance of intervention, or both (Bass and Avolio, 1990). There is generally lack of transactions or agreements with subordinates under a laissez faire leadership likewise involvement, feedback and rewards. There is failure to motivate subordinates and recognition and satisfaction of their needs are rarely considered. Critics have argued that laissez faire leadership is negatively related to productivity (Skogstad et al, 2007). Groups becomes unproductive when supervisors relinquish their leadership role to the group members. Teams led by uninvolved leaders are less productive in the quality and quantity of the problems they solve and tend to have low satisfaction compared to team led by involved leaders (Buch et al, 2014).

It has also been found to be a major contributing factor to low cohesion among group (Bergen and Bressler, 2014) and to the stimulus that causes stress in the workplace such as role ambiguity, role conflict, and the perception of mediocre interpersonal treatment by the leader (Skogstad et al, 2007). Laissez faire style of leadership which is seen as a lack of adequate leadership may create stress among teams with subsequent consequences in interpersonal tensions. There might be an escalated level of interpersonal conflicts among co-workers in the absence of a leader to manage these interpersonal tensions.

Servant Leadership

Adding the element of social responsibility to transformational style of leadership, servant leadership is viewed to be particularly relevant in today's era as (Graham, 1991). Coined by Robert Greenleaf in 1970, servant leadership clearly emphasizes the need of followers more

than any other leadership styles (Parolini et al, 2009). This style of leadership emphasizes the ideal of service in the leader-follower relationship (Philips, 2010). Thus, moving away from the focus on influence which generally is considered as the key element of leadership. Since it was coined in 1970, there is still no consensus about a definition and theoretical framework of servant leadership. However, inspired by the work of Greenleaf, so many writers and researchers have come up with their own definitions and models. Hence resulting in many interpretations of servant leadership (Philips, 2010; Russell and Stone, 2002; Spears, 1996). Greenleaf (1977) himself defines servant leaders as “leaders who place the needs of their subordinates before their own needs and centre their efforts on helping subordinates grow to reach their maximum potential and achieve optimal organisational and career success” (p.2). This type of leaders seeks the development of their followers purely for the good of the followers and not merely a means to reach the leader’s or organisational goals (Ehrhart, 2004). Servant leadership goes beyond the enrichment of self-ego/self-interests and builds a working atmosphere that generates feelings of empowerment among employees. This encourages and motivates employees to be productive. Servant leadership plants within followers a spirit of servanthood and also creating value for the community at large.

A servant leader is genuinely concerned with serving followers in order to help them grow. It is different from other leadership styles where the ultimate goal is the well-being of the organisation. This kind of leadership style creates an atmosphere that encourages followers to attain their fullest potential. According to Greenleaf, servant leaders doesn’t exercise their powers to coerce followers into getting things done but to persuade, encourage and convince followers. Compared to other kind of leadership styles where leaders are usually driven by the need for power, servant leaders are driven by the ultimate need to serve (Sun, 2013). This ultimate need to serve leads to a responsibility to the growth of the followers, the organisation and the community at large (Chen et al, 2015).

Just like other leadership styles, Liden et al (2008) developed a set of dimensions that defines the servant leadership style. Nine dimensions were identified by these researchers after a review of servant leadership literature offering inconsistent set of dimensions. These nine dimensions include:

- (a) Emotional Healing: expressing sensitivity to the personal concern of others
- (b) Value creation for the Community: being aware of the community needs and showing genuine and honest concern for helping.
- (c) Conceptual Skills: being very knowledgeable of the establishment and job roles in order to be in a higher position to effectively provide support and assistance to others, most especially immediate subordinates.
- (d) Empowering: inspiring and motivating subordinates in problems identification and solving and also deciding on when tasks should be completed and how to complete them.
- (e) Helping the growth and success of subordinates: expressing genuine and honest concern for subordinate's career growth and development through the provision of support and mentoring.
- (f) Putting Subordinates First: demonstrating to subordinates in words and actions that satisfying their work needs is a priority through assisting them with problems they are facing with their assigned duties.
- (g) Behaving Ethically: engaging in an open, fair and honest interactions with others
- (h) Relationship: building long term relationship with immediate followers
- (i) Servanthood: the desire to be characterised by others as someone who serves others first.

In creating an efficient yet reliable scale for use in future servant leadership research, Liden et al (2008) classified two of the nine dimensions (Relationship and servanthood) as problematic

and non-interpretable. Servanthood was deemed as non-interpretable because no single grouping of items representing the factor/dimension emerged as the dominant source for it (Liden et al, 2008). Relationship was deemed non-interpretable because the items loaded on the factor/dimension are less than 4. According to the researchers each factor with a loading of less than 4 items should be deemed non-interpretable because of the anticipated intercorrelation among the factors. After an examination of all the factors, the researchers narrowed the factors to 7 factors and a total of 54 items: behaving ethically (11), emotional healing (9), conceptual skills (9), helping the growth and success of subordinates (8), creating value for the community (7), empowering (6), and putting subordinates first (4). However, to create a more efficient and reliable scale for use in future research, the researchers chose the four highest loading items on each factor. Thereby creating an amended, 28 item scale of servant leadership.

Criticisms of servant leadership

Just like other leadership styles, servant leadership style has its limitations. Crippen (2004) argues that the idea of leading and serving at the same time seems to undermine the primacy of leadership upon which all other managerial task in a firm depends entirely on. Having to balance leading and serving makes servant leadership an arguably challenging task (Ford and Harding, 2015). Pannaccio et al (2014) also suggested that focusing constantly on the needs and preferences of others to include both followers, shareholders or even the servant leader's family creates workplace stressors such as role ambiguity, role conflict, and overload for the leader himself/herself.

Furthermore, a clearer identification of these needs is required when attending to the needs of others. So many factors such as miscommunication or lacking awareness of the stakeholders themselves might obscure the clarity of these needs to a servant leader (Pannaccio et al, 2014).

These leaders face the risk of role overload when their resources are insufficient enough to meet all the role demands associated with various work tasks (Panaccio et al, 2014). Consequentially, it is more likely for servant leaders to engage in emotional labour to manage their emotions in the course of attending to the needs of others (Liden et al, 2014).

2.3.2 Leadership in Africa

It is very much unrealistic to suppose that much of what can be said about leadership will apply equally across all nations (Blunt and Jones, 1997). Nigerian society lean towards egalitarianism within age group but lean towards gerontocracy or hierarchisation between age groups. Hence, leaders often behave, and are anticipated to lead their followers in a paternalistic manner. Consensus is highly valued in such societies hence decision making within hierarchies often takes eternity to materialise. This is also common in most other West African countries such as Ghana, Cameroon, Togo and so much more. Leaders in West Africa are known for possessing genuine authority but are expected by their followers to exercise that authority in a restricted or infrequent manner and in a humane and considerate way. Hence, they prefer paternalistic rather than authoritarian leadership. The western theories of leadership have not really benefited these West African societies. Hence some researchers are increasingly calling for an indigenised model built on principles, beliefs and values that guide the societal cultures. (Evans, 2018; Iwowo, 2015; Thiemann et al 2006). Jackson (2016) and Kuada (2010) also argues that the concept of leadership in African institutions have to be clearly associated with the norms and values of African cultures. Hence, producing effective leadership across the continent requires Africans turning to their principles and values.

Built on the concept of Ubuntu, these leadership values signify, “I am who am I through others”. The Ubuntu concept hinge on collective responsibility, togetherness, brotherhood and empathy. West Africa for example is characterised by harmonious teamwork, humanistic

values, relationship building and mutual respect for all (Jackson, 2016). Leadership behaviour in Africa is enshrined in the way of relationship building between the leader and the subordinates (Ewans, 2018). In another perspective, Kuada (2010) argues that the relationship techniques applied by African leaders are aimed at patronising the subordinates instead of inspiring them to commit to organisational goals. Which is a form of autocratic -benevolent relationship. Position, authority and seniority drive leadership in Africa and in other countries with high power distance. Thus, Galperin and Alamuri (2017) asserts that leadership styles in these societies tend to be hierarchical and with a central decision-making policy. In these cultures, the personal relationships between employees with the leader could lead to commitment to common goals and other organisational outcomes like performance, job satisfaction and retention (Mustafa and Lines, 2014; Zhong et al, 2016). Such paternalistic approach enhances employees job satisfaction.

Paternalistic Leadership

Paternalistic leadership is the prevalent leadership style in Nigerian business organisations and in the majority world (Jackson, 2015). Aycan (2006) argues that paternalistic dimensions are commonly found in cultures identified as collectivist, hierarchical and high-power distance, and throughout the culture paternalism is promoted as appropriate and acceptable style. Although paternalistic leadership style is very common in Nigeria business organisations, very limited studies exist on this leadership style and its effects on businesses in this part of the world. Silin (1976) on studying leadership concepts and behavioural styles of business owners/managers in Taiwan found that the leadership styles in Taiwan were greatly different from the leadership styles associated with western businesses. He concluded that a kind of leadership style, paternalistic leadership very widespread in Taiwanese businesses is very much different from the popular western leadership styles such as transformational and servant leadership styles. The differences observed include didactic leadership, moral leadership,

centralised authority, maintaining social distance with subordinates, keeping intentions ill-defined and implementing control tactics (Silin, 1976).

Farh and Cheng (2000) defined paternalistic leadership as a style of leadership that combines strong discipline and authority with fatherly benevolence and moral integrity couched in a personalistic atmosphere. This definition demonstrates that paternalistic leadership consists of three crucial elements: Authoritarianism, Benevolence, and Moral leadership. Based on this definition, Cheng et al (2004) developed a survey scale that measures the constructs of paternalistic leadership. A three-dimensional paternalistic scale was established. This scale identified Benevolent paternalism, Moral paternalism and Authoritarian paternalism as the three dimensions of paternalistic leadership.

Authoritarian Paternalism

Authoritarian leadership refers to a leader's behaviour of asserting strong authority and control over subordinates and demanding undisputed obedience from them (Wang & Guan, 2018). Authoritarian leaders demand best performance from their subordinates, and they are completely responsible for making all decisions (Wang et al, 2013). This leadership style is predominant in African, Asian, middle east and Latin American institutions (Pellegrini and Scandura, 2008). In a traditional African family, absolute authority and power is exercised by a father over his family. This value is often implemented by leaders in African organisations through the establishment of a centralised hierarchy and by assuming a father like role with an authoritarian leadership style. These leaders assert power and authority over their followers to bring about followers' acquiescence and submission. Employees are expected to adhere to high standards and punished for performing poorly (Wang et al, 2013)

Authoritarian leadership has been depicted as destructive leadership in some research which affirms its damaging impact on employee outcomes, such as Job performance (Chan et al, 2012), employee voice behaviour (Li and Sun, 2015), and team identification (Cheng and Wang, 2014). Thus, there is a consensus among some leadership scholars on the undesirability and ineffectiveness of authoritarian leadership in organisational management. However, some leadership scholars fail to agree that authoritarian style of leadership is homogeneously unfavourable for both employees and organisations. An empirical study conducted in Taiwan by Cheng et al (2004) found authoritarian leadership style to be conducive to employee responses. Tian and Sanchez (2007) affirm that there was a positive correlation between authoritarian leadership and affective trust in an empirical study conducted in Chinese organisations. Cheng et al' (2003) findings also asserts that authoritarian leadership is positively related with employee performance. The conflicting feelings in regard to the relationship between authoritarian leadership and employee outcomes have encouraged calls for more studies on the psychological mechanism fundamental to the effect of authoritarian leadership on employee performance (Chen et al, 2011). Though a majority of studies have suggested the negative impact of authoritarian leadership on employee behaviours especially in the west, it is highly possible that under certain conditions, authoritarian leadership would have a positive effect on employee or subordinate's performance.

Benevolent Paternalism

Farh and Cheng (2000) concluded that benevolent leadership originates in Confucianism which demonstrates mutuality in social relations. In Confucianism, a leader should be benevolent to his followers and in turn, the followers should be loyal to the leader (Lin et al, 2018). Similarly, to these Confucian principles, under benevolent leadership in work domains, mutual obligations on the basis of duty fulfilment emerge. Benevolent leadership can be referred to as a form of individualised care within an organisation whereby the leader provides coaching and

mentoring, strive to solve subordinates work problems and shows concern for subordinate's career development (Erkutlu & Chafra, 2016). Such leaders also treat subordinates as family members, helping them during their personal emergencies and expressing concern beyond work relationships (Wang and Cheng, 2009). In traditional Nigerian societies, leaders enact a paternalistic role with fatherly benevolence. Benevolent leadership style embodies a responsibility and encouraging action to one's followers in the organisation that inspires them to respond in kind and obey the requests of the leader (Chan et al, 2012). Hence, the benevolence aspect of paternalism is expected to ward off any act of defiance caused by the authoritarianism aspect.

Benevolent paternalism is similar to the individualised consideration aspect of transformational leadership, in the sense that benevolence offers individualised care and encouragement to employees in the workplace (Cheng et al, 2013; Farh et al, 2008). When benevolent leaders show concern for subordinates' feelings and needs, provide positive feedback and help them develop necessary skills, the subordinates respond by showing respect and loyalty to their benevolent leader in completion of their role obligations (Wang and Cheng, 2009). A paternalistic leader expects a return of performance effort from subordinates when expressing benevolence (Uhl-Bien & Maslyn, 2005).

Generally, it has been supported to positively influence subordinates' attitude and behaviour such as encouraging improved performance (Chan and Mak, 2011), trust (Wasti et al, 2011), loyalty and hard work (Shin et al, 2012) and innovative behaviour (Gumusluoglu et al, 2017). Though Li et al (2018) found negative effects of benevolent leadership on team performance.

Moral Paternalism

Actions by leaders serve to emphasize behaviours that are acceptable and appropriate within the organisation. Leaders' conduct is visible to employees and reinforces their reputation and

support of ethical values (Aycan, 2000). Moral leaders emphasize the importance of ethical behaviour. Through consistent talk moral leaders signal that morality, ethics and values are vital to both the leader and the organisation. The influence of moral leaders on their subordinates could be more understood through the concept of social learning which maintains that people can learn both through direct experience and observation (Aycan, 2008). According to theory of social learning, influence is achieved through two aspects: attractive role modelling and positive reinforcement of behaviour (Pellegrini and Scandura, 2008). Moral leaders are attractive to their subordinates because of their integrity and altruistic motivation. Reinforcement of behaviour can be achieved when subordinates watch what leaders pay attention to and measure (Schein, 2009). Utilising transformational leadership skills, that is, making use of reward systems are one way of reinforcing behaviour among subordinates.

Some researchers have disapproved paternalism as it can turn into biasness where only loyal group of followers have access to the resources (Kabasakal and Bodur, 2003). While others disapprove it based on ideological and rational ground. Padavic and Ernest (1994) argued that public are increasingly becoming aware of the different ways of democratic relativity through the help of media educational and political organisations in addition to market determinism press for huge layoffs, unionisation and general wellbeing policies resulting to the failure of paternalism.

2.4 National Culture

In order to understand how indigenised leadership practices and behaviour affects employee's outcome it would be important to understand the impact of culture on leadership behaviour. This section proceeds to a discussion on Nigerian culture to further strengthen the justification of the paternalistic leadership style appropriateness to Nigeria. Aycan (2008) affirms that leadership in general and paternalistic leadership in particular cannot be studied without

bearing in mind its cultural context. A good understanding of national culture will help describe how culture influences leadership styles in different countries (Browaeys and Price, 2011). Gert Hofstede surveyed 116000 IBM employees in fifty countries between 1967-1973 in an attempt at identifying ways in which culture varies from country to country worldwide (Hofstede, 1980). Hofstede cultural dimension is a guiding framework for countless studies in business and management research. In his research, Hofstede identified six cultural dimensions known as power distance, indulgence/restraint, long/short-term orientation, uncertainty avoidance, individualism/collectivism and masculinity/femininity.

Individualism versus collectivism: individualism considers the importance of an individual as opposed to a group in a given culture while collectivism considers the importance of a group as opposed to an individual in a given culture. Under individualist culture, more importance is assigned to personal interests than the interests of a group. Individualists focus more on establishing their individuality and see themselves as more differentiated and separate from their peers. Therefore, people within an individualist society tend to look after themselves more as individuals rather than groups than those from collectivist society. In collectivist societies, interests of the group are highly prioritised over personal interests (Wagner, 1995). People within collective cultures perceive that their attitudes and behaviours are strongly influenced by the feelings, thoughts and behaviours of others (Magnini et al, 2013).

Power distance: this dimension represents the degree to which less powerful members in various institutions accept and expect power to be unequally distributed. In cultures with high power distance, followers and leaders appear to support the unequal distribution of power. In contrast, followers tend to disapprove this unequal distribution of power in cultures with low power distance. Therefore, employees in cultures with high power distance are more willing to expect and accept his/her demands from their leaders with the belief that doing so will potentially strengthen their relationships with their leaders (Pellegrini and Scandura, 2008).

Several researchers on Nigeria work culture indicates that high power distance is a major cultural value of Nigerian employees (Hofstede, 2010; Okolo and Iguisi, 2011; Iguisi, 2012; Dikko, 2017). Over several decades, strong evidence has been established that Nigeria ranks high in power distance (Hofstede, 2010).

Uncertainty avoidance: this dimension represents the extent at which members of a given culture are comfortable in unknown or unstructured situations and the degree at which a society attempts to have uncontrollable situations under control (Hofstede, 2010). Cultures with high uncertainty avoidance tend to be uncomfortable with unstructured structures. They tend to be threatened by the unknown and the ambiguity. In contrast, cultures that are low on uncertainty avoidance willingly accept risk and open to uncertainties. Due to its relationship to risk, disparities in uncertainty avoidance are possibly the most substantial cultural dimension in international settings due to its relationship to risk (Demmler et al, 2018).

Masculinity versus femininity: it has been a general misconception that men are basically superior to women. Nevertheless, egalitarianism is being practiced by some cultures that emphasizes the equality of genders. Attitudes toward appropriate roles for women, their relative power in institutions and general treatment may differ across cultures. Thus, masculinity in the Hofstede's cultural dimensions refers to the societal norms exerting influence on the societal roles attached to men and women. In societies that are high on masculinity, women are supposed to be more tender, modest, and concerned with the quality of life while men are supposed to be tough, assertive and interested in material success. In contrast, femininity refers to a culture where there is overlap of social gender roles, both women and men are expected to be tender, humble, and concerned with the general wellbeing of individuals and societies. Therefore, there is not much disparity in gender roles between men and women in feminine cultures in contrast to masculine cultures (An and Kim, 2007).

Long-term orientation versus short-term orientation: According to Hofstede (2001, p. 359) “long-term orientation stands for fostering of virtues oriented towards future rewards, in particular, perseverance and thrift. While short term orientation stands for the fostering of virtues related to the past and present, in particular, respect for tradition, preservation of “face” and fulfilling obligations”. Cultures that tend to be more future-oriented, embracing delayed gratification of material and social needs score high on long-term orientation whereas cultures that value respect for traditions and social obligation and care more about immediate gratification score low on long-term orientation (Hofstede, 2010).

Indulgence versus Restraint: “Indulgence stands for a society that allows relatively free gratification of basic natural human desires related to enjoying life and having fun while restraint stands for a society that suppresses gratification of needs and regulates it by means of strict social norms” (Minkov and Hofstede, 2010). Individuals of indulgence-oriented cultures are mostly characterised as fun oriented, whereas individuals in restraint-oriented cultures are generally not interested in entertainment, fun and leisure of any sort (Hofstede et al, 2010). Individuals in restraint-oriented cultures seem to be make modest decisions, have limited wants and desires, and generally expresses lack of interests in the opposite (Bathae, 2011). These people attach less importance to fun and leisure unlike those in indulgence-oriented culture, resulting in limited hedonic behaviours.

Criticisms of Hofstede’s Model

Hofstede’s model on national culture provides scholars and practitioners with a highly valuable insight into the dynamics of cross-cultural relationships. However, despite the broad acceptance of this model, it still has its limitations and thus does not escape criticisms. There are critical reasons to argue that Hofstede model is outdated, archaic and may not be appropriate for application in today’s contemporary business environment. First, globalisation has

broadened geographical inter-linkages of products, markets, firms and production factors, with a huge proportion of each derived, created or available in more countries and regions (Bond, 2002; Burnett and Huisman, 2009; Chandrawati, 2011). Businesses are increasingly investing overseas and multinational companies expanding their operations worldwide which may reflect in high number of expatriates workers and immigrants. Also, these businesses promote its own culture wherever they operate and inevitably workers are expected to adapt themselves to organisational culture. The organisational culture of these MNC is consequently about the same regardless of their global location.

Secondly, advanced internet technology that enables the widespread use of social media has enhanced the globalisation effect on national cultures (Kaul, 2011; Kaul, 2014; Wang, 2015). The easy accessibility of the internet and the readily availability of online contents such as fashion, movies and music has skyrocketed cultural exchange and the adoption of practices and ideas, particularly western cultures (Kaul, 2011). For example, independent and individualistic images of American or British people are positively spread on the internet and these may be appreciated by young Nigerians, motivating them to be individualist who prefer freedom lifestyle and aim for self-accomplishment.

Thirdly, Hofstede assumes that domestic population is a homogenous whole (Bond, 2002; Courtright et al, 2010; Katija, 2017). However, most nations are groups of ethnic units (Redpath, 1997). For instance, it is impossible to believe that there is one culture in Nigeria, because they are all Nigerians. Generalizing the culture of a wide range of country is inappropriate. Nigeria is a very ethnically diverse country with over 300 ethnic groups and diverse cultural background. The culture of the Igbo people in south eastern Nigeria was patterned along gerontocracy and decentralisation arrangements while that of the Hausa people in northern Nigeria was patterned on monarchical, emirate system where power and authority flow from the top (from the emir) and followers were expected to follow. In addition, the Hausa

people places a high premium deference to authority, loyalty, obedience and sensitivity to the interests, opinions, views and demands of one's superiors. Their culture frown at the self-assertiveness of the worker as individual initiatives not sanctioned by ones' superior were negatively evaluated (Aluko, 2003). The Igbo culture on the other hand idealises egalitarianism, individualism and anarchic pursuits. There is fierce individualistic struggles and ruthless determination to succeed. The Igbo people look down on individuals who depend on superiors or rely on them for their progress. Unquestioning obedience and subservience signify weakness (Aluko, 2000)

Thus, attempting to generalise Nigerian culture is extremely complex due to the numerous ethnic groups. Two or more ethnic groups would share two similarities but so many disparities. Hofstede analysis is therefore constrained by ignoring the diversity of cultures among a nation's ethnic groups.

2.4.1 The Nigerian Culture

the culture of Nigeria is shaped by Nigeria's multiple ethnic groups. The country has over 300 ethnic groups with over 521 languages (Nwosu, 2016). The four largest ethnic groups being Hausa & Fulani in the north, Yoruba in the southwest and Igbo in the southeast. The rest of Nigeria's ethnic groups are spread all over the country but majority of them can be found in the middle belt and the north. The Fulani ethnic group are spread all over west and central Africa. The Igbos and most of the minority ethnic groups such as Efik, Ibibio, Annang. Ijaw people are predominantly Christian while the Hausa and Fulani people are predominantly Muslims. The Yoruba people have a balance of members that are adherent to both Islam and Christianity. It is evident that globalisation has brough massive threat on some aspects of Nigerian culture. For instance, religion. Christianity and Islam have almost completely replaced the practice of indigenou religious beliefs. It is undeniable that globalisation is having

a profound effect on Nigeria and its cultures. Globalisation is driven with utmost specificities by mass media (Kaul, 2011; Kaul, 2014; Ajekwe, 2017). The unmitigated exposure to foreign cultural ideas and values alien to Nigerian societies is a serious danger to dominant cultures (Odinye and Odinye, 2012; Ajekwe, 2017). Almost every Nigerian home or workplace has satellite technologies that provide daily access to international TV stations such as CNN, MTV Base, Hollywood and Sky news with profound homogenising and cosmopolitanism impacts on cultures.

Cultures in Nigeria encourage communalism or collectivism and discourages individual autonomy (Okolo and Iguisi, 2011; Iguisi, 2012; Dikko, 2017). Activities such as tilling the land; building living quarters and food security are approached collectively. This practice of communalism has been around from time immemorial and continues even today by several ethnic groups. Nigerians respect seniority. Seniority can emerge from age (gerontocracy) or education (professionally), or hierarchy in community (Dikko, 2017; Vincent and Iguisi, 2018). Right from young, Nigerians are taught how to obey and respect senior people both at home and in schools (Folarin, 2013). At work, colleagues in senior positions expects to be respected such that their decisions are not questioned. This type of obedience and respect for seniority and authority lead to both power distance and risk avoidance (Dikko, 2017; Vincent and Iguisi, 2018). Feeling less powerful in relation to others leads to dependency syndrome, self-confidence and decision-making ability (Ajekwe, 2017).

2.5 National culture and Leadership

Researchers in leadership and management studies have argued that cognitive systems and behavioural repertoires established in certain cultures can influence leadership in a variety of ways (House, 2014; Smith et al, 2002; Leung and Bond, 2004). These studies have documented their understanding of the impact of cultural factors on perception and practice of leadership

(Mittal and Elias, 2016). They theorised that, cultural differences enable the development and sustainment of leadership behaviours in different cultures (House et al, 2004; Smith et al, 2002; Leung and Bond, 2004). There is growing need for leaders operating in different cultural environments to learn new behaviour and skills due to the cultural biasness of leadership behaviour

Apart being recognised as a leadership style, paternalism is also a cultural trait. Hence, it's imperative to define the structural and cultural determinant of paternalism. Paternalism is a predominant cultural trait of traditional African societies such as Nigeria. Several countries have seen the significant influence culture has on leadership style and behaviour in their societies (Browaeyns and Price, 2015). According to GLOBE (global leadership and organisational behaviour effectiveness) effective culture can be strongly linked to the beliefs, norms and values of the individuals being led in a society or in an organisation (House et al, 2004). Hofstede et al (2010) argued that it's impossible to separate leadership from the other elements of society, thus both followers and their leaders are all component parts of a society. A good understanding of the behaviours of leaders relies on understanding the societal cultures which includes the historical events experienced by the country's generation, family orientation and function and personality types (Demmler et al, 2018). Social exchange theory also explains the need to align leadership and national culture. This theory states that a person feels morally obligated to pay back any benefits that he or she is provided by another (Blau, 1964). In affirmation, Deluga (1994) and Howell & Hall-merenda (1999) asserts that this sense of obligation is present across cultures. Social exchange theory will further be discussed in more details under the conceptual framework.

Researchers on leadership and culture have argued that leadership styles and behaviours are connected to societal cultures across the globe (Ashraf et al, 2014; Fairhust and Connaughton, 2014). Thus, some societies may endorse democratic leadership behaviours while authoritarian

leadership behaviour may be endorsed in others. According to Hofstede et al (2010) there is prevalence of democratic leadership behaviour in cultures with low power distance, femininity, low uncertainty avoidance, individualism, high indulgence and marked with the strong belief that being successful at work is an outcome of one's effort ability while authoritarian leadership is predominant in cultures with high power distance, masculinity, high uncertainty avoidance, collectivism, high restraint and characterised with the belief that the luck and fate of individual efforts at work are influenced by environmental factors (external environmental orientation).

In contrast to authoritarian leadership, democratic leadership may be unsuitable for cultures who respects the formal chain of command and whose members are hesitant to bypass this hierarchical order. Therefore, traits of authoritarian leadership can easily be found in less developed nations where followers depend mostly on the leaders in making vital decisions whereas traits of democratic leadership are very common in advanced nations where subordinates are empowered and encouraged to get involved in making crucial decisions. It is worthy to note that leaders within cultures traced to authoritarian leadership environment displays paternalistic characteristic. This is because the followers expect leaders to utilise their authority moderately and in a benevolent and considerate way in such environment (Muczyk and Holt, 2008).

Paternalistic leadership has been considered to be very much accepted in conventional, hierarchical, high power distance and collectivists societal cultures such as Africa, middle east, Latin America and Asia. However, it has been disapproved in equalitarian, industrialised and individualistic western cultures, where paternalism has been referred to as "benevolent dictatorship" (Pellegrini and Scandura, 2008). In high power distance cultures, Subordinates endorse and do not have hard feelings about paternalistic leaders' superiority whereas in low power distance subordinates resent authority, they question the lack of equality and differences in power immanent of paternalism (Dikko, 2017). Paternalistic leadership is viewed positively

in collectivistic societies because members of such societies highly value responsibility for others, conformity and interdependence whereas it's viewed negatively in individualistic cultures because they value self-determination, self-reliance and autonomy. People in this individualistic culture will perceive leaders' deep involvement with followers as violation or invasion of privacy (Mansur et al, 2017).

2.5.1 The Nigerian Culture and Paternalistic Leadership

In Nigeria, the concept of leadership is greatly a function of the traditions and cultural values of the people (Hassan and Lituchy, 2017). The cultural setting in which individuals find themselves influence their perception and understanding of leadership (Ali, 2012; Adewale, 2020). The process of socialisation has a huge impact on the perceptions of leadership in Nigeria. For example, people that grew up in a typical traditional environment are socialised from their young age to show respect and obedience to elderly people and community leaders. Even when an elderly person is wrong, a child is not expected to correct him/her. Hence the social arrangement promotes the infallibility and sacrosanctity of the elderly who are seen as the community leaders. Thus, Fashoyin (1992) posits that paternalism must be seen as an inevitable aspect of social relationship in Nigerian societies. This is in line with the traditional chieftaincy system in Nigeria where traditional leaders in some parts of the country are accorded reverence because they are seen as fathers and custodians of the communities they rule. Thus, there is widespread belief that the paternalistic and non-egalitarian nature of traditional rule is expressed in the leadership behaviour of managers in Nigerian organisations which is however generally seen as effective by subordinates (Fashoyin, 1992; Folarin, 2013; Dikko, 2017; Rasaq, Osei-Bonsu and Bulley, 2017).

Fashoyin (1992) contends that the Nigerian system of social relations is strongly rooted in paternalism and this has found expression in the workplace. In the workplace, individuals

display collectivism and high-power distance in their work culture. As previously explained using the Hofstede national culture dimensions, unequal power distribution in such societies is generally expected and accepted by both leaders and followers. Employees or subordinates generally display willingness to accept orders from their leaders and expresses low desire for empowerment (Kuada, 2010; Bulley et al, 2017; Evans, 2018). Employees in such societies believe a strong bond with their leaders may be developed when they accept demands and obey orders from their leaders (Dikko, 2017; Magnini et al, 2013). In contrast, employees in societies with a low power distribution or low power distance expects to be consulted by their leaders and have the freedom to express their opinions (Wanasika et al, 2011; Gill et al, 2010; Yan and Hunt, 2005).

Also in regards to the patriarchal nature of Nigerian societies which are characterised by male control and authority in all spheres of life. Men are looked upon as the head of the family and the presence of only a few women in high-ranking positions in organisations demonstrates patriarchy (Olojede, 2004; Suleiman, 2010). Olojede (2004) posits that the lack of more women in leadership positions is constrained by gender roles. Therefore, creating the perception of the masculine characteristics consistent with the concept of leadership in Nigeria (Hofstede, 2010). Leaders are thus, regarded as a superior father who makes all the decisions.

Nigerians have a high regard for moral behaviour, spirituality and the importance of religion. leaders are expected to have integrity and show considerable amount of concern for the needs and well-being of the followers during difficult times. Hence, these leaders adopt the moral, benevolence and authoritarian dimensions of paternalism; however, the authoritarian is predominant (Suleiman, 2010; Ogbeidi, 2012; Chukwu and Ebuka, 2013) and often power driven based on status with limited regard for merit and skills (Bulley et al, 2017). Given the literature review on culture and leadership in Nigeria, there is therefore a strong tendency to

believe that paternalism is deep rooted in Nigeria due to the social relationship in Nigerian societies.

2.6 Leadership and Customer Perceived Service Quality

The role of service management staff in enhancing the performance of customer contact employee has been duly documented in service management literature (Zeithaml and Bitner, 1996; Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Jabnoun and Rasassi, 2005; Farrell, 2008, Clark et al, 2009; Ismail et al, 2009; Farrell et al, 2009; Dolatabadi and Safa, 2011; Yee et al, 2011; Lee et al, 2011; Pahi and Hamid, 2015; Sweta et al, 2017). Zeithaml and Bitner (1996) posits that the effectiveness of the service delivery process that results in excellent service quality is influenced by the leadership style adopted by service firm managers. Managers must adopt leadership style that ensures employees attitudes and behaviours are conducive to the delivery of quality service (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Farrell, et al, 2009; Sweta, et al, 2017). Contrary to this widely supported view, some scholars have suggested otherwise. Pantovakis and Patsioras (2016) confirms the presence of a weak correlation between leadership style and service quality in an empirical study exploring the influence of leadership on the service quality – customer satisfaction relationship in The B2B environment. This is contrary to popular opinion however it could be argued that this study focused on B2B which typifies the uniqueness of the study.

Leadership styles have received great attention in sales management (Bass, 1997; Kirby et al, 2013; Brown, 2014; Mulki et al, 2014; Schwepker and Schultz, 2014), and organisational psychology (Yammario et al, 1994; Bernhard and O’Driscoll, 2011; Monga et al, 2012; Hamdi and Rajablu, 2012). However, there is still much work needed in relation to enhancement of service quality in organisations despite the fact that the major cause of service deficiency in organisations is a lack of effective service leadership (Stutts, 1999; Pahi and Hamid, 2006).

The performance of customer contact employees especially in high contact industries is dependent upon a number of employee work factors such as role stress, job satisfaction, organisational commitment, adaptability (Singh, 1998; Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Clark et al, 2009; Cho et al, 2013; Olugbade and Karatepe, 2018; DeTienne et al, 2012; Suan and Nasurdin, 2013, Schwepker and Dimitriou, 2021). Thus, the service managers have a dual role of optimising employee work perceptions such as job satisfaction and fostering service-oriented efforts on the part of service employees. Managers are expected to exhibit service-oriented behaviours conducive for enhancing service employees' performance (Schwepker and Dimitriou, 2021; Olugbade and Karatepe, 2018; Gill et al, 2010; Bowen and Lawler, 1992). Such service-oriented behaviours include empowering customer contact employees (Bowen and Lawler, 1992; Clark et al, 2009; Dust et al, 2013; Saleem et al, 2019), providing organisational support systems (Diehart et al, 1993; Ahmed and Muchiri, 2014; Thao and Kang, 2018; Addo and Dartey-Baah, 2019), internal marketing efforts (Varey, 1995; Razgah et al, 2018; Akbari et al, 2018), careful selection and training of contact employees (Lashley, 1998; Testa and Sipe, 2012; Nerdinger and Pundt, 2018), providing performance feedback to employees and recognition for performance (Schneider, 1994) and motivating contact employees (Lewis and Gabtelsen, 1998; Ahmad et al, 2014; Naile and Selesho, 2014; Anderson et al, 2016). Therefore, leaders are expected to have both direct and indirect effects on the quality of the service provision.

Schmitt et al (2016) have shown that leaders play an important role in encouraging employees to inspire new ideas or to improve work procedures for the better of the organisation. In other words, leaders can enhance service quality of organisations. A lot of recent studies have proved that both transformational and transactional leadership style are positively related to service quality (Schaubroeck et al, 2016; Schmitt et al, 2016; Ali et al, 2015). Employees with transformational leaders are empowered and inspired to be innovative during customer

interactions in order to better satisfy the customers (Schmitt et al, 2016). The higher the number of effective new ideas proposed, the more customised services can be offered, leading to enhanced service quality. While employees working with transactional leaders are rewarded on the basis of customer orientation, friendliness, the ability to solve customer problems and other behaviours that are directed towards improved service quality (Ali et al, 2015). This kind of reward system for performance gives the employees the incentive to engage in behaviours that are conducive to improved service quality.

While investigating transformational leadership, team performance and service quality. Lee et al (2011) argued that intellectual stimulation is the only transformational leadership dimension that has a positive relationship with service quality. In contrast, Jabnoun and Rasassi (2005) affirms the existence of a positive relationship between service quality and all the dimensions of transformational leadership style - charisma, inspiration, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration while active exception and passive avoidant dimensions of transactional leadership showed a negative relationship with service quality in the health sector. Schaubroeck et al (2016) likewise contend that all the dimensions of transformational leadership style positively influence peers' service quality adherence and service performance in an empirical study examining how leadership styles of individuals designated by management to serve as service quality leaders among their peers were related to changes in peers' beliefs and service behaviour.

Though Jabnoun and Rasassi (2005) conclusions on transactional leadership style is in contrast with the results of Pahi and Hamid (2015) which argue that both transformational and transactional leadership styles positively affect service quality. Contrary to the above affirmations on the positive influence of transformational leadership style on service quality, Yee et al (2011) suggest that transformational leadership cannot directly influence service quality unless mediated by learning goal orientation. This suggestion is reaffirmed by Ismail et

al (2009) confirming that two transformational leadership characteristics namely individualised consideration and intellectual stimulation can only influence service quality in the presence of empowerment. Hence, empowerment is deemed a vital factor in influencing service employees. This is also supported in the empirical study of Clark et al (2009) who observed that leaders following an empowering leadership style are capable of influencing customer contact employees to commit to the organisation's goal of delivering high quality service to hotel customers.

Most of these scholars clearly supports the need for a mediator to fully influence service quality. Namasiuayam et al (2014) argues that a mediator such as employee satisfaction is needed to influence service quality delivery of employees. Such mediating factors are positively affected by an effective leadership style and then subsequently influences service quality delivery. For instance, in Malaysian universities, Jamaludin et al, (2015) found that job satisfaction mediates the positive influence of transactional leadership on academic staff commitment to service. Similarly, Liao and Chuang, (2007) suggests that self-efficacy mediates the influences of transformational leadership on service performance. This aligns with the model of service employee management developed by Hartline and Ferrell (1996) which shows that to increase customer perception of a service, self-efficacy and job satisfaction of employees must be increased while role ambiguity and conflict must be reduced to the minimum possible by the managers.

One common thing that these studies share is that none observed a positive relationship between laissez faire leadership style and service quality delivery. Although some researchers found laissez faire to possess a positive influence over many organisational and independent variables such as innovation and employee commitment (Ali and Ibrahim, 2014; Sorensen, 2000). However, these findings have been disputed by Dunn et al (2012) and, Judge and Piccolo (2004) who concluded that Laissez faire may negatively relate to employees'

commitment to organisational goals, which high service quality is part of. Unlike transformational leadership whose behaviours such as encouraging higher level of aspirations, caring about subordinates and encouraging subordinates' personal development have a positive effect on employee attitude and motivate employees to actively offer service to help colleagues to achieve organisational goals (Patiar and Mia, 2009). Hence, laissez faire is regarded as a less efficient style because of its passive nature (Antonakis et al, 2003). Madlock (2008) found that laissez faire leadership results in low employee satisfaction. This will negatively affect the final outcome to the customers. Hence, its effectiveness in influencing frontline employees towards high service quality delivery is highly disputed.

Popli and Rizui (2017) explained how employee engagement and perceived leadership style influences service orientation (measured in terms of behaviour towards internal and external customers and consumers) in various service sectors including telecommunication, banking, tourism and insurance. They suggested that a significant and moderate correlation exists between service orientation and transformational leadership, and between transformational leadership and employee engagement, while a negative correlation exists between service orientation and laissez faire leadership and between laissez faire and employee engagement. This indicates that a leader that scorers high in transformational leadership would positively impact employee engagement in an organisation, and the greater the employee engagement, the greater the employees service orientation. In the health sector, Bahadori et al (2016) investigated the correlation between patient satisfaction of nursing care and ward level leadership in teaching hospitals of Iran university of medical sciences. The study involved the selection of thirty-four head nurses based on census sampling, one hundred and two nursing staff and one hundred and seventy patients selected by random sampling. The researchers posit the inexistence of a significant relationship between the full range leadership styles (transactional, transformational and laissez faire) and patient satisfaction. This is surprising as

the results of previous studies have shown significant associations between leadership and increased patient satisfaction.

Similarly, to transactional and transformational leadership that have been proven to influence service quality in organisations, servant leadership have its fair share of support in influencing service quality in business organisations, most especially in the hotel sector. Investigating the relationship between service employees' perceptions of service quality provided to hotel guests and their perception of service leadership provided by their managers, Koyuncu et al, 2014) suggested there was a significant and positive correlation between each dimension of servant leadership with each dimension of SERVQUAL. Thus, supervisors act as role models to employees, supporting them emotionally to succeed while employees respond by providing customers with excellent service.

The influence of servant leadership on the service performance of frontline employees is noticeably strong that even top-level leaders' servant leadership in a highly bureaucratic organisations can cascade via the hierarchy to trigger a positive attitude in the frontline employees during service encounters. Ling et al (2016) have proven this to be true in an empirical study testing a trickledown effect regarding how servant leadership flows from top to middle level leaders, resulting in frontline employees service oriented behaviours and service quality in hotels which revealed that both top and middle level servant leadership cascade down to positively correlate with employees service oriented behaviours which then mediates the influence of supervisor level servant leadership on frontline employees service quality delivery. Likewise, in the banking sector, Wang et al (2007) demonstrated that servant leadership could cascade down through organisational hierarchy to influence frontline employees service performance. However, contrary to the findings of these scholars, Linuesa-Langreo et al, (2017) suggested that no direct relationship exists between servant leadership and customer service performance. However, these authors argued that this relationship can be mediated

through enhancing service climate as servant leadership can only positively influence the service climate in hotels.

There is very limited or no study on the relationship between paternalistic leadership and service quality. Though it has been duly elaborated in the literature that in order to increase customer perception of service quality managers must adopt leadership style that ensures employees attitudes and behaviours are conducive to the delivery of quality service (Clark et al, 2009; Hartline and Ferrell, 1996). Paternalistic leaders' benevolent treatment has been well demonstrated to influence employees' attitudes and behaviours that are deemed conducive to the delivery of quality service (Unler and Kilic, 2019; Song, 2016; Pellegrini et al, 2010; Chen and Kao, 2009; Erben and Guneser, 2007; Farh et al, 2008; Aycan, 2006; Lok and Crawford, 2004; Cheng et al, 2002). Paternalistic leaders who care for and support their subordinates creates the feeling of reciprocity in subordinates' minds which fosters both their commitment to organisational goals and their job satisfaction levels. The significance of the feeling of reciprocity has been illustrated by the social exchange theory in the next section.

Employees feel emotionally attached to an organisation when they perceive their organisation as a family rather than a company based on the benevolent treatment of care and support, they receive from their paternalistic leaders (Unler and Kilic, 2019). Hence, if paternalistic leadership has been demonstrated to influence employees' satisfaction and commitment to organisational goals, then it's rational to expect that such leadership can promote employees' service quality. Though it's been equally demonstrated that paternalistic leaders' authoritarian behaviour induces violent and negative emotional reaction in subordinates, in such that a negative emotional reaction might be regarded to affect subordinates' work attitudes. This can easily affect service quality and job performance as a result of a negative work environment climate (Hui et al, 2007; Ling et al, 2016). In high contact service industries, employees showing a happy mood and enjoying their job increases their willingness to show a positive

attitude and behaviour in service encounter to provide better service quality to customers. Employees working with a paternalistic leader exhibiting more of authoritarianism, constantly worry about being blamed for making mistakes or failing to meet expected goals of their job roles, thus developing evasive ideas (Cheng et al, 2006; Ching et al, 2019). Evasive ideas stimulate the development of negative emotions that could negatively affect employees' behaviours in service encounters.

The authoritarian aspect of paternalism is also found to affect employees' commitment to organisation goals due to the leaders' strict control and authority (Cheng et al, 2002; Afsar et al, 2014). While being more benevolent and displaying moral responsibility that creates an ethical climate in the organisation enhances commitment to organisational goals (Afsar et al, 2014) which service quality is a major part of, especially in the hospitality sector. Despite the negative linkage of the authoritarian aspect of paternalism to employees' attitudes and behaviours, Yuzbasioglu (2018) posits that authoritarian leadership positively affects employees' outcomes such as commitment and satisfaction providing that it's used more sparingly than benevolence and moral leadership. Likewise, Chen (2013) contends that degree of internal service quality for employees will be higher with a manager that is predominantly authoritarian if the employees perceive that the manager provide a clear vision and mission, utilise their influences to provide support, fairness, encouragement, openness and harmony.

Benevolent leaders can induce followers' performance especially through the inducement of positive emotions (Luthan and Youssef-Morgan, 2017). Such leaders' expression of care and nurturing behaviours are likely to induce positive feelings among their followers who experience high levels of comfort, warm feelings, trust and identification with the leader to continue the positive cycle (Wasti et al, 2010). Such positive cycle translates into performance on their job roles as it creates a positive service climate for service performance to flourish. On the other hand, it has been documented that, authoritarian leaders are likely to trigger negative

emotions among their followers such as distrust, fear, anger, anxiety and uncertainty (Guoa et al, 2013). Such leaders fail to manage their emotions hence are likely display abusive behaviours in the workplace (Erturelen et al, 2013). These negative behaviours provoke destructive psychological processes among substitutes resulting to negative affective states that hinder their performance in the workplace (Luthans and Youssef-Morgan, 2017). Subordinates experiencing negative affectivity due to a leader's authoritarian behaviour questions their self-competence (self-efficacy) and lack flexibility and innovativeness.

Zhang et al (2014) contends that authoritarian aspects of paternalism impede innovativeness in employees through its negative influences on the psychological resources of the subordinates that is destructive to the motivational and emotional forces of confidence, self-worth, optimism and hope. Authoritarianism encourages a state of lack of self-determination or autonomy which hinders an employee's sense of self competence that negatively affect empowerment. However, the benevolence and moral aspects of paternalism are being promoted as the ideal leadership to stimulate innovativeness. Rego et al (2012) contends that the positive emotions and perceived support created by benevolent leaders stimulates the will to sustain will power, achieve performance in their roles, consider different perspectives in their approach to problems and contributes to the success of their organisation by displaying an excellent level of innovativeness and tasks performance, while moral leadership is associated with employees attitudes and behaviours as they respect their employees and provide them autonomy for carrying out their tasks, which in turn contributes to a sense of self determination (Farh et al, 2006) that is likely to enhance their capability to perform well in their roles.

Paternalistic leaders' enactment of benevolent and moral leadership foster trust between the leader and the subordinate's relationship, turning it into a social exchange in nature (Cheng et al, 2011). Desired behaviours are exhibited by subordinates when there is strong perception of caring and considerate deeds from the leader. Such employees go beyond their job descriptions

to benefit the shared goals of the organisation (Cheng et al, 2013). Unlike under transactional leadership, the authors further stressed that subordinates perform extra role activities not just because they are only motivated to do so but because of lack of reproof when things go wrong. Thus, Cheng et al (2013) concludes that benevolent and moral leadership positively influence subordinates' attitudes and behaviours. These attitudes and behaviours are expected to be valuable during service encounters for the provision of excellent service quality and ultimately ensure customer satisfaction and loyalty. Authoritarian dimension is not capable of influencing these subordinates' attitudes and behaviours (Afsar, 2014 and Cheng et al, 2013). Notwithstanding, the benevolent and moral aspect of paternalism are expected to nullify the negative impact of authoritarian dimension. As a result of this review, it is expected that subordinates will perceive the support they get from their benevolent and moral leaders as a motivation to increase their job performance during service encounters.

2.7 The Conceptualisation

In order to delineate how leadership influence employees' attitudes and behaviours towards delivering excellent quality services, two prominent theories will be discussed prior to developing the relationships. These are the theories of social exchange and reasoned action.

Theory of Social exchange

The theory of social exchange focuses upon the concept of exchange relationships based on personal and social interactions (Bettencourt et al, 2001). Hence it constitutes a vital paradigm for understanding employees service behaviours (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005). However, it has been rarely applied in business and management (Nielsen, 2005). Primarily the theory of social exchange is based upon the concept of **reciprocity**. Essentially a receiver of a service is expected to express his/her gratitude by returning a service at the expected time or occasion (Farrell, 2008). Apart from services, exchanges could be in the form of love, status,

information, money and goods (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005). Due to the research context, the focus lies in the exchange of information and services.

Figure 0.5: Types of exchange. (Farrell, 2008)

Mutual and univocal reciprocity are two types of reciprocity (Befu, 1977). Mutual reciprocity states that one's giving is to be returned by the recipient only (Befu, 1977). Hence it refers to dyadic social exchanges which basically is an exchange between two parties as shown in the above table. On the other hand, univocal reciprocity involves multiple exchanges among three or more individuals, also referred to as generalised exchange (Takahashi, 2000). While mutual reciprocity is seen as individualistic social exchange, univocal reciprocity is seen as collectivist

social exchange (Cole et al, 2002). In group generalised exchange, individuals take turns to give to a group while in individual generalised exchange individuals bring their resources together for the benefit of one member at a time.

Due to the cyclical nature of chain generalised exchange, there is no room for freeloading behaviour (taking advantage of other generosity without giving anything in return). This is a common limitation with individual generalised exchange. Therefore, with regards to the context of this study which focuses on the process of service delivery, it appears that chain generalised social exchange is present, taking the form of the model (A->B->C->A) where A represents the organisation, B represents customer contact employees and C represents customers. In line with the purpose of this study, the managers of the hotels (A) provide leadership to customer contact employees (B) who in turn engage in a range of customer-oriented behaviours to satisfy customers (C) and the customers reciprocates by paying for the hotels' services. Therefore, given the objective of trying to assess the role of paternalistic leadership style on service delivery, this study is adopting chain generalised social exchange.

Figure 0.6: Flow of resources. (Farrell, 2008)

A major objective for all service managers should be to encourage customer contact employees to reciprocate following provision of resources. Customer contact employees are basically expected to perform customer-oriented boundary spanning behaviours COBSBs to deliver high quality service and satisfy customers (Bettencourt et al, 2001). For COBSBs to be performed by customer contact employees they need to have obligation to reciprocate (Bettencourt et al, 2005). Thus, service managers need to provide their employees with something of value such

as managers displaying appropriate leadership. Hence in the context of this study, leadership style of the hotel managers represents this value.

The Theory of Reasoned Action

The theory of reasoned action suggests that employees' behaviours must be driven by their work attitudes, beliefs and/or their intentions (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). This theory argued that leadership do not directly influence the behaviours of employees rather it has an indirect impact on employee behaviours via mediating attitudes, beliefs and/or intention variables. This theory has been suggested in studies linking leadership, negatively to role stress such as role conflict and role ambiguity (Rizzo et al, 1970), positively to job satisfaction (Netemeyer et al, 1997), positively to self-efficacy and adaptability (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Clark et al, 2009).

Role conflict and role ambiguity are classed as negative attitudes due to their negative intentions on employee behaviours (Singh, 1998). Job satisfaction, self-efficacy and adaptability are classed as positive attitudes due to their positive influence upon work outcomes (Bettencourt and Brown, 2003; Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Clark et al, 2008). These constructs have been the focus of recent research in the service marketing literature (Brown et al, 2002; Clark et al, 2009; Farrell, 2008).

The Conceptual Framework and Hypotheses Development

Based upon the literature review and the discussion on the theories of social exchange and reasoned action, the following conceptual framework will direct the study. The framework proposes that the responsiveness, reliability, empathy and assurance of employees influence the customer's perception of the service quality delivered, and that the leadership style adopted by the managers affects these behaviours through mediating employees' attitudes such as role clarity, job satisfaction, self-efficacy and adaptability. The conceptual framework is based on

the theories of social exchange, and reasoned action, models of service employee management (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996), SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al, 1988), and Cheng et al (2000) paternalistic leadership scale. The independent variables are the leadership styles while the dimensions of service quality are the dependent variables. Role clarity, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, adaptability mediates this relationship.

Figure 0.7: The conceptual model. (Created by the researcher)

Keywords

H1A-	Authoritarian leadership and role clarity
H1B+	Benevolence leadership and role clarity
H1C+	Moral leadership and role clarity
H2A-	Authoritarian leadership and Job satisfaction
H2B+	Benevolence leadership and Job satisfaction
H2C+	Moral leadership and Job satisfaction
H3A+	Role clarity and job satisfaction
H3B+	Role clarity and adaptability
H3C+	Role clarity and self-efficacy
H4A+	Self-efficacy and job satisfaction
H4B+	Self-efficacy and adaptability
H5+	Adaptability and customer perceived service quality
H6+	Self-efficacy and customer perceived service quality
H7+	Job satisfaction and customer perceived service quality

Table 0.2: Keywords to the codes in the conceptual model. (Created by the researcher). (Note: Negative sign – represents a negative relationship. Positive sign + represents a positive relationship).

Leadership styles and Role clarity

Job specifications formally describe work tasks, but role expectations are shaped by structured organizational policies and procedures, human histories and experiences, and treatment by co-workers and superiors (Peterson et al, 1995). Managers create the roles and assign the tasks. They are mainly responsible for shaping subordinate's role perceptions. When evaluating work progress and performance, they have the legitimate power to redefine jobs, revise job specifications and adjust job characteristics. According to role theory, employees perceive their job roles to be vague, contradictory or overwhelming when expectations are unclear, conflicted or overwhelming. The negative perceptions then influence their attitudes and behaviors at work, such as job satisfaction, self-efficacy, adaptability, and commitment to service quality.

Role ambiguity (antonym: role clarity) denotes uncertainty about the expectations, behaviours and consequences associated with a particular role (Rizzo et al, 1970). A lack of clarity of information associated with one's role was defined by Roy et al (1965) as role ambiguity. Role ambiguity was defined by Beehr and Glazer (2003) as the lack of clarification about the roles, goals and responsibilities involved in fulfilling one's role in the organization. Role clarity, on the other hand, is characterized as the extent to which people feel that they have clear instructions on the expected roles and behaviors associated with their work (Kahn et al, 1965). It means that within the organization and team, the follower is conscious of his or her duty, position and tasks (Rizzo et al, 1970) and that the follower knows what the leader needs of him or her (Kalshoven et al, 2011). The behavior of leaders therefore forms a key driver for the clarification of an experienced role. Role clarity helps to lessen stress on the team, exhaustion or burnout on the employees, while in contrast role ambiguity leads to stress.

It is possible that if participants encounter role ambiguity, both individual and group functioning would suffer (Carron and Hausenblas, 1996). Francis and Barling (2005) point out that bad leadership is a root cause of essential stressors in the workplace such as role ambiguity. An immediate supervisor's leadership style is closely linked to subordinates enduring stressful

work situations marked by a lack of clarification regarding their roles and responsibilities (Skotsgad et al, 2007).

The experience of role ambiguity would arise from the expectations and subsequent communications emanating from a role sender (Kahn et al, 1964). It has been established that the immediate supervisor is usually the primary source of role-related expectations in a work setting (Beauchamp et al, 2005). Leaders demonstrate a set of clear values that can assist subordinates to understand the ends to which they are working by setting clear and desirable targets and requirements for achieving these (Racga and Walker, 2013). The immediate leaders have a significant impact on subordinates' role expectations by giving clear orders and information and assisting with objectives (Beauchamp et al, 2005). Leaders can also influence the role stressors of followers by ensuring that they have the information necessary to perform work assignments and by providing knowledge and support that allows them to develop the skills needed to perform tasks (Nielsen et al, 2008).

Hence, by ensuring that subordinates have the requisite information to carry out their duties, they contribute to reducing ambiguity about expectations and behaviors and increasing clarification of roles. In order to be effective, leaders have to provide structure for employees, according to the path target theory, by letting them know what they are supposed to do and providing them with what is lacking or needed in the situation (House, 1996). Doing this eliminates role ambiguity among followers. The clarity of requirements in the job roles of subordinates is a key component of leadership (Skotsgad et al, 2007). Therefore, a failure to clearly define or convey role expectations by leaders results in employees having ambiguous expectations and the eventual perception of role ambiguity.

Authoritarian leadership emphasizes absolute power and control over subordinates and requests subordinates' indisputable obedience (Cheng et al, 2004). The hierarchical order that

requires subordinates to be submissive, dependent, and obedient is strictly controlled by these leaders (Pellegrini et al, 2010). Authoritarian leaders make all the main decisions, delegate tasks, issue orders and set high expectations (Wang et al, 2013). Subordinates perceive that the legitimate supremacy inherent in authoritarian leadership must be obeyed, or else they must be punished. Hence, their behaviors are confined to explicit in-role requirements to be good employees but are unmotivated to work beyond their roles (Chen et al, 2014). Authoritarian leaders withhold vital information and resources for control and subordinates believe they are unable to obtain job support. They set high standards at the same time and task subordinates with error-free expectations. Subordinates are unclear about how to meet such high expectations since job support information is withheld from them and the bureaucratic distance prevents them from actively dissenting or daring to seek assistance (Wang et al, 2013). In addition, unquestioned obedience, compliance and dependence are constantly expected from them by these leaders (Chan, 2013). So unclear information must be acknowledged by employees and processed. Therefore, it is hypothesized that;

Hypothesis 1A: an increase in the use of authoritarian leadership is associated with a decrease in employee role clarity.

Benevolent leadership is characterized by an individualized, holistic concern for subordinates' well-being and demonstrates reverence, care, concern and encouragement for members of the group. High levels of trust, mutual support and open channels of contact with followers are expected to be created by a benevolent leadership (Neubauer and Lank, 1998). Therefore, these positive attitudes and behavior of a leader are extremely unlikely to translate into role ambiguity that causes work stress for employees. The care and support given by benevolent leadership may also prevent followers from placing unattainable demands on themselves that surpass their capabilities. Therefore, it is hypothesized that;

Hypothesis1B: an increase in the use of benevolent leadership is associated with an increase in employee role clarity.

Moral leadership represents the expression of ethically appropriate attitudes and provides an example of how moral issues and problems can be solved by the practice of unselfishness and self-discipline (Nielsen, 1989). Staffs would have confidence in their leaders if they perceive that their leaders would never take advantage of them and never engage in reckless actions. Job tension would not be felt by them as a result. However, Kaygisizel and Otken (2015) argue that the emotional and moral interest of moral leaders will blur the boundaries of the work for followers. Followers can become confused about what is expected of them and explanations may be unclear due to this benevolent and moral treatment. It is worth noting, however, that moral leadership's behavior is concerned with transparency and providing clarity about expectations to followers. It's more of leading by example. Such behavior from the manager thus allows the employee to understand what is expected of him or her in regard to performance goals and duties. Moral leadership requires the show of integrity and being considerate and equal in the treatment of staff by leaders. Roles and responsibilities for workers are constantly clarified by moral leaders.

Hypothesis1C: an increase in the use of moral leadership is associated with an increase in employee role clarity.

Leadership Styles and Job Satisfaction

Previous studies have examined the relationship between paternalistic leadership and employee job satisfaction. Afsar (2014) found that moral leadership increases teachers job satisfaction while authoritarian decreases it in his study among Pakistani college instructors.

Their findings showed that employees tend to be satisfied discharging their duties under a leader that leads by example and with kindness. According to Cheng (2004) a leader's morality have a high influence on employees. Similarly, Jheng (2012) reveals that benevolence and moral leadership have remarkable positive effect on employee job satisfaction whereas authoritarian leadership negatively affects job satisfaction. In the same vein, Hafeez and Hayat (2017) also documented that benevolence and moral leadership positively affects employee job satisfaction while authoritarian negative affects it.

These findings show that benevolent behaviour of leaders inspire employees and create an emotional bond between leaders and employees. This emotional connection increases satisfaction in employees as they are motivated, empowered and feel more positive about their job. Leaders are more likely to foster satisfaction among employees when employees are treated with care, fairness and shown considerable support. Subordinates who see in their moral leader a role model are more likely to develop higher levels of job satisfaction due to the trust and respect they have toward the leader. Employees working in an environment characterised by moral and ethical conduct tend to be more satisfied with jobs (Kim and Brymer, 2011). In addition, Nigerians tend to regard morality as the fundamental prerequisite of human beings. Nigerians are more likely to feel satisfied in their work when exposed to leaders' morality. On the other hand, employees that perceive their leaders to be bossy and controlling are likely to be unsatisfied in their roles. Following this review, it is hypothesised that,

Hypothesis2A: an increase in the use of authoritarian leadership is associated with a decrease in employee job satisfaction.

Hypothesis2B: an increase in the use of benevolent leadership is associated with an increase in employee job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 2C: an increase in the use of moral leadership is associated with an increase in employee job satisfaction.

Role clarity, adaptability, self-efficacy and job satisfaction

Employee workplace stressors such as role ambiguity and conflict contribute heavily to the inability of employees to effectively perform in service encounters. Lack of role clarity experienced by employees reduce their job satisfaction and productivity which could negatively affects a customer's perception of service quality in a service encounter (Schneider et al, 1980). Managers must endeavour to increase job satisfaction and decrease employee workplace stressors such as role conflict and ambiguity. Role ambiguity has been linked to low self-efficacy, reduced job satisfaction, and commitment among customer contact employees in hospitality settings (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996).

To increase customers' perceived service quality, Hartline et al (1996) recommends that managers must reduce employee's workplace stressors (role conflict and ambiguity) whilst increasing job satisfaction, self-efficacy and commitment to the shared goal of delivering excellent service quality. Role clarity is a vital antecedent to productivity. The findings of Parasuraman et al (1990) reveals employee responses (self-efficacy, job satisfaction, commitment) mediates the influence of role clarity on customers' perceived service quality. Employees that are confident in carrying out their tasks, satisfied with their jobs and can easily adjust their tasks to meet the needs of customers clearly understands their roles, responsibilities and processes at work and this would ultimately translate in excellent performance in service encounters. Hence, it is anticipated that role clarity which is the opposite of role ambiguity will positively influence employees job satisfaction, adaptability and self-efficacy. Therefore, the following hypothesis are proposed;

Hypothesis 3A: employee role clarity will positively influence employee job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 3B: employee role clarity will positively influence employee adaptability.

Hypothesis 3C: employee role clarity will positively influence employee self-efficacy.

Self-efficacy, Job satisfaction and adaptability.

Past research finds evidence that self-efficacy positively influences job satisfaction and adaptability (Hartline et al, 1996; McDonald and Siegall, 1992). McDonald and Siegall (1992) affirms that employee job satisfaction elevates the feeling of confidence and competence that accompanies self-efficacy making the performance of tasks and roles more fun and gratifying. Likewise, the feeling of confidence and competence associated with self-efficacy is expected to influence employees to become more willing and able to adjust their tasks and roles to meet customers' needs, thus, increasing employee adaptability. These factors; increased competence and increased confidence also are expected to increase employee adaptability because employees competent and confidence on their job become more able and willing to adapt to meet customer's needs and requests.

Previous research also finds that self-efficacy is a major determinant of organisational commitment (Meyer et al, 2002; Garcia, 2009; Zeb & Nawaz, 2016). These researchers argue that employees with high self-efficacy carry out their roles and responsibilities in an organisation with high levels of devotion and commitment. Individuals with high levels of self-efficacy are likely to make greater efforts and demonstrate greater commitment while undertaking an organisational task. Self-efficacy affects the level of employee interest. Though the present study is not investigating the impact of self-efficacy on organisational commitment, however showing greater commitment to a firm shared values and goals signifies satisfaction among the employees in carrying out their roles and responsibilities. In line with the findings of the previous research, the following are proposed;

Hypothesis 4: an increase in employee self-efficacy leads to an increase in (a) Job satisfaction, and (b) Adaptability.

Adaptability and service quality

Employee adaptability is defined as the employee ability to adjust their behaviour to the interpersonal demands of the service encounter (Clark et al, 2009). Adaptability is functionally equivalent to innovativeness and functional flexibility because of the presence of common components in their definition: (1) ability to adjust and (2) interpersonal situation. Ashforth and Humphrey (1993) contends that employees who thoughtlessly conforms to a service script are expected to make a mess of their tasks and less efficient in meeting their customers individual needs and requests. Customers tend to be satisfied with a service when employees understand their special needs and can easily adapt to meet them (Bitner, 1990). It is then practical to anticipate that customer contact employee's ability and willingness to adjust in meeting the special needs of customers positively influences the customers perception of the service quality. Hence, the following is proposed;

Hypothesis 5: an increase in employee adaptability leads to an increase in the level of service quality as perceived by customers.

Job satisfaction and service quality

Job satisfaction positively influences employees' behavioural performances (Churchill et al, 1985). During a service encounter, employee behavioural performance is measured by the customer perception of the service (Hartline et al, 1996). Employees satisfied in their job are highly expected to engage in behaviours conducive to the satisfaction of customer needs (Weatherly and Tamsik, 1993). Several researchers suggest that employee job satisfaction influences customer perceived service quality (Gronroos, 1983; Bowen and Schneider, 1985). Hence, the following is proposed;

Hypothesis 6: employee job satisfaction positively influences service quality as perceived by customers.

Self-efficacy and Service quality

Self-efficacy which means an employee's belief in his or her ability to perform job related tasks becomes stronger over time as the employee successfully performs his/her tasks and builds confidence needed to fulfil roles and responsibilities. As an employee grows in his or her self-efficacy, he/she tend to exert more effort and cope well with task related obstacles. Hence, customer contact employees that are very confident in their ability to excellently execute their tasks tend to cope well in challenging situations that emerge during the service encounter which basically involves responding to customer needs, handling special requests and performing under difficult circumstances. The better performance of highly self-efficacious employees in service encounters positively impacts customers' perceived service quality. It is expected that customers receive better service quality when served by contact employees that believe strongly in their own abilities to excellently execute their tasks and roles. Hence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 7: An increase in employee self-efficacy leads to an increase in the level of service quality as perceived by the customers.

2.7 Conclusion

To conclude, in relation to the conceptual framework with respect to the theory of reasoned action, role clarity and job satisfaction represents customer contact employees 'attitudes' about their jobs (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996). These mediators were chosen for their ability to influence the employee behaviours i.e., self-efficacy and adaptability which act as predictors of the outcome variable i.e., customer perceived service quality. The significance of these chosen mediators in managing customer contact employees towards excellent service

performance have been confirmed in related studies (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Clark et al, 2009) and as such constitute a justifiable platform from which to study the antecedent role of paternalistic leadership in service quality delivery.

The key constructs of interest in this study have now been identified, introduced and reviewed. The research gap that this study seeks to address has been clearly identified in this literature review. It has been emphasised that previous researchers have explored the impact of the full range leadership style and servant leadership style on service quality delivery using some of the constituents identified in this chapter as the mediating variables, however, the role of paternalistic leadership as an antecedent to an employee's excellent service performance behaviour is an area of the literature that requires attention. Finally, this chapter formulated a conceptual framework which will be empirically tested. The methodology for the empirical testing of this conceptual framework will now be discussed in the next chapter.

CHAPTER 3: THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology drives the research in the right direction of achieving the research aims and objectives. A detailed discussion on the research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, methods of data collection and analysis to be conducted will be carried out in this chapter of the thesis. A suitable research methodology applied based on the research problems justifies the credibility of the research findings.

3.1 Research Design

Describing the most appropriate design for achieving the research aims is very important before a researcher embarks on data collection (Parahoo, 2014). A good design is needed for data to be collected and analysed in a way that controls the variables. It decreases errors related to measurement and therefore improving the reliability and validity of the entire study (Polit and Breck, 2007). Malhotra and Birks, (2006) grouped research into exploratory or conclusive research. Where exploratory research concerns the generation of insights and ideas and better suited for issues that has not been widely investigated (Deshpande, 1983) or problems that are difficult to be measured quantitatively (Churchill, 1999). Conclusive research can be descriptive or causal research (Hair et al, 2006). Descriptive research investigates the existence of a correlation between two variables in a construct (Saunders et al, 2019) whereas causal research investigates a cause-and-effect relationship (Kumar, 2019). The present study aims to determine whether a relationship exists between a specific style of leadership and service quality. Therefore, this study is a descriptive one. Thus, primary data will be collected to test the relationships presented in the conceptual model.

3.1.1 Cross Sectional versus Longitudinal Design

Descriptive research available to researchers are grouped into (a) cross sectional design and (b) longitudinal design. In cross sectional design, collection of information is from a specific

population sample at once while in longitudinal design collection of information is done repeatedly over a period of time from a fixed sample. Longitudinal design enables more data to be collected and more rigorous analysis to be executed. This gives the design an edge over cross-sectional design. Also, in contrast to longitudinal design, one major limitation of cross-sectional design is that it doesn't afford the researcher the chance to evaluate changes over time unlike longitudinal design hence making it more difficult to infer causal effects.

In longitudinal design it is easier to establish the occurring sequence of an observed phenomenon. This is a necessary condition required prior to inferring causality (Bollen, 2009). Though longitudinal design has been shown to have numerous advantages over cross-sectional design however it has few major drawbacks which are being very costly and entails the research to be carried out over a long term (Saunders et al, 2015). Hence considering both the time and financial constraints, a longitudinal design is less practicable for this research. Therefore, a cross-sectional design was adopted for this research study. Most of the drawbacks expected of the cross-sectional design adopted can actually be mitigated. For example, the occurring sequence of an observed phenomenon can be partly established through literature review and findings from previous studies. Also, through careful questionnaire design, current and past data can be collected by the researcher so that deduction about causality can be made.

Based on the literature, a correlational design was employed to establish the strength and direction of the relationship among the variables (leadership styles, role clarity, job satisfaction, adaptability, self-efficacy and service quality), hence this present descriptive study utilizes a quantitative, cross-sectional and correlational design. Data for the examination of the relationships among the variables was collected using a quantitative data collection technique.

3.2 The Research Philosophy

Philosophers have hotly debated the relationship between data and theory for over three centuries (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). Not thinking through such philosophical issues can adversely impact the quality of one's research. These philosophical issues underpin the design and evaluations of the research. Understanding them helps the researcher to clarify research designs, recognise the research designs that will work, and which won't work and also help the researcher to easily identify and even formulate designs that they have not stumbled upon in their previous experiences.

Research philosophy is generally a comprehensive term representing the school of thought that underpins the development of knowledge and the nature of that knowledge in regard to research (Kumar, 2019). Three major philosophical realms directly involve in business and management research includes ontology, epistemology and axiology (Saunders, 2019). Ontology describes a researcher's view on the nature of reality. Hence it is the study of the nature of reality (Hughes and Sharrock, 2016). Similar to ontology is epistemology that studies the knowledge of reality (i.e., the structure, sources, constituents, and limits of that knowledge) and justified beliefs (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Epistemology explains what amounts to the acceptable knowledge of reality and the relationship of the researcher with the reality. Axiology explains the association between personal values (ethics and aesthetics) with knowledge. Not taking these philosophical views into consideration threatens the quality of a research (Easterby-smith et al, 2011).

Researchers have classified some research paradigms which researchers align with in studying social phenomena under the two major philosophical stances, ontology and epistemology. Saunders et al (2019) classification of these two philosophical stances differs from that of Ritchie and Lewis (2003). Ritchie and Lewis (2003) perspective on ontology entails the combination of realism and relativism. Their epistemological viewpoint consists of positivism

and interpretivism. Whereas realism, positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism are identified by Saunders et al (2019) in both ontological assumptions and epistemological perspectives. However, scholars have failed to come to an agreement on the categorization and classification of these two philosophical views (Easterby-Smith et al, 2011). Proctor (1998) recommends that these research paradigms must be addressed and understood before deciding on the research methodology to adopt.

3.2.1 Positivism

Positivism, also referred to as empiricism, reductionism and hypothetic-deductive, was first coined by Auguste Conte during the age of enlightenment (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Positivism requires the identification of causal explanations and basic rules explaining the regularities of social behavior in humans (Saunders et al, 2019). The main aim of positivists may also be said to be consistent with that of natural scientists. A positivist researcher believes that the external world is ordered and regulated and that there is an objective reality (truth) system with basic patterns that are predictable or explanatory using theories or rules. Knowledge is regarded by positivists as value free that should not be affected. Just as Ghauri and Gronhaug (2010) pointed out, Positivism researchers view the study of a phenomenon as a fully independent and objective that can't be influenced by the researchers' interests, values or beliefs. Positivist researchers' carryout theory-based research which starts with theory identification, through hypothesis formulation and data collection to confirm a pattern with generalisation (deductive reasoning).

According to Delanty (2007), positivism is based on five tenets. Firstly, the unity of scientific method, with natural science as a model for social science (Scientism). Secondly, a unity in the subject matter of science which implies reductionism, atomism, and objectivism (phenomenalism). Thirdly, where experimentation leads from observation to verification

(empiricism). Fourthly, the dichotomy between facts and values (value freedom). Finally, technically useful knowledge (instrumental knowledge) is important. One of the benefits of following the positivist method is that it offers a broad coverage of the spectrum of circumstances to the researcher (Clarke, 2009). Furthermore, as a whole, it is fast and economical. When time and resources are minimal, it is very suitable. In the context of this analysis, for example, the researcher is researching a phenomenon in Nigeria from distant UK, thus the positivist method can mitigate the financial and time constraints of the study in contrast to the interpretative approach (to be addressed later) that requires a physical communication between the researcher and the participants of the study usually taking up a large amount of time, money and other resources.

3.2.2 Interpretivism

Interpretivism was introduced as a response to the limitations of the positivist approach. It provides the means to understand social phenomenon within rather than outside of the social context. Delanty (2000) developed an outline of the key emphasis that underpins the interpretivist approach. Firstly, interpretation of meanings (Hermeneutics). Secondly, separation of natural sciences from social sciences in both subject matter and method (Anti-scientism). Thirdly, tends to be descriptive rather than critical and incline towards an ethical relativism. Fourthly, interpretation is made possible by human nature (Humanism). Fifthly, language defines the world (Linguistic constructionism). Finally, the hermeneutic circle, i.e. the relationship between the researcher and the researched (replacing the subject-object relation in natural science with the subject-subject relation in social science: inter-subjectivity)

The Interpretivist strategy assumes that real life scenarios are subjective and psychologically made up by humans. Proponents of this research philosophy suggests the explicitly promotion of the researcher's participation (Hussey and Hussey, 1997). They further suggest a thorough minimization of the distance between the researcher and that under observation. The observer

and the observed should maintain as much distance as possible. The interpretivist researcher relates with the research participants in an engaging manner and the outcomes of this encounter focuses on the comprehension and interpretation of the phenomenon studied from the perspective of the researcher (Molina-Azorin, 2016). As a result, it focuses on providing meanings to a social phenomenon. Therefore, in contrast to positivism that focuses on the measurement of a social phenomenon.

Phenomena are viewed by interpretivists as a matter of the connotation individuals allot to a certain situation rather than the cause and effect of that situation (Hughes and Sharrock, 2016). Positivism was thus criticized by advocates of interpretivism as an unacceptable way of analyzing a social science phenomenon. In contrast, interpretivism, has been criticized for its failure to provide a decent solution to replace positivism (Hughes and Sharrock, 2016). Incommensurability is often considered by most positivists to be a significant weakness of the interpretivism philosophy (Kumar, 2019). Others argues its highly subject to the bias of the researcher (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

3.2.3 Realism

Emerging out of the positivist/interpretivist paradigm wars, realism has become popular among researchers as a philosophical framework for social scientific research (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Realism functions as a general methodological framework for research but it is not associated with any particular set of method. In realism, ontology (what is real, the nature of reality) is irreducible to epistemology (i.e., or knowledge of reality), hence, deviating from both positivism and interpretivism for endorsing the ‘epistemic fallacy’, that is the complex reduction of reality to human knowledge (ontology to epistemology). Realist critiques positivism for the restriction of reality to what can be experientially known mainly by the

means of scientific experiments and critiques interpretivism for viewing reality as completely interpreted / constructed based on human knowledge (Bhaskar, 1998).

Realism goes beyond positivism, which merely restricts science to the pattern of quantifiable events (actualism) that actually exist, and beyond interpretivism, which reduces the ontology of the universe to our world experiences. Realism presents the existing paradigms of positivism and interpretivism with a radical alternative (McEvoy and Richards, 2003; Houston, 2001). Realism distinguishes between three distinct ontological realms or nodes of reality: the real or deep structures and mechanisms that give rise to a phenomenon, the actual (the features of reality that are in existence but might not really be experienced) and the empirical (the features of reality that can be directly or indirectly experienced). Such causal processes cannot be directly understood since they are unavailable to examination but can be deduced via a mixture of quantifiable examination and theory generation. Instead of the mere identification of generalizable laws (positivism) or the identification of the lived experiences or beliefs of social actors (interpretivism), realism ultimately aims to establish deeper levels of explanation and comprehension of social phenomena.

Realists identified two main patterns in positivism, firstly, positivism focus exclusively on observable events and fail to consider the extent to which these observable events are influenced prior theoretical frameworks, and secondly, that they deal with relationships between the variables in isolation (Olsen, 2007). Relationships are treated as if they are disconnected from external forces in a closed system and the interactions between mechanisms and the contents of their occurrence are not taken account of (Bhasker, 2020). Realists points out that the real world or actuality functions as a multidimensional open system and forces are generated as a result of the interactions between mechanisms, human agency and social structures (Molina-Azorin and Fetters, 2016). Though realists acknowledge the value of

discourse, human perception and motivation inherent in interpretivist methodologies, they nevertheless, criticize interpretivists that couldn't address the fundamental social structures that may allow or control the actions of individuals or the social networks in which social actors are embedded (Mingers, 2004). Realism entails progressing from the level of empirical examinations and lived experiences to hypothesize about the fundamental social structures and mechanisms that provide a satisfactory explanation or reason for the social phenomenon investigated (Williams, 2003) similar to retroduction which is seen by realists as the logic that underpins realism (McEvoy & Richards, 2006). Retroduction is defined as a mode of analysis in which events are studied with respect to what may have, must have, or could have caused them. In a much simpler sentence, it means finding answers to why events have happened in the way they did (Olsen & Morgan, 2005).

Realism adopts the principles of positivism but stresses the need for some form interpretation in viewing and studying the world (Thomas, 2004). The world is not intrinsically meaningful but our interpretation of it adds meaning to it (Thomas, 2004). In contrast to positivism, realism is not so stringent regarding the physical existence of concepts that are evaluated and related. Positivists argue that it is difficult to claim things are real (e.g., leadership) when their existence cannot be demonstrated (Williams and May, 1996). However, realists argue that with their interpretations, the existence of concepts may be physically established.

3.2.4 Pragmatism

The heated debate between the proponents of positivism and interpretivism on the most appropriate philosophical position to align with in the study social science phenomena still hasn't ended in any generally accepted philosophical solution (Saunders et al, 2019). As a result, a pragmatic 'just get on with it' perspective was proposed by Eastman and Bailey (1996). Supporting the 'just get on with it' perspective, Crossan (2003) maintains that the contrasting

philosophical principles don't determine the definite methods of data collection and analysis to be utilized in a research, thus shouldn't hinder the utilization of any approach. Researchers are therefore encouraged to take the best suitable approach to studying a phenomenon rather than allowing their beliefs or concerns regarding ontology or epistemology to dictate and guide the study.

Nonetheless, with dual approaches, there could be a greater possibility that a research phenomenon will be well studied. The combination of methods will increase the trust of the researcher in the suitability of the methodology put into operation to study the research phenomenon. This will ultimately increase the confidence of the researcher in the findings of the research. Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2007) contend that internal cross-checking, a multi-method approach contributes to the convergent confirmation of study findings. Such multi-method strategy minimizes

3.2.5 Research Paradigm to be adopted (Positivism)

The combination of two or more paradigms will help the researcher to answer complex questions through the utilisation of all the tools and methods at the researcher's disposal (Creswell, 2003; Gorad & Taylor, 2011). However, this has been disputed by Sale et al (2002) who argued that the paradigms are incompatible and can't be combined in one research (Sale et al, 2002). Creswell (2003) recommends six factors that normally influence the selection of research paradigms. These include: (1) the researcher's own belief about the best way to study human behaviour, (2) the research questions (3) the rigour of the research, to include both the universality and verifiability of results (4) the degree of understanding of the problem provided by the method (5) the extent to which the results will generalise to other settings or persons and (6) the usefulness of the findings.

The researcher's own belief: to understand the correlation between variables in the conceptual framework, the researcher strongly believes that positivism is the appropriate research paradigm for this study. The findings derived from positivism solely depend on measured quantities (Kumar, 2019). In addition, previous studies on leadership and employee behaviour have followed the positivism philosophy (Pahi and Hamid, 2015; Dolatabadi and Safa, 2011; Clark et al, 2009; Hartline and Ferrell, 1996). Therefore, the researcher aims to align this study with previous studies by adopting positivism.

Research questions: the research questions require quantifiable answers. Hence to provide answers to all the research questions, quantitative data has to be collected. Due to the nature of the research questions, the positivism stance will be taken in this research whereby data will be collected via surveys as it has been suggested by Saunders et al (2019) that adopting a philosophical position boils down to the research questions. The researcher will adopt positivism in getting evidence in the form of data as it's best suited to achieve the research aim since it intends to measure the relationships between various variables quantitatively leading to statistical analyses.

The universality and verifiability of results: two most important criteria for research are credibility and reliability of the collected data. Some researchers have suggested that data collection need to be done in a way that limits the involvement of the researcher preparing the ground for hypothesis testing without manipulating the data (Yee and Khin, 2010; Aliyu et al, 2014; Kumar, 2019). Also, the predictive nature of positivism enables the establishment of verifiable truths. The structure of the research instrument used in a positivist research such as a questionnaire ensures the high reliability of the collected data in that it provides participants to be less subjective when responding to the questions.

The extent of the researcher’s understanding of the limitations of the research method:

the researcher should understand that each research method has its own limitations (Oakshott, 2012; Swift and Sally, 2014). While quantitative method forces responses in order to produce results that can be linked to larger situations, qualitative method is unable to link results to larger situations and puts so much focus on individual results (O’Gorman and MacIntosh, 2015). Rather than discarding each method due to their weaknesses, researchers should incorporate both methods in order to ensure the accuracy of their studies (Hair et al, 2019). Thus, both can be concurrently used in a research study. However, the ultimate choice to implement a quantitative research method arose from the adoption of positivism, the nature of the study and the phenomena to be examined. As this study aims to study the causal relationships between leadership styles and service quality, qualitative approach would have been best suited for the study as it would provide a detailed description of the phenomena examined, however, it can’t be adopted in this context as it is less feasible for generalizing and hard to test. Hence quantitative approach is more suited in this context as it is more reliable for testing hypothesis and generalizations.

The usefulness and generalization of the findings: as the study aims to investigate the relationship between leadership styles and customer perceived service quality, the researcher’s involvement with the respondents at the stage of data collection have to be at a tiniest degree, maintaining objectivity to avoid influencing the objects under investigation or be influenced by these objects in order to obtain high quality data for hypothesis testing. Generalization of findings from hypothesis testing is vital to a good research (Blumberg et al, 2014; Bell et al, 2018). In positivist research, a truth that can be determined in one situation can be easily generalized to other situations as positivism is aimed at creating general laws that can be applied across different situations (Sekaran and Bougie, 2019; Ghauri et al, 2020).

Following the establishment of a literature based conceptual model of leadership influence on the behaviour of customer contact employees in service encounters, this research seeks to test this conceptual model by adopting positivist epistemologies. An understanding of the research philosophy then leads to the next stage of the research which is research approach and data collection methods

3.3 Research Approach

The relevance of hypothesis to the research marks the boundary between inductive and deductive approach. The deductive approach tests the validity of hypothesis whereas inductive approach brings about new theories' development and generalizations (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). The relevance of hypothesis to the research marks the distinctive point between deductive and inductive approach Hypothesis validity tested is using the deductive method, while the inductive method leads to new theories development and generalizations (Saunders et al, 2019). The researcher adopts a deductive method if during the research process, several hypotheses that need to be supported or dismissed are formulated. On the other hand, the inductive method does not require formulating hypotheses (Saunders et al, 2019). Typically, the research process begins with the aim or major objective of the researcher and then followed by the research questions and objectives. Inductivism or inductive approach coincides with the interpretivist philosophy approach in which, with the use of observation, the researcher can create an image of the social phenomenon investigated.

3.3.1 Deductive Approach

The deductive approach method applies to the testing of hypotheses. Testing is concerned with supporting the current hypothesis or dismissing it. The researcher begins with an abstract, conceptual link between ideas and moves forward to strong empirical evidence (Neuman, 2003). As a result, current and existing theoretical evidence plays a significant role as it

contributes to hypothesis development, the choice of variables, and the subsequent models and measures, researchers expect to employ. Hypotheses are accepted or rejected by comparing results from observed reality (collected data) with the predicted result.

It is said that the deductive approach is compatible with the quantitative data collection and analysis methods (Haruvy and Stahl, 2004). While deductive method enables the utilization of the work of previous researchers, it fails to enable the identification of other unforeseen variables such as new constructs that are likely to exist. It at most enables the researcher to evaluate whether the hypothesized relationship exists and to what degree (Corbin and Strauss, 1998).

3.3.2 Inductive Approach

The inductive approach deals with the elucidation and conceptualization of a phenomenon reached through the generation of hypotheses and the development of expositions for the observed hypothetical relationships (Saunders et al, 2019). It is a methodical qualitative data analysis technique in which it is assumed that the analysis will be driven by clearly identified assessment objectives. Therefore, it is thought to necessitate the building of theory from scratch (bottom-up). The researcher starts with a field of study and allows the emergence of theory from the data (Corbin and Strauss, 1998).

3.3.3 Research Approach Selected (DEDUCTIVE)

The deductive approach rests on a research problem originating from existing theories. The theories applied in this research emanates from the ServQual model for measuring service quality, Bass and Avolio (1989) leadership model and the model of service employee management (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996). The research problem is to demonstrate the applicability of these models in the Nigerian hospitality sector with the aim of determining how leaders can influence frontline employees towards providing top quality services. Deductive

approach starts with existing theories while inductive approach starts with empirical data and ends with the generation of new theories, concepts and models. Therefore, this research mainly rests on deductive approach. Also, Deductive approach was adopted because of its low-risk nature since it is based on previously tested theories while inductive has a riskier nature due to the probability of nonappearance of a theory because of insufficient data.

3.4 Research methods

Methodology differs from a research method in that it relates to the philosophical principles underpinning the process of a research whereas a research method refers to the data collection and analysis techniques and procedures under these philosophical assumptions (Saunders et al, 2019). Hence, based on the philosophical assumptions of this study, the researcher aims to employ a quantitative research method for data collection which will involve the development of questionnaires for collection of empirical data from both the customers and employees which afterwards will be analysed statistically using IBM statistical package for social sciences, SPSS.

A numeric or statistical approach to research design constitutes a quantitative research process (Clarke, 2009). The researcher collects data in such a way that the data can be quantified, giving room for statistical analysis. The researcher tends to create meaning by measuring reality through objectivity uncovered in the data collected. Quantitative researcher tends to find explanation and predictions that can be generalized to other places and persons (Hayes, 2009). Thus, the aim is to demonstrate, validate or confirm relationships and to build generalizations that lead to theory. The quantitative research method has been categorised into three key methods: observation, experiment and survey (Kent, 2007; Schindler and Cooper, 2008).

3.4.1 Survey

Survey involves conducting survey on research participants and taking record of their responses for analysis (Schindler and Cooper, 2003). This approach has been employed extensively to investigate so many topics in business and management studies such as participants motivation, satisfaction, commitment, intention, attitude and a lot more. The investigator must have a well-defined dependent and independent variable and a clearly defined conceptual framework of the hypothesized relationships to be examined in relation to the phenomenon's observations in order to begin a survey research (Kumar, 2019). Hence it is commonly related to the deductive research approach (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). It involves the use of questionnaires and structured interviews to collect quantitative data to be analysed scientifically (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). Malhotra and Birks (2000) classified the survey strategy into three main methods; personal face-to-face survey, telephone survey and mail survey. Schindler and Cooper (2008) replaced the mail survey with the online survey. Their classification is described below;

- (1) Personal interview survey: participants are interviewed by a competent interviewer in person.
- (2) Telephone interview survey: participants are interviewed by a professional interviewer over the phone.
- (3) Self-administered survey: survey questionnaires are either sent to the participants by fax, by post, by email over the internet or by other online services.

Using survey strategies comes with advantages such as: the ease in administering the survey, consistency of the obtained data and, it is relatively simple to code, analyse and interpret the data (Malhotra and Peterson, 2006). Despite these advantages, the researcher also pointed out the constraints of using survey methods. These include: the likelihood that the desired information may not be provided by the respondents, respondents may avoid sensitive questions and lack of validity for some data set due to personal views and feelings. Schindler

and Cooper (2008) likewise pointed out some advantages of using survey such as; (a) data can be easily adapted to the desired information (data's versatility), (b) the data obtained is purely internal to the respondents and, (c) it is more efficient and cheaper than observation. Nonetheless, concerns have been raised about this method such as; (a) respondents' inability to participate as a result of daily commitments, (b) respondents may find the interview topic embarrassing and, (c) fear in respondents regarding the possible consequences that might be faced for taking part in the survey.

3.4.2 Experiment

Experiment owes much to research in natural sciences. The purpose is to study causal links. Hence can also be seen in some social sciences research mainly psychology. The approach seeks to find whether a change in one independent variable produces a change in another dependent variable (Hakim, 2012). The researcher can systematically modify the variables of the research and identify the possible outcomes by careful observation. Because it requires control and careful observation and evaluation, experiment offers the most concrete evidence of the relationship existing between the independent variable and the dependent one (Ary et al, 2002). There are numerous advantages of using the experimental approach. They include; (a) it gives the researcher the ability to navigate the independent variables (b) it is more convenient and cheaper than other quantitative research strategies and, (c) conducting a repeat of an experiment can lead towards finding the overall impact of the independent variables across situation, times and people (Schindler and Cooper, 2008). They are however not bereft of limitations. Some limitations of using the experiment approach outlined by Schindler and Cooper (2008) include: (a) generalizations from non-probability can result to problems (b) ethical limits to the control manipulation still applies (c) studies about intentions, predictions or expectations are difficult.

3.4.3 Observation

Observation is where the researcher attempts to participate in the activities of subjects and thus becomes a member of their group, organisation or community (Saunders et al, 2019). The group become fully aware of the researcher's position as an observer. Though it has been used much less than the other quantitative research strategies in business and management research, it can however be a very valuable tool usually as the main research method but supported with other methods. It involves a high level of immersion by the researcher in the research settings, with the objectives of sharing in people's lives while attempting to learn their symbolic world and understanding their meanings (Delbridge and Kirkpatrick, 1994). One key limitation pointed out by Ary et al (2002) is that participants tend to behave differently from their habitual behaviour on realising they are under observation, or they may not be honest in answering the questions. Hence, the observer effect tends to be one of the most powerful threat to the reliability and validity of data collected through observation (Malhotra and Peterson, 2006).

3.4.4 Justifications for the Survey Method

The survey method has been the most used method of research in social sciences (Ary et al, 2002). A survey has many characteristics and benefits which includes scanning a wide field of issues, populations, programmes in order to measure or describe any generalized features (Cohen et al, 2000). The use of this research method is increasing significantly especially in client-based marketing research (Kent, 2007). Surveys are cost effective and more efficient than observation. It allows the researcher to collect a huge volume of data for statistical analysis in an economical and efficient way more than observation (Kent, 2007). Surveys are the best in describing the characteristics of a big population. It makes the study of large samples very much feasible. Since this study is dealing with an established industry in Nigeria which is the

hospitality industry, the survey method appears to be the most appropriate to make use of because of its capability of covering a wide target population.

The survey method allows for the standardization of the questions. This enhances the precision of the measurements by enforcing uniformed definitions upon the participants. This also enhances the research reliability. Hence, since multiple choice closed questions are employed for data collection, the survey method is very suitable for this study's participants. The survey method enables information to be gathered and be transformed into numerical data where after the data are analysed statistically to ascertain correlations between variables. This makes it easier to justify the situation under study by using numerical data as today's management are now becoming more interested in numbers and figures. The survey method enables the generalization of the findings across the whole study population based on the study sample since the findings emerged from statistical evaluations. Therefore, employing the survey method enables the researcher to evaluate the difference between results of the study analysis and the anticipated result if the study is to be conducted over the whole target population. From the above rationale, it can be argued that the survey research strategy is by far the most suitable research strategy for this study.

3.5 Survey Instruments

Three survey instruments widely employed for data collection include personal interviews; telephone interviews and self-administered survey (Schindler and Cooper, 2008). The personal interview survey involves a trained interviewer interviewing a set of people or sample population. **The personal interview** method is categorised into four major categories; computer assisted, street, in-home and in-office methods (Schindler and Cooper, 2008). This technique promises good cooperation from participants however its major limitation is that it involves a lot of capital. There has been noticeable decline in the use of personal interview

because of the financial constraints (Schindler and Cooper, 2008). **The telephone interview** method involves interviewing the participants over a telephone by a skilled interviewer (Malhotra and Peterson, 2006). This technique generates quicker results, provides anonymity, and much cheaper than the personal interview (Schindler and Cooper, 2008). **Self-administered** survey can be conducted by either post mail or electronic mail (internet enabled). It's very much cheaper than the other two survey techniques. Self-administered survey also has an advantage over the other two methods in facilitating central control of the survey, whereby the surveys are filled in by the respondents in their own convenient time leaving less or no room for interviewer bias (Kent, 2007). However, it has its limitations which include: (a) low response rates (b) cannot be lengthy or complex (c) anxiety among some respondents, (d) the unavailability of the interviewer for explanation (Schindler and Cooper, 2008).

3.5.1 Justification of the Survey Instrument Selected

The needs and requirements of a study coupled with time, financial, and resources constraints must be considered in selecting the most suitable technique for a research study (Forza, 2002). Thus, telephone interview technique was rejected as the survey is excessively long for a telephone interview. There are two set of questionnaires. one out of the two has more than 30 questions. In addition, it is not actually favourable to respondents answering questions over the phone while on their shifts as it would reduce their concentration on their jobs. Personal interview also has been eliminated as the survey is too long, the researcher intends to reduce his involvement as much as possible to minimize bias and it will be very expensive to conduct among a huge number of customers and employees. Following this elimination process, the self-administered survey method is presumably the most appropriate for this study. In order to eliminate the drawback of the interviewer absence for probing or explanation of questions in self-administered surveys, the researcher will attach a properly designed cover letter explaining the research rationale and thus enhancing the respondents understanding. Self-administered

surveys promise anonymity which other techniques doesn't. for instance, in personal interviews, employees might not give sensitive information due to fear of repercussions. In addition, low response rates in self-administered survey can be minimised if the surveys are administered in appropriate conditions with properly written covering letters and may be incentives to motivate or encourage participants.

3.6 Data Sources

This study will involve the collection of both primary and secondary data. Secondary data which includes previously collected data from already existing sources such as industry report, government publication, journals, textbooks, company archives and similar sources will be utilised for a richer comprehension and understanding of the phenomenon. Primary data will be collected via the survey research strategy which entails the distribution of questionnaires to both customers and employees of all the hotels within the Awka capital city. The primary data collected will be used to test the hypothesis crafted from the literature review.

3.7 Data Collection Instrument and Design

Questionnaires will be utilised in this research. The development and design will be highlighted in this section.

3.7.1 Questionnaire

Questionnaire is one of the most used data collection instruments for survey research. It consists of a series of question for collecting data from the respondents. It is one of the most efficient, cheap and less time-consuming way of data collection from a large sample size. Questionnaires will be used to collect evidence in the form of data that will be coded and analysed statistically. To adequately collect enough evidence for answering the research questions. The questionnaire will be categorised into three: customers questionnaire, employees' questionnaire and managers questionnaire. Seven instruments were used in the

design of the questionnaires: the demographic information sheet, the SERVQUAL scale, the role clarity scale, job satisfaction scale, organisational commitment scale, self-efficacy scale, adaptive selling scale, multi-factor leadership scale and paternalistic leadership scale.

Customer Questionnaire

A ten-item scale based on the original SERVQUAL scale (Parasuraman et al, 1990) will be used to construct the customer questionnaire. The measure was limited to those items directly related to employee-related aspects of service quality because the goal is to measure the quality of service provided by customer contact employees, so this study is limited to the evaluation of items that specifically evaluate aspects of service quality related to employees. This modification is in line with the findings of Hartline et al (1996). As per Babakus and Boller (1992), Cronin and Taylor (1992), and Brown et al (1993) suggestions, the scale was also modified to integrate perceptions and expectations into a single measure. In terms of both reliability and validity, researchers have shown that the integration of perception and expectation into a single measure (SERVPERF) performs better than the SERVQUAL scale in regard to both reliability and validity (Babakus and Boller, 1992; Brown et al, 1993). It also decreases the time required for respondents to complete the questionnaire and also eliminates obscurity. This modification of the measure is in line with the findings of Hartline et al (1996) and Silverman and Grover (1995) that customers employ expectancy disconfirmation in assessing a firm's service quality.

The scale consists of 10 questions. All measuring customer perceived service quality based on employee responsiveness, empathy, assurance and reliability. In addition, the scale includes the demographic characteristics of the respondents in terms of gender, age, income and education. These demographic characteristics are treated as independent variables according to which customer perceived service quality may vary. Data collected from this questionnaire survey will assist in answering research question number 1, "what perceptions do customers

have about the service quality delivery in the Nigerian hospitality sector?”. Hotel guests are asked to rate each item using a five-point Likert scale ranging from “much worse than I expected” to “much better than I expected”. The higher the scores, the higher the perceived service quality. Five-point Likert scale is chosen over seven-point Likert scale to reduce confusion in respondent. In addition, it also helps to reduce the frustration level of respondents with seven-point Likert scale questionnaires. The questionnaires will be constructed online using google forms, printed out and administered to hotel guests at the point of checkout.

Employee Questionnaire

Also, to be designed using the five-point Likert scaling to collect nominal, ordinal and interval data, the employee Questionnaires will be administered to employees to collect evidence in form of data regarding employee’s role clarity, job satisfaction, adaptability, self-efficacy and commitment to service quality. To remain consistent with previous research, this questionnaire will be based on measures from studies on employee’s role clarity, job satisfaction, adaptability and self-efficacy. These includes:

The seventeen-item scale of Chonko et al (1986) tests the degree to which employees clearly understand how to fulfill their duties and perform their job roles. The scale asks customer contact employees to demonstrate how confident they are about performing job roles on a scale from "not at all certain" to "completely certain." Higher scores represent greater role clarity>

Brown and Peterson (1993) five item scale that evaluate the degree to which employees are satisfied with a number of job dimensions such as compensation, internal service, pay, supervisor treatments etc. The scale asks employees to demonstrate the level of their satisfaction with each aspect, using a five-point scale from "extremely dissatisfied" to "extremely satisfied." Higher scores represent higher satisfaction with the job after averaging across all aspects.

Jones (1986) eight scale items designed to assess the perceptions of employees about their confidence, credentials, abilities and job skills. The scale was modified by dropping 4 interrelated items. Employees scored each item on a scale of five points from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." Greater scores represent greater perceived self-efficacy.

The adaptive selling scale of 16 items was updated by lowering 12 redundant items by Spiro and Weitz (1990). The final 4-item scale measures the capacity of customer contact employees to adapt to varying service encounters by altering their customer service approach. Employees expressed their agreement with each item via a five-point scale from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. Greater scores represent a greater level of adaptability in employees.

The scale will also consist with a section for the demographic characteristics of the employees in terms of gender, age, position, length of employment and education. These are treated as independent variables according to which customer perceived service quality may vary. Given the above, the questionnaires were designed in a manner that meets the objectives of the study. A considerable reliability and validity are expected to be established to verify the questionnaires efficiency.

Validity

Techniques for carrying out a research should be reviewed for validity and reliability (Saunders, 2012). The degree to which the researcher has calculated what he has set out to measure is known as validity (Smith, 1991). Is the researcher measuring what he/she think he/she is measuring? Babbie (1989) defined validity as the degree to which an empirical measure satisfactorily explains the concept investigated to an acceptable standard. Achieving a perfect validity in a research is however impossible (Saunders, 2019). Therefore, the study aims to maximise validity as much as possible. We have content and construct validity. Both kinds of validity will be applied to the development of the two questionnaires.

Content validity

Content validity relates to the extent to which the investigative questions are sufficiently covered by the measurement device (Saunders, 2019). The measurement device in this research includes the measurement questions in the questionnaires. In order to arrive at a good judgement on what is “adequate coverage”, a carefully put literature review and guidance from specialists in the field to assess the suitability and appropriateness of each measurement questions in the questionnaire will help establish content validity (Kumar, 2019). Careful definition of this study through a thorough literature review and the adoption of items and scales previously tested for content validity in past studies within the area of leadership, marketing and human resource management justifies this study content validity.

Construct validity

Construct validity is determined by establishing each construct’s contribution to the overall variance observed in a phenomenon. Factor analysis will be employed in the study to help determine the construct adequacy of the measuring device used. Factor analysis and multitrait-multimethod analyses are key established statistical tools that help in determining the adequacy of construct’s measuring device (Tabachnick and Fidel, 2007). Tabachnick and Fidel (2007) propose that factor loadings with an absolute value of less than 0.32 (reflecting 10% of the mutual variance) be ignored. Factors retained should possess not less than three items with a loading higher than 0.4. A relationship also exists between the sample size and the appropriate factors. Stevens et al (2012) recommends that a sample size of 100 factor loadings is significant at the 0.01 when they are greater than 0.512, a sample of 200 are significant when they are greater than 0.364 and a sample of 300 are significant when they are greater than 0.298.

There are two types of construct validity: convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity refers to the extent to which a scale correlates with other scales of the same

construct while discriminant validity refers to the extent to which a construct is distinct from other constructs. Homogeneity of scales in the same constructs is explained by convergent validity while heterogeneity between different constructs is explained by discriminant validity. Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion for convergent validity requires the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) greater than 0.5. Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion for discriminant validity requires that factor loadings indicators on the assigned construct have to be higher than all loadings of the constructs with condition that cut off value is higher than 0.70. According to this method, diagonal values must be greater than horizontal and vertical values. The researcher aims to increase the relationship between scales in the same construct (convergent validity) while distinguishing one construct from others (discriminant validity). Both convergent and discriminant validity are established and illustrated further in the next chapter.

Reliability

Reliability refers to the extent that the method of data collection employed in a study will give similar or same results at different times under the same or similar conditions (Kumar, 2019). For a research tool to be reliable, it has to be consistent and stable. The more consistent and stable a research instrument is, the more reliable it becomes. Internal consistency is one of the methods for determining relationship in quantitative research instrument. It involves correlating the responses to each question in the questionnaire with responses to other questions in the questionnaire. The reliability of the research instruments is tested using Cronbach's most frequently used methods for calculating internal consistency (Saunders, 2019). Cronbach alpha (α) is the most commonly used measure of internal consistency reliability (Kumar, 2019). Reliability coefficient (α) or Cronbach alpha can range from 0 to 1, with 0 reflecting an unreliable questionnaire and 1 reflecting a perfectly reliable questionnaire. A reliability coefficient (α) of 0.70 or greater is believed to be satisfactory reliability. Various conditions can affect Cronbach values. Some of these are:

- a. Distribution of score: skewed data reduces Cronbach alpha value while normal data increases it.
- b. Numbers of items: Less than 10 variables in a scale could cause Cronbach alpha to be low
- c. Items with 0, 1, and negative scores: such items should be eliminated
- d. Wording of items: reversing of negative worded questionnaire should be done before scoring.

The reliability of the scales is established and illustrated further in the next chapter.

3.8 Selection of Research Hotels

A minimum target of 12 indigenously owned hotels were planned to be surveyed. However, due to the total shutdown of the entire hospitality sector due to the pandemic, a total of only 4 were finally surveyed. They are Hotel 1, Hotel 2, Hotel 3 and Hotel 4 (not their actual names but assigned numbers due to anonymity and confidentiality). The core activities of these hotels are very similar which include providing accommodation, food and drinks to guests, providing leisure facilities like swimming pool, gyms, providing conference and banqueting facilities, and business services. They also provide facilities for transporting tourist to tourist attractions and monuments within the state and its surroundings.

3.9 Sampling

Studying an entire population of the research subjects has been impossible for researchers due to the enormous time and capital it consumes. Hence, researchers tend to collect data from a portion of the population after which the results of the analysis can be generalized to that population. Thus, sampling is the process of selecting the right individuals, objects, or events as representatives for the entire population (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). The target population for this study is all the customers and employees of the hotels in Awka, Nigeria.

Customer sampling

Getting the correct sample frame for the customers is still difficult as none of the hotels under survey have a complete list of their customers. Therefore, the researcher is making use of the convenience non-probability sampling technique. According to Saunders et al (2019) “in the situation where it is not possible to get a complete list of the respondents to form the sample frame, a non-probability sampling technique should be adopted”.

Employee sampling

The four hotels surveyed have a total of 167 employees. In order to get insight knowledge, all the employees from various units within the hotels were surveyed. Two of the hotels have 40 employees each, while the other two hotels have 45 and 42 employees each as shown in the table below. Hence a total population of 167 employees. The sample size is estimated to be 117 at 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. This calculation was done using the survey monkey sample size calculator. Simple random probability sampling technique was employed to select the sample employees at each of the hotels till a total of 117 was reached. Questionnaires were thereafter administered to these employees via post.

Hotel	Sample Units	Population	Sample size	Sampling technique
Hotel 1	Employees	40	28	Simple random probability
Hotel 2	Employees	40	28	Simple random probability
Hotel 3	Employees	45	32	Simple random probability
Hotel 4	Employees	42	29	Simple random probability

Table 0.1: Sample size for employees. (Created by the researcher)

3.10 The Research Participants

Hotels play a significant role in Anambra state’s hospitality sector and that of Nigeria at large. The level of contact between the service employees and customers is very high in hotels

(Hartline and Ferrell, 1996). Hence, quality employee-customer interactions are valuable for hotels. Due to the high level of contact, contact employees are posed with great opportunity to influence customers' perception of service quality (Singh, 1993).

12 hotels were contacted for the study, of which 8 agreed to participate. Data from the biggest four were successfully collected before the pandemic struck and the consequent complete shutdown of the entire hospitality sector for months. Hence all eight were not surveyed. This affected the number of participants reported for this study. Initially the researcher intended to recruit a total minimum of 200 employees and 700 hotel guests. However, data were only obtained from a total of 95 employees and a total of 104 customers as a result of the disruptions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. The samples allow for testing the hypothesis but inhibit the generalisation of the results.

Hotel reception staff, housekeeping staff, food/room service, Bell staff and supervisors were all chosen as they perform several interactions with hotel guests whilst reporting to the owner/manager that provides the leadership. Most of the participants have worked at their hotels for less than 5 years, about 60% of the participants. Only about 2% have worked at their hotels for more than 10 years. The participants are predominantly females, about 63.8% and only few of them have some form of university education.

The customers are mainly domestic travellers using the hotel services for leisure or mainly business purposes. More than 60% of the participants are males. The hotel sector in Awka caters for all age groups. The predominant age group of the sample is 18 – 29 (29.1%) followed by 50 – 59 (24%). Most of the participants have a good source of income, 32.7% of them earns above 250,000 naira, followed by 31.7% that earns between 100,001 – 250,000 naira. Due to high pricing at these hotels, the participants are likely from rich and educated background

mainly using the hotels' service for business purpose or leisure as 81.6% of them indicate they have some form of university education.

Given the above, data on leadership styles and service-oriented behaviours of employees were obtained from the first sample (hotel employees) while data on customer perception of service quality were obtained from the second sample (hotel guests).

3.11 Data Analysis

The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) and SMARTPLS were used for coding and analysing the study data. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation analysis were both performed using the SPSS while structural equation modelling was performed using the SMARTPLS. Descriptive statistics was used for the demographical data, customer perception of service quality, employees' attitudes and leadership styles which were presented using means, standard deviations. Independent sample t-test and analysis of one-way variance (ANOVA) were utilised to identify the variances between groups. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to establish the relationship between variables.

Structural equation modelling was applied to establish the relationships between multiple independent and dependent variables in the conceptual framework. This helps to gain a better understanding of the contribution of the hotel managers leadership style on employees' service behaviour. The alpha coefficient test was examined via Cronbach's alpha coefficient to test the scales' reliability. Cronbach's alpha coefficient measures the levels of internal consistency between interrelated items (Pallant, 2011). Presentation of data was carried out in table formats to aid readers in understanding the whole picture. Table formats facilitate the presentation of large amount of data in a brief but comprehensive manner (Parahoo, 2014).

3.12 Pilot study

Prior to the full distribution of questionnaires, a pilot study was conducted. Questionnaires were administered to 10 guests of the hotels. The researcher's major aim was to identify any difficulties that may hinder the collection of data during the main data collection stage. A pilot study is needed to determine the feasibility of a research and to identify and clarify any issues with conducting the research within the timeframe (Kumar, 2019). It helps to identify and solve any potential problems that may occur in the main study (Gerrish, 2015) and provide opportunities for possible solutions.

After obtaining ethical approval form from the university of Scotland ethics committee., a total of 10 customer questionnaires and 20 employee questionnaire and 4 manager questionnaire of each of the four hotels, their staff and customers. The questionnaires included a cover letter assuring respondents of full anonymity and confidentiality. Also, respondents were asked to write down on the questionnaires the time they started and finished completing the questionnaires. This informs the researcher on how long it takes the respondents to complete the questionnaires. The average time taken to fill the questionnaires was between 10-15 minutes. All the questionnaires were dully filled, valid and then analysed.

The pilot study identified a very low perceived service quality among the surveyed customers. According to the table below, the mean score for the items was from 2.5000 to 3.3000. this thus reflects a low perceived service quality. The staff courteousness, responsiveness and attention to customer needs received the lowest score of 2.5000. Only 30% of the customers intend to recommend their hotel to friends and family while the greater 70% will not recommend. This result reflects the poor level of service quality as perceived by customers in this sector and gives a hint as to what to expect in the main study.

Variables	(No)	Mean
Receiving prompt service from employees	10	2.6000
Employees never being too busy to respond to my requests	10	2.5000
Employees behaviour that instils confidence in me	10	2.7000
Safety you feel in your transactions with the employees	10	3.3000
The employees' courteousness	10	2.5000
The employees' ability to answer questions	10	2.6000
The individual attention received you receive from us	10	2.6000
The personal attention you received from our employees	10	2.5000
Having your best interests at heart	10	2.8000
Our employees' ability to understand your specific needs	10	2.9000

Table 0.2: Pilot study for customers perceived service quality. N= Number of respondents (Created by the researcher)

The pilot study also identified that paternalistic leadership is the predominant leadership style among managers in the hospitality sector in Anambra. Employees were surveyed to understand leadership styles from their different viewpoints based on the items adapted from paternalistic and transformational leadership scales (Cheng et al, 2004 and Avolio and Bass, 2005 respectively). From the employees' perspective, the mean scores for the paternalistic leadership items were between 4.4500 and 3.3000 with the overall score at 3.5266. While the mean scores for transformational leadership are between 3.0000 and 1.9500 with the overall score at 2.3252. These means scores reflect that the surveyed customer contact employees perceive their managers as more paternalistic than transformational.

Subscales	Number	Mean
Appears intimidating in front of his/her subordinates (Authoritarianism)	20	3.8500
Brings me a lot of pressure when we work together (Authoritarianism)	20	4.1500
Very strict with his/her subordinates	20	4.0500
Scolds me when I fail expected target (Authoritarianism)	20	4.3000
Disciplines subordinates for violation of his/her principles (Authoritarianism)	20	4.4500
Often shows his/her concern about me (Benevolence)	20	3.5500
Understands my preference enough to accommodate my personal requests (Benevolence)	20	3.5500
Encourages me when I encounter difficulties in work (Benevolence)	20	3.4000
Would try to understand the real cause of my unsatisfied performance (Benevolence)	20	3.4000
Trains and coaches me when I lack required abilities at work (Benevolence)	20	3.6000
He/she is responsible on the job (Moral)	20	3.8000
He/she takes responsibility on job and never shirks his/her duty (Moral)	20	3.6000
Sets an example to me in all aspects (Moral)	20	3.6000
Well self-disciplined before demanding upon others (Moral)	20	3.8000
Leads rather than follows subordinates to deal with difficult tasks (Moral)	20	3.3000
Express with a few simple words what we could and should do (Inspirational Motivation)	20	1.9500
Enable others to think about old problems in new ways (Intellectual Stimulation)	20	2.0000
Providing others with new ways of looking at puzzling things (Intellectual Stimulation)	20	2.4000
Help others develop themselves (Individualized Consideration)	20	2.1500
Let others know how he/she think they are doing (Individualized Consideration)	20	2.4500
Give personal attention to others who seem rejected (Individualized Consideration)	20	3.0000

Table 0.3: Pilot study for employees' perception of managers' leadership styles. N= number (Created by the researcher)

From the managers' perspective, the mean score for the paternalistic leadership items was between 2.5000 and 5.0000 with the overall score at 4.0000. While the mean scores for transformational leadership items was between 1.5000 and 3.0000 with the overall score at 2.0000.

Subscales	Number	Mean
Appears intimidating in front of my subordinates (Authoritarianism)	4	2.5000
Brings a lot of pressure when I work with my subordinates (Authoritarianism)	4	2.7500
Very strict with my subordinates (Authoritarianism)	4	4.5000
Scolds my subordinates when he/she fail expected target (Authoritarianism)	4	4.5000
Disciplines subordinates for violation of his/her principles (Authoritarianism)	4	4.5000
Often shows concern about my subordinates (Benevolence)	4	5.0000
Understands my subordinate's preferences enough to accommodate his/her personal requests (Benevolence)	4	4.5000
Encourages my subordinates when he/she encounter difficulties in work (Benevolence)	4	4.5000
Would try to understand the real cause of my subordinates unsatisfied performance (Benevolence)	4	4.7500
Train and coach my subordinates when he/she lack required abilities at work (Benevolence)	4	4.5000
I'm very responsible on the job (Moral)	4	4.5000
I take responsibility on job and never shirks from my duty (Moral)	4	4.5000
I set an example to my subordinates in all aspects (Moral)	4	4.5000
Well self-disciplined before demanding upon others (Moral)	4	4.5000
Leads rather than follows subordinates to deal with difficult tasks (Moral)	4	4.5000
Express with a few simple words what we could and should do (Inspirational Motivation)	4	1.5000
Enable others to think about old problems in new ways (Intellectual Stimulation)	4	2.5000
Providing others with new ways of looking at puzzling things (Intellectual Stimulation)	4	1.7500
Help others develop themselves (Individualized Consideration)	4	3.0000
Let others know how he/she think they are doing (Individualized Consideration)	4	1.5000
Give personal attention to others who seem rejected (Individualized Consideration)	4	1.7500

Table 0.4: Managers' perception of their own leadership styles. N= number (Created by the researcher)

The employees showed higher overall score than the managers for transformational leadership subscales but lower overall score for paternalistic leadership subscales. For both the employees and managers the highest scoring subscale in transformational leadership was individualised consideration. Under paternalistic leadership, authoritarianism scored highest for employees while benevolence scored highest for managers. This difference between the employees and managers perception of their paternalistic leadership reflects that those employees perceive the managers of being more authoritarian than either of benevolence or moral. It's fair to agree with their judgement as the managers must have been biased in completing the questionnaires due to the negative connotations widely attached to authoritarian leadership.

In general, both employees and managers concurred in their perceptions of the predominant style of leadership in the sector. As paternalistic leadership gained the highest mean score from both the managers and employees' perspective, coupled with enough evidence from the literature review, this study will hence focus on the effects of paternalistic leadership style on service quality delivery in the hospitality sector of Anambra State, Nigeria.

3.13 Limitations of the Research Methodology

Firstly, the total shutdown of the entire hospitality sector in Nigeria and travel restrictions due to the impact of Covid-19 pandemic suppressed the chances of surveying more hotels to reach a larger sample size. Like previously mentioned, 12 hotels were contacted for the study, of which 8 agreed to participate. Data from the biggest four were successfully collected before the pandemic struck and the consequent complete shutdown of the entire hospitality sector for months. Hence all eight were not surveyed. This affected the number of participants reported for this study. Thus, there is potential that enough statistical power wouldn't be attained due to the smaller sample size of the research participants.

Secondly, the researcher initially intended to carry out an observation and a face-to-face interview with the owner/managers of the hotels. Again, this wasn't achieved due to the Covid-19 Pandemic which impacted international travel that lasted for months. The findings are anticipated to be richer if the researcher had carried out some form of qualitative means of collecting data from the owners/managers. However, the study is wholly quantitative alike similar past studies.

Thirdly, there are concerns about the potential of social desirability bias which is defined as the tendency of survey respondents to answer questions in a manner that will be viewed favourably by others. A social desirability scale would have been included in the employee questionnaire but that would further lengthen the questionnaire, which might affect the response rate.

3.14 Conclusion

This chapter has presented in detail the research methodology for the present study. A descriptive, cross-sectional and correlational design was used to study the relationship between hotel managers leadership styles and customer perceived service quality. Positivism research paradigm and deductive research approach was followed throughout. Hence, data was collected quantitatively using survey questionnaires from two set of respondents: employees and customers. Prior this, the sample characteristics were presented.

In addition, a discussion on the data analysis technique and procedure was carried out. Finally, this chapter discussed the pilot study which was needed to determine the feasibility of the research and to identify and clarify any issues with conducting the full-scale research within the time frame. Results of the pilot study revealed a very low perception of service quality among guests of the four hotels. It also identified paternalistic leadership as the dominant leadership style in this industry.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This chapter of the dissertation presents the results of the study regarding the role of leadership styles in service quality delivery in the Nigerian hospitality sector. The first section presents the results of the study regarding guests' perceived service quality in the surveyed hotels. It involves descriptive statistics where mean scores to the responses were measured to assess perception of service quality from the guests' perspective. The second section presents the results of the study regarding the role of paternalistic style in the delivery of superior quality services among these hotels. It measures how the dimensions of paternalistic leadership style influence employees' attitudes and behaviour towards delivering top service quality. The main statistical techniques for this section involve Pearson's correlation analysis and structural equation modelling which tests the relationships.

4.1 Customer Perception of Service Quality

The study explored the opinion of customers about the service they received from their respective hotels. This was to evaluate their perceptions of the services delivered by the customer contact employees of the hotels. The mean score was calculated. High mean score reflects high perception of service quality while low mean score reflects low perception of service quality. The study findings showed that the overall score of customer perceived service quality of the hotels was 2.6, that is 52% of the total score of 5, with standard deviation at 1.2. This is a relatively low score. There is not much gap in the mean scores among the hotels as in the diagram below.

Hotels	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Hotel 1	25	2.6	1.3
Hotel 2	25	2.5	1.2
Hotel 3	25	2.6	1.2
Hotel 4	29	2.6	1.2
Total	104	2.6	1.2

Table 0.1: Overall mean score on customer perception of service quality. (Created by the researcher)

The low mean scores reflect that, customers have low perception of the service quality in these hotels. The similar scores among the hotels show that hotels in this sector don't operate differently from each other in regard to service delivery. Many customers expressed a negative perception of the quality of services among the hotels in regard to factors like the promptness of the service, the courteousness of the employees, the attention given to the guest by the hotels' staff during the service encounter.

The customer perception of service quality also varies in relation to the demographic characteristics of the customers. This is illustrated in the table 4.2 below. Like explained earlier, high mean score represents a high perception of service quality among the customers. Based on the statistical significance values, ($p < .05$) the mean scores for overall customer perception of service quality differ according to age ($p = 0.02$), income ($P = 0.00$) and education ($P = 0.01$). There was no significance difference between the mean scores for females and males in the gender group as P value (0.27) was greater than 0.05. the observed difference must have been due to chance. Females expressed lower perception of service quality compared to males. The old expressed lower perception of service quality compared to the young. Those with higher education expressed lower perception of service quality compared to those with less education. And as for income, the rich expressed lower perception of service quality than the less rich. The results show that the customers with better livelihood and life experiences expects more from their hotels in regards to service quality.

Demographic Characteristics	(No)	Mean	Standard Deviation	Sig
Gender: Male	62	2.8	1.2	0.27
Female	42	2.4	1.2	
Age: 18-29	28	3.3	1.3	0.02
30-39	20	3.0	1.3	
40-49	23	2.1	0.8	
50-59	26	2.2	1.1	
>60	7	2.2	1.1	
Education: Some Sec School	5	3.9	1.3	0.01
Sec School	14	3.1	1.3	
Some University	42	2.7	1.2	
University	43	2,2	1.1	
Income: 30001-50000	16	3.9	0.8	0.00
50001-100000	21	3.2	1.3	
100001-250000	32	2.4	1.2	
>250000	35	1.8	0.6	

Table 0.2: Mean scores on customer perception of service quality based on demographic characteristics. (Created by the researcher)

4.1.1 Differences in mean score of customer perception of service quality according to demographic characteristics.

The table 4.3 below shows that the females using the services of hotel (1) expressed the highest perception of service quality (M=3.06) while females dealing with hotel (3) expressed the lowest perception (M=1.95). The low customer perception of service quality among female respondents in hotel 3 and 4 might be due to the unfriendliness of the staff in their encounter with the hotels' services. Women pay more attention to the atmosphere in the hotel and friendly staff attitudes than men. Gender affects service quality perceptions (Juwaheer, 2010; Aljasser and Sasidhar, 2013). As Iacobucci and Ostrom (1993) contends, women focus more on the interpersonal components of a service interaction. Female guest attribute higher level of expectations in service quality dimensions than their male counterparts.

Hotel	Male	Female
Hotel 1	2.18	3.06
Hotel 2	2.63	2.47
Hotel 3	2.93	1.95
Hotel 4	3,01	2.11

Table 0.3: Differences in mean scores on customer perception of service quality according to the gender of the respondents. (Created by the researcher)

The table 4.4 below shows that customers over the age of 60, dealing with hotel (1) expressed the highest customer perception of service quality (M=4.50) which is 90% of the total score. The customers above 60 years dealing with hotel (3) showed the lowest customer perception of service quality (M=1.7) which is 34% of the total score. The mean scores for the other age classes (18-29, 30-39, 40-49, 50-59) varied in the range between 4.50 and 1.7. Distinctions in customer perception of service quality in terms of age and the hotels are significant ($P < 0.05$).

The result is a reflection that older age group may find it discouraging using online booking and reservation systems rather than the old-fashioned system of booking at the reception desk. Hence, they are expected to have more interactions with the receptionist and expectations are expected to be very high during these encounters as they are more experienced travellers than the younger ones.

Hotel	18-29 years	30-39 years	40-49 years	50-59 years	>60 years
Hotel 1	3.74	1.83	1.83	2.86	4.50
Hotel 2	4.10	3.56	1.94	2.22	1.75
Hotel 3	3.69	2.91	2.11	1.94	1.70
Hotel 4	2.56	3.80	2.45	2.02	2.06

Table 0.4: Differences in mean scores on customer perception of service quality based on the age of the respondents. (Created by the researcher)

With regards to the income of the customers and perception of service quality, perception of service quality differs according to the income of the customers. The table 4.5 below shows that those with 50,001-100,000-naira monthly income, dealing with hotel (2) expressed the highest perception of service quality (M=4.20) while those with a monthly income of over 250,000 naira dealing with hotel (1) expressed the lowest perception of service quality

(M=1.66). those with a monthly income of 30,001-50,000 naira and 50,001-100,000 naira expressed a substantially higher perception of service quality than those with a much higher monthly income in all the hotels. Customers with different income levels have been found to have different perceptions of service quality (Scott, 1993). The disparity in the perception of service quality based on income levels isn't quite surprising as the wealthiest guests are expected to be the most critical hotel visitors. The more affluent a traveller, the more critical they will be given that the pricing is not the same for every room in each of the hotels. A more affluent traveller paying for premium hotel services expect those services to be really good value for money. Maybe this might be related to their educational level as well as it's generally accepted that individuals with higher income levels also have higher education levels (Farley, 1964).

Hotel	30001-50000	50001-100000	100001-250000	>250000
Hotel 1	3.96	3.70	1.89	1.66
Hotel 2	3.80	4.20	2.30	1.86
Hotel 3	4.10	4.11	2.06	1.87
Hotel 4	3.87	2.05	2.97	2.03

Table 0.5: Differences in mean scores on customer perception of service quality based on the income (Naira) of the respondents. (Created by the researcher)

From the table 4.6 below, it can be deduced that level of education also affects a customer's perception of service quality in hotels. Customer perception of service quality differs according to how educated and uneducated the customers are. Customers with only some sort of secondary school education dealing with hotel (4) expressed the highest perception of service quality (M=4.6) while those with university degrees dealing with hotel (1) expressed the lowest perception of service quality (M=2.10). Also, university graduates scored very low in other hotels (hotel 2 (M=2.31), hotel 3 (M=2.34), hotel 4 (M=2.30) compared to the other groups of respondents. Hence differences in perception of service quality according to the customers level of education and the hotels are significant ($P < 0.05$). Kotler (2010) suggest an increase in educated people leads to an increase in the demand for quality products and services. Those

with higher education are expected to easily detect issues with employees during a service encounter than the less educated guests. The less educated guests might only look out for a comfortable bed, good shower and clean rooms whereas the more educated ones probably of working class travelling for business meetings may expect reliable Wi-Fi connection, a plug for charging all gadgets, an iron, a food menu, a spacious space to work to include tables and chairs, and most especially a warm welcome from the employees giving the necessary information to help you navigate around the town.

Hotel	Some Secondary school	Secondary school	Some University	University
Hotel 1	3.53	2.55	3.02	2.10
Hotel 2	4.40	2.68	2.31
Hotel 3	3.02	3.39	2.34
Hotel 4	4.60	3.48	2.27	2.30

Table 0.6: Differences in mean scores on customer perception of service quality based on the education level of the respondents. (Created by the researcher)

4.2 Customer Contact Employees' Attitudes

The statistical analysis of the data on the customer contact employees attitudinal and behavioural responses (role clarity, job satisfaction, self-efficacy and adaptability) are presented in this section. This mainly involved descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation etc).

4.2.1 Role clarity

As was explained earlier in the methodology, the 17-item scale for measuring role clarity intends to evaluate the hotels customer contact employees' role clarity. High score reflects high clarity in regards to the employee's role while low score reflects low clarity.

The data analysis shows that the mean score for role clarity is 2.7, that is 54% of the total score. This reflects low clarity on the employees undertaking of their roles in their respective hotels. The mean scores for employees of each hotel are shown in the table below. The means scores

of role clarity for the hotels range between 2.3 to 3, i.e., 46% to 60% of the overall score which is a relatively low score range.

Hotels	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Hotel 1	20	3.0	1.2
Hotel 2	25	2.9	1.0
Hotel 3	25	2.3	1.1
Hotel 4	25	2.5	1.0
Total	95	2.7	1.1

Table 0.7: Mean scores for employees of each hotel on role clarity. (Created by the researcher)

To evaluate the differences in role clarity based on the employees' demographic characteristics, analysis of the data revealed the results shown in table 4.8. The table illustrates there is no significant difference in terms of role clarity among all the demographic characteristics. This reflects that, demographic characteristics have no influence on employees understanding of the information or instructions that is needed for them to perform in service encounters. However, those in the age group 51-60 expressed a very low role clarity. This might be as a result of the effect of new technology and new work practices hence they constantly need guidance and instructions to cope.

Demographic characteristics	Number	Mean	Sig
Gender: Male	35	2.84	0.37
Female	60	2.54	
Age: 18-30	42	2.77	0.42
31-40	45	2.71	
41-50	5	2.55	
51-60	3	0.15	
Education: Some secondary school	37	2.35	0.18
Secondary school graduate	37	2.76	
Some university	10	3.09	
University graduate	11	3.22	
Length of employment: 1-5 years	56	2.72	0.40
6-10 years	35	2.61	
11-15 years	3	3.39	
16-20 years	1	1.82	

Position:	Front desk/customer service	30	2.92	0.26
	Housekeeping	23	2.54	
	Food/room service	21	2.48	
	Bell staff	16	2.43	
	Supervisor	5	3.63	

Table 0.8: Mean scores for role clarity based on employees' demographics. (Created by the researcher)

4.2.2 Job satisfaction

The Brown and Peterson (1993) five items scale was utilized to evaluate the extent to which customer contact employees are satisfied with their jobs. The mean score range between 2.40 and 2.68. the lower the score the lower the job satisfaction according to the employees. The total means score for the four hotels was 2.53 which means 50% of the overall score reflecting low job satisfaction among the hotels staff.

Hotels	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Hotel 1	20	2.68	1.32
Hotel 2	25	2.50	1.21
Hotel 3	25	2.56	1.09
Hotel 4	25	2.40	1.12
Total	95	2.53	1.18

Table 0.9: Mean scores for employees of each hotel on job satisfaction. (Created by the researcher)

To evaluate the differences in job satisfaction based on the employees' demographic characteristics, analysis of the data revealed the following results table 4.10 below. It shows the lack of a significant difference in regard to employee job satisfaction among all the demographics. This demonstrates that demographic characteristics don't determine satisfaction with jobs. However, it is expected that older employees and employees that have longer year of service with their hotels would express more dissatisfaction in their roles as they would feel less valuable when they have been with same hotel for years without any form of promotion based on loyalty and length of service. Hence lack of opportunities for career advancement maybe a huge factor in most of these employees' dissatisfaction in the sector. Some scholars have shown that older workers are more satisfied with their jobs than younger workers (Bernal et al, 1998; Saner and Eyupoglu, 2012). This higher job satisfaction among older employees

may be due to the perks that come with having a long career including higher salaries, better benefits and promotions. These are rewards are however rarely obtainable in small hospitality enterprises in Nigeria. Hence the outcome of the analysis might be because of some unfavorable attitude towards aging in a low paying job with no hope of pension and good retirement package. Turner (1955) contend that workers begin to feel hopeless as they contemplate growing older in a job which hold little interest to them and which may, in addition, begin to demand a pace too fast for their advancing years. Their morale decreases and they begin dreaming of ways to leave the company, although they cannot afford to do so (Saleh and Otis, 1964).

Demographic characteristics	Number	Mean	Sig
Gender: Male	35	2.46	0.58
Female	60	2.56	
Age: 18-30	42	2.70	0.39
31-40	45	2.43	
41-50	5	2.28	
51-60	3	1.86	
Education: Some secondary school	37	2.44	0.70
Secondary school graduate	37	2.51	
Some university	10	2.68	
University graduate	11	2.68	
Length of employment: 1-5 years	56	2.62	0.53
6-10 years	35	2.39	
11-15 years	3	2.52	
16-20 years	1	1.80	
Position: Front desk/customer service	30	2.47	0.29
Housekeeping	23	2.62	
Food/room service	21	2.53	
Bell staff	16	2.18	
Supervisor	5	3.44	

Table 0.10: Mean scores for job satisfaction based on employees' demographics. (Created by the researcher)

4.2.3 Self efficacy

Jones (1986) scale was adapted to measure employees' perceptions about their job skills, abilities, qualifications, and confidence. The mean score range between 2.93 to 3.67. the lower the score the lower the self-efficacy of the employees. The overall mean score for the four

hotels was 3.40. this means 68% of the total score which is a moderate score reflecting that most of the employees have confidence in their abilities to fulfil their tasks.

Hotels	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Hotel 1	20	3.60	1.09
Hotel 2	25	3.67	1.20
Hotel 3	25	2.93	1.09
Hotel 4	25	3.41	1.14
Total	95	3.40	1.13

Table 0.11: Mean scores for employees of each hotel on self-efficacy. (Created by the researcher)

The differences in employees' self-efficacy according to their demographics was evaluated and expressed in the below table. Regards to the differences of self-efficacy based on employees' demographics, data analysis shows that self-efficacy significantly varies in relation to gender and education ($P,0.05$). males expressed higher self-efficacy ($M=4.00$) compared to females ($M=3.17$). there is significant difference between the two groups at ($P=0.04$). regarding level of education, the table shows that university graduates expressed higher self-efficacy ($M=4.27$), followed by employees with some sort of university education ($M=4.00$), secondary school graduates ($M=3.43$) and those that didn't graduate from secondary school (2.92). there is a significant difference between these four groups at $P= 0.02$. It's no surprise that the employees in the age group 51-60 are less self-efficacious than their colleagues given the circumstances surrounding the clarity of their roles. This result is in line with the global measures of self-efficacy which shows age differences, with older adults having less self-efficacy and greater concern about their performance than younger adults (Berry et al, 1989; Hertzog et al, 1989; Mensah and Lebbaeus, 2013; Bausch et al, 2014). Reduced self-efficacy could only occur for highly difficult tasks or only for unfamiliar tasks (West and Berry, 1994; Riggio et al, 2010; McCoy, 2010).

Demographic characteristics	Number	Mean	Sig
Gender: Male	35	4.00	0.04
Female	60	3.17	
Age: 18-30	42	3.52	0.52
31-40	45	3.33	
41-50	5	3.33	
51-60	3	2.49	
Education: Some secondary school	37	2.92	0.02
Secondary school graduate	37	3.43	
Some university	10	4.00	
University graduate	11	4.27	
Length of employment: 1-5 years	56	3.41	0.59
6-10 years	35	3.34	
11-15 years	3	3.83	
16-20 years	1	2.50	
Position: Front desk/customer service	30	3.54	0.32
Housekeeping	23	3.26	
Food/room service	21	3.08	
Bell staff	16	3.48	
Supervisor	5	4.05	

Table 0.12: Mean scores for self-efficacy based on employees' demographics. (Created by the researcher)

4.2.4 Adaptability

Spiro and Weitz (1990) 16 item adaptive selling scale was modified by dropping 12 redundant items to measure customer contact employees' ability to adapt to changing service encounters by altering their approach toward customers. The mean scores for the employees' responses range between 2.82 and 3.31. low score represents low employees' adaptability while high scores represent high employees' adaptability. The overall mean score for the four hotels was 3.11, which is 62% of the total score, reflecting moderate adaptability level among the employees.

Hotels	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Hotel 1	20	3.31	1.30
Hotel 2	25	3.26	1.14
Hotel 3	25	2.82	1.00
Hotel 4	25	3.05	1.08
Total	95	3.11	1.19

Table 0.13: Mean scores for employees of each hotel on adaptability. (Created by the researcher)

The differences in adaptability according to the employees' demographic characteristics was measured and presented in the table below. There is no significant difference in terms of adaptability among all the demographic characteristics except for education which shows a significant difference ($P < 0.005$). Regarding level of education, the table shows that university graduates expressed higher adaptability ($M = 3.90$), followed by employees with some sort of university education ($M = 3.52$), secondary school graduates ($M = 3.05$) and those that didn't graduate from secondary school (2.78). A significant difference exists between these four groups at $P = 0.02$. Hence, customer contact employees with better education will show more adaptability in their behaviour to varying service encounters by changing their approach toward guests than their less educated counterparts. Age is also a visible factor in adaptability. It is a general knowledge that people find it harder to adapt to new situations as they age (Barth, 2000; Niessen et al, 2009; Stathokostas et al, 2013). Most men in latter middle and old age are obviously at least as flexible in their outlook as most young men (Ciutiene and Railaite, 2014). Most organisations are beginning to see a rise in lack of adaptability in their later middle and old aged workforce both at the shop floor and the upper-level management (Nature, 2016).

Demographic characteristics	Number	Mean	Sig
Gender: Male	35	3.31	0.17
Female	60	2.97	
Age: 18-30	42	3.21	0.38
31-40	45	3.04	
41-50	5	3.20	
51-60	3	2.08	
Education: Some secondary school	37	2.78	0.02
Secondary school graduate	37	3.05	
Some university	10	3.52	
University graduate	11	3.90	
Length of employment: 1-5 years	56	3.13	0.60
6-10 years	35	3.04	
11-15 years	3	3.33	
16-20 years	1	2.25	
Position: Front desk/customer service	30	3.21	0.20
Housekeeping	23	2.94	

Food/room service	21	2.89	
Bell staff	16	2.96	
Supervisor	5	4.14	

Table 0.14: Mean scores for self-efficacy based on employees' demographics. (Created by the researcher)

4.3 Dimensions of Paternalistic Leadership Style

This section of the chapter measures the mean score for authoritarian paternalism, benevolent paternalism and moral paternalism dimensions of paternalistic style of leadership

4.3.1 Authoritarian

The data analysis indicates that the mean score for practicing authoritarian paternalism was 4.18 with a standard deviation of 1.07, illustrating that the managers of the hotels scored about 83.6% in their practicing of authoritarian leadership style according the employees' responses. From the table below it shows that the mean score for practicing authoritarian leadership slightly varies among the hotels.

Hotels	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Hotel 1	20	4.16	1.08
Hotel 2	25	4.32	1.02
Hotel 3	25	4.10	1.13
Hotel 4	25	4.15	1.07
Total	95	4.18	1.07

Table 0.15: Mean scores for practicing authoritarian paternalism. (Created by the researcher)

4.3.2 Benevolent

The data analysis of the responses from the customer contact employees to the items assessing the level of practicing of benevolent dimension of paternalistic style of leadership indicates that the overall mean score for practicing benevolent paternalism was 3.50 and the standard deviation was 0.98 reflecting that according to the customer contact employees the hotel managers scored about 70% in their practice of benevolent leadership. The result shows just a slight difference in the mean score among the hotels.

Hotels	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Hotel 1	20	3.56	0.98
Hotel 2	25	3.52	1.01
Hotel 3	25	3.54	0.99
Hotel 4	25	3.36	0.95
Total	95	3.50	0.98

Table 0.16: Mean scores for practicing benevolent paternalism. (Created by the researcher)

4.3.3 Moral

From the data analysis to measure the degree of practicing moral paternalism by the managers based on the responses from the employees the results show that the overall mean score was 3.61 and the standard deviation was 0.78. This reflects that the hotel managers scored about 72.2% in their practice of the moral leadership dimension of paternalistic style of leadership. Similar to the results of the other two dimensions, there is just a slight difference in the mean score among all the hotels.

Hotels	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Hotel 1	20	3.62	0.78
Hotel 2	25	3.63	0.80
Hotel 3	25	3.57	0.78
Hotel 4	25	3.62	0.77
Total	95	3.61	0.78

Table 0.17: Mean scores for practicing moral paternalism. (Created by the researcher)

4.4 Testing the Hypothesis

The acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses will involve the application of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) which determines the association or correlation between variables. SEM is much suitable for measuring the relationships between more than one independent variable and one or more dependent variables.

4.4.1 Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

In general, leadership styles are predicted to have a positive impact on employee's attitudinal responses and behaviors, which will then have a positive impact on the quality of service,

consistent with previous studies that have shown a positive relationship between these constructs. This part of chapter four focus on the results from the statistical test of the hypotheses using structural modeling. Hypothesis are either accepted or rejected depending on whether the T value related with each path loading is greater than the criterion of practical significance (critical value >1.96) for the 5% significance level and the P value is less than 0.05.

SEM analyze relations of the multiple independent and dependent variable simultaneously (Gefen, Straub, & Boudreau, 2000). It is a set of statistical methods that allow for the analysis of a series of relationships between one or more independent variables, either continuous or discrete, and one or more dependent variables, either continuous or discrete (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). It is an effective multivariate technique very common in scientific research to test and analyze multivariate causal relationships. It can also be referred to as confirmatory factor analysis, path analysis, analysis of variance structures, simultaneous equation modelling, causal analysis or causal modelling. Structural equation modeling enables the answering of questions involving multiple regression analysis of factors. It combines two methods of statistics: path analysis and confirmatory factor analysis. The first major step in a SEM analysis is model specification, making this is a confirmatory technique rather than an exploratory one. The model is estimated, assessed, and might even undergo some modifications. The aim of the analysis may be to test a model, to test clearly defined hypothesis associated with a model, to make minor changes to an existing model, or to test a set of similar models. Confirmatory factor analysis measures the fitness of the model while the proposed hypotheses are tested with the path analysis test. The results of these two models are discussed below.

Confirmatory factor analysis (Measurement model)

Confirmatory factor analysis is the method for measuring latent variables (Byrne, 2016). It is used to validate the appropriateness of a measurement model before regressions among the

latent variables are involved. Based on the correlated variations of the data set, CFA calculates the latent variables and can minimize the dimensions of the data, bring the scale of multiple indicators to conform to standard, and justify correlations immanent in the data set (Byrne, 2016). It is one of the major techniques for assessing measurement invariance, a crucial problem in ensuring that measurement instruments are used in a fair manner and devoid of bias towards some groups. It assesses reliability, validity and model fitness of the constructs.

Reliability and validity analysis

Factor loading should be greater than 0.4 (Hair et al, 2017). In this study, all the factor loadings were greater than 0.6. Few items were deleted due to low factor loadings. These items were RC1, RC2, RC8, ALDR5, ESE1, and MLDR3. Reliability shows the consistency of the scale. It is measured by using the composite reliability or the Cronbach alpha (Alarcón, Sánchez, & De Olavide, 2015). The reliability values of the variables have to be higher than 0.7. It has been analyzed that, values of all the variables are greater than 0.7 indicating that consistency exists in all the scales. Validity is of two types convergent and discriminant validity. Correlation between the items of the variable is measured by convergent validity. It is also called average extracted variance (AVE). Its value should be greater than 0.5(Walter, Ritter, & Gemünden, 2001). Results show that all are variables possess convergent validity having values greater than 0.5. The results of reliability, convergent validity, and factor loading are given below in table 4.23.

Variables	Items	F. Loadings	Composite reliability	AVE
Adaptability	ADAP1	0.745	0.93	0.771
	ADAP2	0.914		
	ADAP3	0.922		
	ADAP4	0.918		
Authoritarian leadership	ALDER1	0.808	0.914	0.727

	ALDER2	0.751		
	ALDER3	0.877		
	ALDER4	0.96		
Benevolent leadership	BLDER1	0.749	0.835	0.504
	BLDER2	0.777		
	BLDER3	0.7		
	BLDER4	0.691		
	BLDER5	0.622		
Self-efficacy	ESE2	0.932	0.955	0.877
	ESE3	0.951		
	ESE4	0.927		
Job satisfaction	JS1	0.816	0.94	0.759
	JS2	0.896		
	JS3	0.916		
	JS4	0.906		
	JS5	0.818		
Moral leadership	MLDER1	0.878	0.891	0.673
	MLDER2	0.849		
	MLDER4	0.747		
	MLDER5	0.802		
Role clarity	RC10	0.72	0.943	0.540
	RC11	0.816		
	RC12	0.759		
	RC13	0.771		
	RC14	0.768		
	RC15	0.803		
	RC16	0.699		
	RC17	0.706		
	RC3	0.688		
	RC4	0.676		
	RC5	0.703		
	RC6	0.699		
	RC7	0.722		
	RC9	0.737		
Customer perceived service quality	SQ1	0.918	0.975	0.795
	SQ10	0.876		
	SQ2	0.915		
	SQ3	0.866		
	SQ4	0.847		
	SQ5	0.906		
	SQ6	0.884		
	SQ7	0.923		

	SQ8	0.891		
	SQ9	0.888		

Table 0.18: Results of reliability, convergent validity and factor loadings. (Created by the researcher)

Discriminant Validity

It checks that correlation among the predictors of the model and these variables should not be highly correlated. It has been tested using the method proposed by (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). According to this method, diagonal values must be greater than horizontal and vertical values. It has been analyzed that all the diagonal values are in an acceptable range and greater than other values, indicating that items are not highly correlated.

	ADAP	A_Ldr	B_IDR	CSQ	ESE	JS	M_LDR	RC
ADAP	0.878							
A_Ldr	-0.032	0.853						
B_Ldr	0.026	-0.51	0.71					
CSQ	-0.03	0.168	0.014	0.892				
ESE	0.774	-0.085	0.168	-0.081	0.937			
JS	0.679	-0.13	0.105	0.092	0.524	0.871		
M_LDR	0.079	-0.377	0.678	0.076	0.143	0.116	0.821	
RC	0.722	-0.09	0.098	-0.028	0.68	0.779	0.135	0.714

Table 0.19: Result for discriminant validity. (Created by the researcher)

Model Fitness

According to (Gefen et al., 2000) validation of the measurement model is necessary for measuring the structural model. Model fitness results are in an acceptable range indicating the validation of the measurement model. The value of standardized root means square residual (SRMR) less than 0.1 indicating model fit (Hu & Bentler, 1998). The value of SRMR of this model is under the range. The RMS_theta value is used for analyzing the reflective model's significance. The value close to zero indicating a good model fit value. According to (Henseler et al., 2016) RMS_theta value less than 0.15 or 0.12 showing model fitness values for reflective models. The model of this study has RMS_theta is 0.15. It shows that our model is fit and we test the structural model for hypotheses testing.

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.078	0.085
Chi-Square	2,603.41	2,625.35

Table 0.20: Test for model fitness. (Created by the researcher)

All the model fitness indices above show the validation of the measurement model. It means that now structural model can be analyzed using the data validated by the measurement model.

The diagram of the measurement model is given below

Figure 4.1: Measurement model. (Created by the researcher)

Path Analysis (Structural Model)

Path analysis was developed to quantify the relationships among multiple variables. It explains the causal relationships among variables. Mediation is a common function of path analysis which assumes that a variable can influence an outcome directly and indirectly through another variable.

In the structural model, the proposed hypotheses are tested using the regression. It has been analyzed that adaptability has an insignificant relationship with customer perceived service quality because of having $p\text{-value} > 0.05$. It results in rejecting the proposed hypothesis H6.

Authoritarian, moral and benevolent paternalism have an insignificant relationship with role clarity. The researcher also rejected H2(a), H2(b), H2(c) hypotheses

The results show the positive and significant effect of self-efficacy on the adaptability ($\beta=0.527$, $p<0.05$). Role clarity has a significant and positive effect on adaptability ($\beta=0.527$, $p<0.05$), on self-efficacy ($\beta=0.68$, $p<0.05$), and on job satisfaction ($\beta=0.787$, $p<0.05$). All these H5(a), H4(a), H4(b), H4(c) hypotheses are accepted. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant relationship with the customer perceived service quality at the level of 10%, ($\beta=0.209$, $p<0.1$). H7 is accepted. The effect of self-efficacy on service quality and job satisfaction is also insignificant indicated by the greater p -values. It results in a rejection of H6(a) and H5. The hypotheses H3a, b, c proposed the relationship of leadership dimensions with job satisfaction. It has been analyzed that authoritarian leadership, benevolent leadership, and moral leadership have an insignificant relationship with the job satisfaction indicated by the $p\text{-values}>0.05$. Thus H3(a), H3(b) and H3 (c) are rejected.

Figure 4.2: The structural model. (Created by the researcher)

The results of hypotheses are given in table 4.26 above. All the constructs under study were ascertained to have been measured reliably and validity. Structural model was tested to ascertain the relationships between constructs. This study contains eight constructs listed in table 4.26 and shown in figure 4.26 above.

Hypotheses	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Decision
ADAP -> CSQ	-0.062	-0.044	0.198	0.314	0.754	Rejected
A_IDR -> RC	-0.064	-0.056	0.143	0.449	0.654	Rejected
B_IDR -> RC	-0.085	-0.013	0.205	0.415	0.678	Rejected
ESE -> ADAP	0.527	0.518	0.073	7.265	0	Accepted
ESE -> CSQ	-0.142	-0.145	0.175	0.809	0.419	Rejected
ESE -> JS	-0.012	-0.022	0.126	0.093	0.926	Rejected
JS -> CSQ	0.209	0.213	0.126	1.651	0.099	Rejected
M_LDR -> RC	0.182	0.143	0.185	0.985	0.325	Rejected
RC -> ADAP	0.364	0.373	0.064	5.641	0	Accepted
RC -> ESE	0.68	0.684	0.055	12.373	0	Accepted
RC -> JS	0.787	0.8	0.096	8.243	0	Accepted
A_IDR -> JS	-0.047	-0.045	0.105	0.452	0.651	Rejected
B_IDR -> JS	-0.057	-0.008	0.159	0.358	0.721	Rejected
M_LDR -> JS	0.133	0.101	0.147	0.91	0.364	Rejected

Table 0.21: Result of the hypothesized relationships from the path analysis. (Created by the researcher).

Leadership and role clarity

From table 4.27 below, no positive relationship was found between authoritarian leadership and role clarity. The result is expected and is consistent with arguments that authoritarian leadership is incompatible with the requirements of the hotel environment due to its autocratic nature (Chan, 2013). Similarly, to H1A, no positive relationship was found between benevolent leadership and role clarity (H1B). That was an unexpected result. A positive relationship between moral leadership and role clarity was demonstrated in this study. However, while the relationship was in the hypothesised direction, the relationship was not significant at the 0.05 level and neither did it exceed the criterion for practical significance (1.96). Hence, the hypothesis is not accepted. In light of the results of the hypotheses 1A, 1B, 1C, it may be suggested that the dimensions of paternalistic leadership do not play any role in reducing role ambiguity nor increasing role clarity for customer contact employees. It was expected that authoritarian paternalism will negatively impact role clarity due to its strong authority and discipline which makes subordinates sometimes too scared to ask for clarification when role expectations become a bit confusing. Surprisingly it wasn't expected that benevolence and moral paternalism couldn't improve role clarity. This might be because authoritarian paternalism is more predominantly expressed in the owner/managers leadership hence subduing the positive effects of benevolence and morality.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H1A	Authoritarian leadership	Role clarity	-0.064	0.314	0.754
H1B	Benevolent leadership	Role clarity	-0.085	0.415	0.678
H1C	Moral leadership	Role clarity	0.182	0.98	0.325

Table 0.22: Result of the relationship between paternalistic leadership and role clarity. (Created by the researcher)

Leadership and Job satisfaction

From table 4.28 below, it is not surprising that the hypothesized relationship between authoritarian leadership and role clarity was negative with a T value of 0.452 and P value of

0.651. This is consistent with findings of previous studies which suggest that authoritarian leadership has no positive effect on job satisfaction among employees (Afsar, 2014; Hafeez and Hayat, 2017). However, contrary to expectations benevolent leadership have no positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Although it's shown that moral leadership has a positive effect on job satisfaction, there is no evidence of a significant effect similar to the relationship between moral leadership and role clarity explained above. In other words, moral leadership on its own is not enough to influence employee job satisfaction. This is inconsistent with the findings of past studies which have suggested a positive and significant relationship between these two dimensions of paternalistic leadership style and job satisfaction (Hafeez and Hayat, 2017; Afsar, 2014). The lack of a positive and significant relationship between benevolence and morality in this study might be attributed to the domination of authoritarian paternalism. The strict control, fear and punishment of authoritarianism may have dominated caring and reward-based factors of benevolence and morality. Appropriate care, recognition, love, empowerment and reward are likely to increase job satisfaction in employees when there is no strict control.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H2A	Authoritarian leadership	Job satisfaction	-0.047	0.452	0.651
H2B	Benevolent leadership	Job satisfaction	-0.057	0.358	0.721
H2C	Moral leadership	Job satisfaction	0.133	0.91	0.364

Table 0.23: Result of the relationship between paternalistic leadership and job satisfaction. (Created by the researcher)

Role clarity and Job satisfaction

In table 4.29 below, role clarity was found to have a direct positive relationship with job satisfaction. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. There is nothing surprising about this relationship as it has been suggested substantially in previous studies (Schneider, 1980; Hartline and Ferrell, 1996) which have demonstrated that lack of role clarity experienced by

employees reduce their job satisfaction. The basic argument to support this is that when there is reduced role ambiguity among employees, they tend to be happy with their jobs as they get the job done effectively with no issues. However, if they are not clear on their roles they however tend to be dissatisfied.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H3A	Role clarity	Job satisfaction	0.787	8.243	0

Table 0.24: Result of the hypothesized relationship between role clarity and job satisfaction. (Created by the researcher)

Role clarity and adaptability

The result is presented in table 4.30 below. The hypothesis is accepted as there was a direct positive relationship between role clarity and adaptability with path coefficient of 0.364, T value of 5.61 and P value of 0. Though there is limited evidence of this relationship in previous studies however it is expected that employees that are able to adapt their roles in delivering top quality service to customers must have presumably have a clear understanding of their tasks, responsibilities and processes.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H3B	Role clarity	Adaptability	0.364	5.641	0

Table 0.25: Result of the hypothesized relationship between role clarity and adaptability. (Created by the researcher)

Role clarity and self-efficacy

The hypothesis demonstrated a positive relation between role clarity and self-efficacy. Result is presented in table 4.31 below. The hypothesis was accepted as there was a positive and significant relationship between role clarity and self-efficacy at path coefficient value of 0.68, T value of 12.373 and P value of 0. This is another expected result as it is consistent with existing theories which suggest that role clarity among customer contact employees affects the employees' self-efficacy (Hartline et al, 1996). Employees with a clear understanding of their roles will grow in confidence in carrying out their roles and responsibilities. The ones that are

unclear about their expectations within a certain role will lack belief in their ability to succeed in that role or accomplish an assigned task.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H3C	Role clarity	Self-efficacy	0.68	12.373	0

Table 0.26: Result of the hypothesized relationship between role clarity and self-efficacy. (Created by the researcher)

Self-efficacy and Job satisfaction

Hypothesis 4A suggested a positive relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction. As expressed in table 4.32 below, in contrast to expectations, this hypothesis was rejected as the path between the two variables (Self-efficacy and Job satisfaction) is negative and not significant. The result proves that employees that are barely self-efficacious tends to be less satisfied with their jobs. The result of this study is in contrast with the findings of previous studies which suggests a positive relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction (Hartline et al, 1996; Mcdonald and Siegall, 1992).

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H4A	Self-efficacy	Job satisfaction	-0.012	0.093	0.926

Table 0.27: Result of the hypothesized relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction. (Created by the researcher)

Self-efficacy and adaptability

Hypothesis 4B suggested that employee self-efficacy is positively related to how much the employees are able to adjust their roles to satisfy customer needs. The result in table 4.33 below validates the hypothesis considering the path coefficient value is 0.527, the T value is 7.265 and P value is 0. Hence, it can be argued that employees' belief in their own ability to carry out a specific task is more likely to translate into their ability to adapt their roles to meet customer needs.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H4B	Self-efficacy	Adaptability	0.527	7.265	0

Table 0.28: Result of the hypothesized relationship between self-efficacy and adaptability. (Created by the researcher)

Adaptability and customer perceived service quality

The results expressed in table 4.34 below shows that the path between adaptability and customer perceived service quality was negative and not significant. Hence, contradicting the hypothesized positive relationship. In view of this finding, the hypothesis is rejected. This shows that hotel guest perception of service quality is not affected by the adaptability of the customer contact employees. This result might be because adaptability is actually not necessary in hotels as customers expect little or no adaptation. Though sometimes customers might request for a different room to the one already assigned, however, these requests are rarely met with rejection. Unlike hotels, adaptability is very much needed in restaurants where employees must be highly adaptive to suit customers differing preferences.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H5	Adaptability	Service quality	-0.062	0.314	0.754

Table 0.29: Result of the hypothesized relationship between adaptability and service quality. (Created by the researcher)

Self-efficacy and customer perceived service quality

Hypothesis 6 suggested a positive relationship between employee self-efficacy and customer perceived service quality. The hypothesis is rejected as the path between self-efficacy and customer perceived service quality is negative and not significant as expressed in table 4.35 below. Hence self-efficacy did not exert any significant influence on service quality in this study. This is surprising as it disputed the findings of previous research that demonstrated a positive and significant relationship between self-efficacy and customer perception of service quality.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H6	Self-efficacy	Service quality	-0.142	0.809	0.419

Table 0.30: Result of the hypothesized relationship between self-efficacy and service quality. (Created by the researcher)

Job satisfaction and customer perceived service quality

Hypothesis 7 suggests a positive relationship between job satisfaction and customer perceived service quality. The result expressed in table 4.36 below reveals a direct positive correlation was given in the results however the correlation was not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. So basically, job satisfaction on its own cannot influence service quality in this study. This result supports previous research that suggest that relationship between the two variables is not consistent (Ariani, 2015; Milana, 2018; Armstrong, 2006; Simpson, 2006) but however differ from previous studies that suggest that service quality is influenced by employee job satisfaction (Ghayas and Hussain, 2015; Kirago, 2015; Yee et al, 2008; Hartline and Ferrell, 1996).

Job satisfaction does not play an important role in service quality. Because of the low job satisfaction in the sector, employees don't seem to pay attention to achieve customers satisfaction. The customers on the other hand seem to have gotten used to the poor quality of service in the sector hence they don't expect any improvement during an encounter or service interactions.

Hypothesis	Antecedent	Outcome	Coefficient	T Value	P Value
H7	Job satisfaction	Service quality	0.29	1.651	0.099

Table 0.31: Result of the hypothesized relationship between job satisfaction and service quality. (Created by the researcher)

4.5 Conclusion

This chapter presents the analysis of the data collected using descriptive statistics and structural equation modelling. Following an extensive analysis of the data collected from guests of the four hotels using standard deviation and mean in SPSS, the findings indicate that guests of the four hotels have low perception of the quality of services in those hotels. The results presented in this chapter also show that none of the leadership dimensions of paternalistic leadership have any significant effect on employee's role clarity and job satisfaction. These two variables need

to be enhanced for customer contact employees to perform well during service encounters, as the study also revealed that self-efficacy, adaptability and job satisfaction have no statistically significant effect on customer perceived service quality. Hence, the results reflect that paternalistic leadership has no influence on customer perceived service quality. The findings of this analysis will be discussed in more details in the next chapter.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

This current chapter seeks to present the findings of the analysis in non-technical detail. It starts first with a summary of the research questions followed with the presentation and discussion of the hypothesis.

The statistical analysis of the data and testing of the hypothesis leads the researcher in the right direction towards answering the research questions presented in Chapter one of this thesis. To rewind, the research questions are as follows:

- What perceptions do customers have about the service quality in the Nigerian hospitality sector?
- How does paternalistic leadership style affect customer contact employees service behavior?
- How does customer contact employee service behavior affect customer's perception of service quality?

What perceptions do customers have about the service quality in the Nigerian hospitality sector?

Customer perceived service quality was measured using a ten-item scale based on the original SERVQUAL scale (Parasuraman et al, 1988). The measure was restricted to those items that are relevant to employee-related dimensions of service quality because the intent is to measure the service quality rendered to customers/guests by employees in the hotel sector. A slight modification was done on the scale to necessitate the combination of expectations and perceptions into a single measure in accordance with the suggestions of Cronin and Taylor (1992) and Brown et al (1993).

Many customers expressed a negative perception of the quality of services among the hotels. Customer perceived service quality among the hotels were assessed in regard to factors like the

promptness of the service, the courteousness of the employees, the attention given to the guest by the hotels' staff during the service encounter. Generally, the findings show a low degree of customer perceived service quality towards the hotels' services.

Several demographic characteristics were utilised in this research to categorise the participants. These demographic characteristics include education, age, gender and income. The characteristics that influence customer perception of service quality, according to the findings, are the customers age, income and education. Mean scores for customer perceived service quality differed significantly according to age, income and education. Older customers expressed lower perception of service quality compared to the younger ones. Those with higher education expressed lower perception of service quality compared to those with less education. Those with higher income expressed lower perception of service quality than those with lower income. The younger customers (18-39) compared to the older ones (40+) expressed the highest perception of service quality. Due to technology used for online booking and reservation that are seemingly harder for older age group than the younger age group. The older age group may find it discouraging using online booking and reservation systems rather than the old-fashioned system of booking at the reception desk. This disputes the common perception that millennial hotel users are less loyal to brands. In addition, the younger customers made up of university students or recent graduates not yet employed and haven't had much dealings with hotels whereas the older ones are usually matured working class adults or retired with lots of dealings with hotels and thus expectations are always high during any service encounter especially on a first visit. It should not be a surprise that the wealthiest guests are the most critical hotel visitors. The more affluent a traveller, the more critical they will be. The result shows that the educated and wealthy customers have been conditioned to expect better service due to their exposure and numerous travels. Most of them are business travellers and must have travelled to different parts of the world or even across Nigeria where they have

experienced and received high quality services. These groups of people don't shy away from complaining to hotel firms or to friends and families through word of mouth after a bad service encounter experience. Those with higher education are expected to easily detect issues with employees during a service encounter than the less educated guests. The less educated guests might only look out for a comfortable bed, good shower and clean rooms whereas the more educated ones probably of working class travelling for business meetings may expect reliable Wi-Fi connection, a plug for charging all gadgets, an iron, a food menu, a spacious space to work to include tables and chairs, and most especially a warm welcome from the employees giving the necessary information to help you navigate around the town. They expect more than a good standard of basic amenities compared to less educated guests that just want to have time outside their home. Therefore, they are much more difficult to impress during a service encounter.

The results of this research are in line with the results of a previous study in the same sector. Anetoh (2016) assessed guests' expectations and perceptions of service performances in the hospitality industry in Nigeria, using SERVQUAL model in which it was determined that the expectations level among hotel guests in Anambra regarding quality of service exceeded the actual performance. Though the service quality measurement models differ, they both still implies that service quality is at a very low level in the state and requires an immediate intervention to attract more travellers and tourists as the size and growth of both foreign and local business travellers are steadily increasing in the country as a whole. Leadership style have been touted as a key factor in influencing service firms' employee behaviour towards delivering great service quality. This relationship has been explored and the findings presented in the previous chapter. A discussion on this relationship will be presented for the answers to the next research questions.

Very limited studies have made an attempt at examining the effect of popular western styles of leadership such as the full range leadership styles; transactional, transformational and laissez faire on customer perceived service quality. By capturing customers perception of service quality and examining the effects of paternalistic leadership on customer perceived service quality, this study is the first to empirically determine this relationship. This study highlights the managerial and practical issues integral in the management of frontline hotel employees service behavior needed to improve the quality of services rendered in the Nigerian hotel sector. It also provides future direction for additional research into leadership in Africa and managing customer contact employees towards enhancing service performance.

How Does paternalistic leadership style affect customer contact employees service behavior?

The findings suggest that role clarity does not increase under a paternalistic leader as none of the dimensions reduces role ambiguity among employees. There is lack of clarity and certainty in customer contact employees' roles. It is expected that strong authority and discipline of a paternalistic leader would elevate the role ambiguity of customer contact employee whereas it would be lessened by fatherly benevolence and moral integrity. However, based on the findings, benevolence and moral leadership also do not affect role clarity. This is not only surprising but also a fascinating finding which may be attributed to the unique and moral concern these leaders express to their employees, treating their employees as family members by showing emotional and moral concern that may blur the moral of the work for subordinates (Kaygisizel and Otken, 2015). This benevolence and moral treat hence might affect the clarity of job roles as employees get confused about what is expected of them.

As always expected, the findings revealed that authoritarian leadership do not increase customer contact employee job satisfaction. Meanwhile, contrary to expectations, benevolent leadership also do not seem to increase job satisfaction among customer contact employees.

This is an interesting finding which might be due to the fact that the authoritarian element dominates the benevolent element of the paternalistic leader. Though these leaders may show care and emotional concern towards employees beyond work, they still wield strict control, fear and punishment. This counter-productive environment and stressful leadership might create dissatisfaction among customer contact employees. Though the relationship between moral leadership and job satisfaction is positive, however, it is not significant enough. Hence, a mediator such as psychological empowerment might be needed to fully operationalize this relationship. This calls for the need for future research investigating the mediating role of psychological empowerment in the relationship between moral leadership and job satisfaction as has been seen in similar studies examining ethical leadership and job satisfaction. (Miao et al, 2019). Employees with a perception of empowerment, with a strong sense of control and energy with respect to their jobs will feel more satisfied in their jobs (Miao et al, 2019).

The results reveal that lack of role clarity among the employees affects their job satisfaction levels. The results are consistent with past research results of Hartline and Ferrell, (1996) who demonstrated that role ambiguity among customer contact employees results to lower level of job satisfaction. When employees have the perception of not knowing what is expected of them in their roles, they tend to be dissatisfied with their jobs. This also applies to adaptability and self-efficacy. In the findings, role clarity increases employee adaptability. Hence, the inverse of role clarity, role ambiguity decreases employee adaptability. So, for the customer contact employees to adaptively serve customers during a service encounter they have to be clear in their job roles. This result is expected as adaptability requires effort and time owing to the fact that the customer-contact employee need to pay a great deal of attention on the guest during a service encounter, but this behavior is expected to be less efficient, inadequate or misdirected when the customer contact employee is experiencing high levels of role ambiguity. Therefore, it is expected that experiencing high levels of role ambiguity will be damaging to employees'

adaptability whereas the experience of higher levels of role clarity will be beneficial to employee adaptability (Roman and Iacobucci, 2009).

Minimal ambiguity is required for customer contact employees to successfully carry out their task during a service encounter. If the employee is clear about a customer's needs and expectations and confident enough to deliver on these needs and expectations, minimal ambiguity and maximum clarity should be experienced. On the other hand, when an employee clearly understands responsibilities associated with his/her roles during a service encounter, their confidence in carrying out the role increases. According to Bandura (2002, p. 373) "cognitions are translated into behavior through a conception-matching process in which cognitive representations serve as guides for the production of skilled actions and as internal standards for making corrective adjustments". Thus, when employees lack a clear understanding of their primary roles and tasks, they will be confused about the accuracy of the cognitive representations guiding their behavior and subsequently might underrate their capabilities, hence, lowering their self-efficacy. On the contrary, when employees are very clear regarding the primary roles and tasks they are obliged to carry out, they should be able to make a clear judgment on their capabilities in relation to these primary roles and tasks.

Although past studies indicate that both employee job satisfaction and adaptability are positively influenced by self-efficacy among customer contact employees, the results of this study are only in line with the self-efficacy/adaptability contentions but not with that of self-efficacy/job satisfaction. The inexistence of a positive correlation in the self-efficacy/job satisfaction construct is presumably linked to the capability of other constructs in the conceptual framework such as role clarity and the leadership dimensions, predicting job satisfaction a bit more than self-efficacy. Role clarity deficiencies among the employees may subdue the effects of self-efficacy on job satisfaction. Employee self-efficacy may only drive

job satisfaction when employees are confident and certain about the fulfillment of their primary role functions.

The inexistence of a positive self-efficacy/job satisfaction relationship may also be due to so many reasons associated with the inherent features of the hotels customer contact roles such as being underpaid, undertrained, overworked, over-stressed and over controlled. Taking into considerations the attributes of a hotel customer contact role, the non-requirement of specialized skills (receptionist, cook, waiter, security) and their level of education, it is highly likely that these hotel employees consider their present job as a temporary career choice having upward mobility in mind. Those with less education probably harbor intentions of furthering their education for the prospects of a better career choice while the graduates or the ones currently in university are expected to have same goals of rising to a higher financial position that unmatched the attributes of nearly all boundary spanning hotel industry roles. Thus, it is assumed that the inexistence of a positive correlation in the self-efficacy/job satisfaction construct is likely due to this common goal of upward mobility among the hotels staff. Locke and Lathan (1990) pointed that, individuals that are highly self-efficacious set high-level targets for themselves creating a state whereby an individual aim to achieve more in order to attain satisfaction. Also, Hackman and Oldham (1980) stressed that employees reach a high level of satisfaction on their jobs when they attach personal significance to the job. They perceive the jobs as the attainment of their goals that are of demonstrated value to them. Therefore, due to their higher goals' aspirations, the personal significance attach to their current jobs may have decreased hence, lowering their level of job satisfaction. The presence of a self-efficacy/adaptability relationship in this study is consistent with previous research (McDonal and Siegall, 1992; Roman and Iacobucci, 2009). To deliver a good quality service during a service encounter, customer contact employees must be able to behave in an adaptive manner and have the confidence in their own ability to do so. The confidence that customer contact

employees possess in their own ability to effectively carry out their primary role functions should exert a major impact on their service behavior, which include behaving adaptively.

How does customer contact employee service behavior affect customer's perception of service quality?

The inability of employee adaptability to influence customers' perceived service quality might be because in hotel service encounters, customers expect little or no adaptation, therefore, employee adaptability is not expected to affect customers' perceived service quality since there was no expectations from the hotel guest to receive adapted service from hotel staff. In addition, the lack of relationship might be due to issues in defining the measurement of the variables as the measurement and conceptualization of employee adaptability in the literature might not correspond to the manner a customer perceives adaptability in employees (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996). The operationalization and conceptualization of employee adaptability in the literature suggest its occurrence from one service encounter to the other (i.e., across customers). nevertheless, hotel guests are not expected to perceive adaptability in an employee across a single service encounter between the employee and the hotel guests. Hence, adaptive employee responses are expected to exert no influence on guests perceived service quality in a single service encounter. This finding aligns with that of Rapp et al (2008) that revealed no significant effect of adaptive selling on customer service, which the researchers credited to customers inability to spot adaptive selling techniques. In another study, there was inexistence of any relational consequence of adaptive selling on customer satisfaction (Mcfarland et al, 2006). The finding is also in line with the findings of Hartline and Ferrell (1996) that revealed the lack of a relationship between adaptability of employees and customers' perceived service quality. There is an inexistence of a relationship between hotel employees' self-efficacy and guests perceived service quality. Generally, it is expected that hotel staff that are confident in their own ability to execute their roles will presumably perform better than their anxious and less

confident colleagues in service encounters which as a result increases customers' perceived service quality. One major reason for a lack of relationship might be because self-efficacy among the employees is not strong enough. Most of the employees are not skilled or knowledgeable enough in their roles hence affecting their confidence and ability to serve customers. Less self-efficacious employees encounter difficulties in performing their primary role functions, which is linked to low performances and reduced customer perception of the service quality. Lee et al, (2014) suggest that developing specialized knowledge and expertise has a particular relevance to an individual's conviction or interactive capability to effectively manage customer interactions. In addition to new skills acquisitions and honing abilities, being self-efficacious will enable employees to respond adaptively to several customer needs and requests.

Alike the previous relationships discussed above, job satisfaction has no influence on customer perceived service quality. Unsurprisingly, dissatisfied employees are expected to underperform more than satisfied employees in any service interactions leading to an increased perception of service quality among the customers as suggested by previous researchers (Snipes et al, 2005; Arianu, 2015). The surveyed employees expressed low satisfaction in their various roles. Hence this might have affected their motivation to perform considerable well during a service encounter. Dissatisfied employees demonstrate a very low level of loyalty to their organization and are reluctant to commit to their organization's goals and values. This translates in their performance during a service encounter. Bitner et al (1990) stressed that low job satisfaction has the potential of causing low quality service encounter performance on the part of the employee leading to customer negative perception of service quality, dissatisfaction, firm switching and negative word of mouth about not only the employee but the firm in general. As job satisfaction declines, customers devalue the quality of the service experience.

Job satisfaction does not play an important role in guest perception of service quality. Maybe because hotel guests are now accustomed with poor quality of services, thus not expecting anything better from the service providers. Because of the low job satisfaction in the sector, employees don't seem to pay attention to achieve customers satisfaction. The customers on the other hand seem to have gotten used to the bad services hence are not looking forward to any improvement during an encounter or service interactions.

CHAPTER 6 SUMMARY OF THE STUDY AND CONCLUSION

6.1 Summary of the Study

To summarise, this research is the first to study the influence of paternalism on customer perceived service quality. The study started with a conceptual and contextual discussion of the research background highlighting the rationale, significance and the aim of the research which was to evaluate the level of influence leadership styles have on customer contact employees' service behaviours in service encounters conducive for the delivery of excellent service quality within small indigenous hotels in Awka, Nigeria. This led to the review of vital literatures on leadership, culture, service quality and consumer-oriented behaviours and then formulation of a conceptual framework based on the literature review to drive the study towards delineating how leadership styles influence employees' attitudes and behaviours towards delivering excellent quality services. The study followed a descriptive, cross-sectional and correlational design based on positivism philosophy. Hence, data was collected quantitatively using survey from employees and customers of four hotels in Awka. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed on SPSS and SmartPLS using descriptive statistics and structural equation modeling respectively.

The major outcome is that hotel guests in Awka have a low perception of service quality. Hence hotel managers are tasked with reversing this perception through their leadership behaviour. However, paternalistic leadership style which is the predominant leadership style in this sector based on cultural characteristics of the Nigerian societies documented in several literatures, is not suitable to influence employees' attitudes and behaviour during service encounters to promote excellent service climate as it has been proven in the study that paternalism does not have any influence on customer's perception of service quality. Many variables such as role clarity, self-efficacy, adaptability and job satisfaction were expected to influence this

complicated process. Though the results show that most of the respondents struggle to cope with ambiguities of their roles, which then consequentially affects job satisfaction, adaptability and self-efficacy in service encounters, customers' perception of service quality are surprisingly not affected. Hence the researcher draws an inference that the customers are accustomed to the low-quality services in the sector with no expectation of improvements in service performance. The results are concerning and consideration should be given to leadership training for managers that underpins employee empowerment and rewards for achievements as this has been proven to work in western organisations. Given the globalisation effects of culture dynamics in societies, western style of leadership may be more appropriate to influence employees service behaviour in service interactions for the benefit of an enhanced service quality in the Nigerian hospitality sector.

6.2 Conclusion

This section will conclude the study by highlighting the academic (theoretical) and practical (managerial) implications of the study, the limitations and suggestions for subsequent research, future researchers may wish to explore. This study has contributed to the existing literature by reporting that paternalistic leadership style has no influence on customer perceived service quality in the Nigerian hotel sector.

6.2.1 Academic and Theoretical Implications

Firstly, the study has shed light on the influence of the three dimensions of paternalistic leadership style (authoritarian, benevolence, moral) on customer perceived service quality. It can probably be said that both authoritarian leadership and benevolence leadership have negative influence upon employee's role clarity and only moral leadership tend to increase employee role clarity however this effect is not significant. Likewise, both authoritarian leadership and benevolent leadership have negative influence upon employee job satisfaction

whereas the impact of moral paternalism on job satisfaction is positive but insignificant. It is worth noting that neither of the three dimensions of paternalistic leadership can increase role clarity among the hotel employees, hence, managers must look for ways to boost role clarity among their employees.

Lack of role clarity seems to have a great influence on customer contact employees job satisfaction and self-efficacy. Their confidence and job satisfaction declines when they are not sure about how to perform their primary role functions. It is expected that customers dealing with such confused employees would not experience the best service encounters. Thus, this negative effect translates into a reduction in a customer's perception of the service quality. Lack of role clarity (role ambiguity) also indirectly affects adaptability as lack of confidence reduces employee's ability or willingness to adjust changes in the service encounter or cope with serving a difficult customer with challenging needs and requests. Making sure that hotel staff especially the contact staff fully understand their primary role functions, responsibilities, requirements, job descriptions and expectations should be a key priority for hotel managers. Establishment of good training programs and proper communication from the managers will help alleviate customer contact employees' role ambiguity.

Secondly, this study has successfully highlighted the complex nature of leadership's influence upon a good number of constructs that contribute to customer contact employee performance during a service encounter. This supports the theory of reasoned action as a critical platform from which organization processes within service industry could be studied and also the social exchange theory which provided a vital platform from which to explain the expected directions of leadership's influence on customer perceived service quality via employee behaviors. In conformity with the theory of reasoned action, this dissertation highlights the significance of role clarity, job satisfaction, self-efficacy and adaptability as vital mediational variables to consider in understanding employee behavior in service encounters.

6.2.2 Managerial and Practical Implications

The research apparently confirms the insignificance of paternalistic leadership in an organizational context, with its inability to influence in customer contact employees' attitudes and behaviors. Authoritarian and benevolent leadership appear to be related to reductions in customer contact employees' role clarity while moral leadership has no significant influence on role clarity. In general, the study found no evidence to support that paternalistic leadership plays any role in positively increasing employee behaviors that affect customer perceived service quality. Therefore, this study has implications not just for hotel managers, but for other managers in the hospitality sector such as restaurant, bars, night clubs.

The ineffectiveness of paternalistic leadership in influencing employees towards performing well in a service encounter might be due to the ongoing gradual transformation of African societies from a purely traditional one to modernity. Modernity influences cultural, social and religious traditions and institutions across the globe. Modernity's global impact has influenced the cultural identity of many African societies. Most of these transformations come from watching television programs, reading articles and books that lean towards portraying the western cultural identity as if it is the most acceptable way of life and more and more Africans travelling to western countries for their education where they are only taught the western way of doing things. Hence, they have lost to a great deal of their African identity and crucial cultural values that connects and bond them together. Coupled with creating a crisis of identity, the global impact of late modernity has led so many Nigerians away from their culture, which may sooner or later be eroded. The mediated experience of global modern western culture has had an alluring and pervasive effect on the thought and decisions of many Nigerians that began in the British colonial years. The uncritical mindset of many Nigerians since the colonial years is informed by the general conception that anything "west is best". This ideology has sunk them into believing their own way of doing things, including values, customs and traditions are

inferior to that of the western world. Hence most are embracing western ideologies and values in order to be considered modern and successful in business, education, politics etc. For instance, the mother tongues are gradually being replaced by the English language as the formal medium of communication in many Nigerian homes and institutions. It's sad to say, but consequentially there are many young Nigerians unable to speak or write in their native language

Hence, it could be argued that the ineffectiveness of paternalistic leadership in influencing employees service behavior is due to the global impact of modernity. As globalization is gradually changing the cultural dynamics of African societies, cultural identities identified by Hofstede cultural dimensions such as togetherness and collectiveness, has now been eroded as people strive for self-determination while they also frown at high power distance. Consequentially, Nigerians tend to make self-regarding autonomous choices and frown at any paternalistic interferences with these choices, irrespective of the benefits of the interference to the person's life. This may somewhat explain the success of the top tier hotels compared to the lower indigenously owned hotels managed by their owners. The top tiers hotels are mainly managed by western trained managers that graduated from top MBA institutions abroad that emphasize heavily on the effectiveness of the full range leadership styles specifically transformational style of leadership. The effectiveness of transformational leadership style in Nigerian hotels have been supported by researchers such as Abomeh (2013) and Ohunakin (2019).

It is probably best to advocate the avoidance of paternalistic leadership as they decrease role clarity and job satisfaction, hence, reducing the likelihood of good performance of customer contact employees in service encounters. Even if paternalism must guide a manager's leadership, he should endeavor to use the authoritative and benevolent dimensions more sparingly than the moral dimension as the study have shown it is the only dimension that

doesn't reduce role clarity and job satisfaction. Managers should cut down on their control and watching of their employees as this could reduce employees' feelings of job satisfaction and confidence. In addition, managers should also limit their getting involved in their employees' life as people are becoming more self-autonomous and vividly frown at paternalistic interferences.

Hotel owners can draw conclusion from the findings of this study so as to meet the needs of all their guests. The study revealed that women expressed a lower perception of service quality than men. Hotel owners should pay more attention to what women want from their hotel experience. They should go an extra mile with a little bit of sensitivity and care. To remain competitive, hotels must develop and focus their services to meet the needs and preferences of women business travelers. Women business travelers express the need to feel safe, comfortable, empowered and pampered (Marsh, 2018). A lot of women are getting into higher positions in their workforce, hence, more business meetings and conferences which attracts the need for business travelling. Hotels should take note of this trend by appealing to this market and work hard to delight the female traveler. Women are more empowered economically and there is a need for extra security to ensure women's safety. Maybe hotels should look at creating women only floors. Though women of nowadays don't want to be treated differently from men, they still have specific needs when travelling on their own some of the needs include assurance that her room have been cleaned and ongoing dialogue with the hotel to provide feedback. Iacobucci and Ostrom (1993) suggest that women focus more on the interpersonal components of a service interaction and Sanchez-Hernandez et al (2010) posits women pay greater attention to relational service quality than functional service quality. Thus, in comparison to men, women look out for the friendliness of the staff in their first association with a hotel services while men pay more attention to the general hotel maintenance and equipment. The staff can be trained

on what to know or what to emphasize on when servicing women or men, as Juwahir (2011) contends that gender affects service quality perceptions.

Hotel owners should look at employing managers with a display of appropriate leadership characteristics or introduce management training programs for the managers to lead employees in a way that will positively influence employees' attitude and service behavior in order to strengthen the service-oriented culture of their hotels. A leader's inappropriate behavior can hinder role clarity among their staff which can have a huge impact on their self-efficacy and adaptability during service encounters. The study has shown that paternalistic leadership style predominant in this sector is not conducive enough in influencing employees' behavior in service encounters. Thus, some leadership training program should be put in place to train managers on appropriate service leadership behavior that is suitable for empowering employees to deliver excellent quality services. Such as transformational leadership that gives employees the power or authority to adapt their behaviors to the demands of each and every service encounter and enhances their self-efficacy (Clark et al, 2009) or transactional leadership style that applies non-financial rewards and incentives to increase employees' behavior and attitude in service encounters to provide higher service quality (Kim and Lee, 2013). According to social exchange theory, reward generates reciprocity or equity thriving behaviors by recipients (Lee, 2006). Appreciation and excellent performances motivate employees' commitment to organization's goals. Thus, investment in leadership training programs is necessary to improve a manager's leadership behavior which will ultimately contribute to positive behavior in employees during service encounter.

6.2.3 Study Limitations

Alike every other research of this form, it is advisable to take the conceptual and methodological limitations of the work into considerations. Hence, the limitations of the study are grouped under conceptual and methodological limitations.

Conceptual Limitations

Firstly, given the rich history of studies into leadership and employee behaviours, there are lots of potential variables that should have been included in this study, there are a multitude of variables, in addition to the ones studied, that can predict employee's behaviour such as organisational commitment, motivation and organisational fairness. The mediating variables in the current study were included because they were integral part of similar past studies of leadership and employee behaviour, and also as a result of their fitness for inclusion into a theory of reasoned action based conceptual framework. Including every single model deemed relevant in the conceptual framework would be met with restraints imposed by time, funding and other resources. The length of a survey questionnaire was found to possess a detrimental impact on participant response rates (Jobber, 1989). Apart from response rates, the length of questionnaire also has a detrimental effect on the general study costs by influencing the cost of postage due to the weight of parcels. Thus, while there are so many variables that could have been included, it is still wise to leave out the less relevant variables for this current study and possibly explore them in future studies. As was discussed earlier, the theory of reasoned action guided the inclusion of variables in the conceptualisation.

Secondly, the study failed to capture the managements' commitment to providing superior service quality to guests. It is very much important to evaluate the hotels' managers commitment to serving customers well. Irrespective of style of leadership, the managers' own commitment to service quality should have a significant effect on the employees' personal commitment in adopting the managers' customer orientation and commitment to service quality. Helping to align the service organisation towards a shared goal of excellent service quality is a major importance of having managers expressing commitment to service quality (Hartline and Ferrell, 1996). Continuously expressing commitment to the provision of excellent quality services can be managers' vision for their hotels. It is highly expected that employees'

commitment to service quality will be modelled on this management vision (Niehoff et al, 1990). Employees would look up to their managers and follow in their vision to increasing service quality.

Methodological Limitations

There several issues with the methodology of this study. Firstly, Bryman (2004) and Conger (1998) have argued that for a comprehensive understanding of the complexities involved in studying leadership, a qualitative approach is no less suitable than a quantitative approach. Hence, there is a concern about the adoption of a quantitative approach. However, given that previous studies developed and validated the measures utilised in this current research, the adoption of a quantitative approach is therefore rationalised.

Secondly, there are concerns regarding the sample, specifically about the adequacy of the sample size. Preferably a larger sample size could have been much appropriate. However, the total shutdown of hotels in Nigeria and travel restrictions due to the current Covid-19 pandemic suppressed the chances of surveying more hotels to reach a much larger sample size. Hence, it is necessary to be cautious in interpreting or considering the findings and the subsequent recommendations based upon these findings. It is worth mentioning that the smaller sample size of this research couldn't provide much statistical power, and this may have influenced some of the results obtained in this study which were contrary to intuition or to common sense expectation (Counter-intuitive).

Thirdly, there are concerns about the potential for common method bias to occur (Podsakoff et al, 2003). Special scales to measure bias should have been considered such as Crowne and Marlowe (1960) social desirability bias scale which is a 33 item self-report questionnaire that evaluates if participants are concerned with social approval, which is seen as one of the most prevalent biases having an effect on survey research. However, including this scale would have

further lengthened the questionnaire, which might affect the response rate. A good way to have reduced bias potential is by collecting data from both employees and managers regarding their perceptions on both leadership and employees' attitudes. Collecting data from more than one group of respondents help reduce bias potential (Luo and White, 2005; Bettencourt and Brown, 2003; Sala and Lynn, 2007). The current Covid-19 situation stifled the opportunity to collect primary data as planned. A face-to-face interview was initially planned to examine the study phenomenon from the managers' perspective. However due to the restrictions on international travel and lockdowns resulting to a total shutdown of the hospitality sector in both UK and Nigeria caused by the current pandemic for much of 2020, face to face interviews with the managers were impossible. Hence, this study was restricted entirely to the employees' perspective.

Another option would have been to contact a subset of the respondents few months after the first survey for a second survey (Luo and White, 2005). However, this would be constrained by time, resources and assurance of anonymity.

6.2.4 Future Research Directions

The review of this study's limitations led to specifying areas that future, marketing and organisational behaviour researchers may wish to consider. A number of ideas can be generated from the conceptual limitation section above.

Firstly, subsequent researchers should give thought to including many other mediating variables in the conceptual framework (e.g., empowerment, organisational commitment, motivation, organisational fairness and shared values). Secondly, future researchers should consider examining variables in greater detail (e.g., five component of job satisfaction). Thirdly, it would be rewarding to make an attempt to replicate the current study in travel, media, sports, health care, finance, retail, education, insurance and several other industries to

further explore the hypothesised relationships. For instance, the association between authoritarian paternalism and role clarity may vary from one service industry to another. Finally, further studies are needed to evaluate how management commitment to service quality would influence customer contact employees service performance in service encounters to ultimately deliver excellent quality services.

From the methodological perspective, a number of leadership models, including paternalistic leadership models are still in the growth or development stage (formative) as suggested by Podsakoff et al (2003). Hence, future work might be necessary to develop new scales/models to measure paternalistic leadership especially one that can give the opportunity to investigate the perceptions of both managers and employees. This would help mitigate any issues of bias. Important extension to this study would have been to collect both employees and managers' perspectives to study whether the leadership style adopted by the manager aligns with that perceived by employees and also to study the employees' attitudes and behaviours conducive for service quality delivery from the viewpoint of the manager. However, these would take time to accomplish.

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APPENDICES

Appendix One: Customer Questionnaire

Dear customer,

This questionnaire seeks your honest opinion regarding service quality issues based on your expectations and the actual service performance received at this hotel. Findings from this research would benefit hotels with regards to the delivery of excellent quality services. Hence, your honest answer to the questions would be highly appreciated. Please indicate the correct response option by circling or ticking where appropriate. Your answers will be kept as highly confidential as possible and would be only utilised for academic purposes.

Thanks for your co-operation

Henry Nwude

(A) This section collects information regarding the demographic characteristics of the customers

(N)	Demographics	Circle the one that applies to you please				
1	Gender	Male		Female		
2	Age	18-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	>60
3	Income range (Naira)	0-30000	30001- 50000	50001-100000	100001- 250000	>250000
4	Education	Some secondary school	Secondary school graduate	Some university	University graduate	

5) How many nights in total are you staying?

6) How many times have you used this hotel?

7) How many adults and/or children are staying with you at this hotel?

(B) This section collects information to measure customer evaluation of the hotel's service quality.

(N)	Service quality attributes	Your evaluation of the hotel's service quality				
		Much worse than expected	Worse than expected	Neutral	Better than expected	Much better than expected
1	Receiving prompt services from our employees					
2	Never being too busy to respond to your requests					
3	Employees behaviours that instil confidence in you					
4	The safety you feel in your transactions with our employees					
5	The courteousness of our employees					
6	The ability of our employees to answer your questions					
7	The personal attention you receive from our employees					
8	Having your best interests at heart					
9	The ability of our employees to understand your specific needs					

10) would you recommend this hotel to your friends and relatives? Yes or No

Appendix Two: Employee Questionnaire

Dear participant,

I am currently writing a dissertation on the role of leadership styles in service quality delivery among small indigenous hospitality enterprises in Nigeria, to fulfil the requirements of my Doctor of Business Administration degree at the University of the West of Scotland.

The aim of this survey is to collect as much information as possible from customer contact employees in this sector regarding the leadership styles of their managers and the employees' attitudinal behaviour in service encounters necessary in the delivery of excellent services to guests. Please indicate the correct response option by circling or ticking where appropriate. Your genuine and honest responses to the questions will be highly appreciated as it would lead the researcher a step closer to achieving the goal of this study. Your responses will be kept as confidential as possible and will only be utilised for academic research purposes.

Thanks for your co-operation

Henry Nwude

(A) This section collects information regarding the demographic characteristics of the employees

N	Demographics	Circle the one that applies to you please					
1	Position	Front desk/customer service	Housekeeping	Food/room service	Reservation/sales	Bell staff	Assistant manager
2	Gender	Female		Male		Prefer not to say	
3	Education	Some secondary school		Secondary school graduate		Some university	University graduate
4	Length of employment (years)	1-5	6-10	11-15		16-20	>20
5	Age	18-30	31-40	41-50		51-60	>60

(B) This section collects information to measure the extent to which employee's perception of his/her manager's leadership behaviour

(N)	Leadership attributes	Your perception of your manager's leadership behaviour				
		Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Frequently	Always
1	My manager appears to be intimidating in front of his/her employees (Authoritarian paternalism)					
2	My manager brings me a lot of pressure when we work together (Authoritarian paternalism)					
3	My manager is very strict with his/her employees (Authoritarian paternalism)					
4	My manager scolds me when I fail expected target (Authoritarian paternalism)					
5	My manager disciplines me for violation of his/her principles (Authoritarian paternalism)					
6	My manager often shows his/her concern about me (Benevolent paternalism)					
7	My manager understands my preference enough					

	to accommodate my personal requests (Benevolent paternalism)					
8	My manager encourages me when I encounter difficulties in work (Benevolent paternalism)					
9	My manager would try to understand the real cause of my unsatisfied performance (Benevolent paternalism)					
10	My manager trains and coaches me when I lack the required abilities at work (Benevolent paternalism)					
11	My manager is responsible on the job (Moral paternalism)					
12	My manager takes responsibility on job and never shirks his/her duty (Moral paternalism)					
13	My manager sets an example to me in all aspects (Moral paternalism)					
14	My manager well self-disciplined before demanding					

	upon others (Moral paternalism)					
15	My manager leads, rather than follows, subordinates to deal with difficult tasks (Moral paternalism)					
16	My manager expresses with few simple words what his/her employees are expected to do (Inspirational motivation of transformational leadership)					
17	My manager enables his/her workers to think about old problems in new ways (Intellectual stimulation of transformational leadership)					
18	My manager provides his/her employees with new ways of looking at puzzling things (Intellectual stimulation of transformational leadership)					
19	My manager helps his/her employees develop themselves (Individualized consideration of transformational leadership)					

20	My manager always tries to give his/her employees feedback on their performances (Individualized consideration of transformational leadership)					
21	My manager personally attends to those employees who seem rejected (Individualized consideration of transformational leadership)					

(C) This section collects information to measure the extent to which employees clearly understands how to fulfil their roles and perform their jobs.

N	Role clarity	Not at all certain	Not certain	Neutral	Certain	Completely certain
1	I am certain about how best to serve my customers					
2	I am certain about how much time to spend on various aspects of my job					
3	I am certain about how to resolve customer complaints					
4	I am certain about how to fill out paperwork					
5	I am certain about how to plan and					

	organize my daily work activities					
6	I am certain about how to handle unusual problems or situations					
7	I am certain about where to get assistance in doing my job					
8	I am certain about the extent to which I can bend the rules to satisfy customers					
9	I am certain about the extent to which I can make decisions without my supervisor approval					
10	I am certain about my hotel's rules and regulations					
11	I am certain about how my supervisor will evaluate my performance					
12	I am certain about how satisfied my supervisor will evaluate my performance					
13	I am certain about the aspects of my work-related training					
14	I am certain about the factors that determine my promotion and advancement					

15	I am certain about how my supervisor expects me to allocate my time					
16	I am certain about how satisfied my customers are with my performance					
	I am certain about what my customers expect of me in performing my job					

(D) This section collects information to measure the extent to which employees are satisfied with a variety of job dimension.

N	Job satisfaction	Extremely dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Extremely satisfied
1	I am satisfied with my overall job					
2	I am satisfied with my supervisor overall job					
3	I am satisfied with my hotel's policies					
4	I am satisfied with the support provided by my hotel					
5	I am satisfied with the opportunities for advancement with this hotel					

(E) This section collects information to measure the extent to which employees believe in their abilities to successfully accomplish a task

N	Self-efficacy	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1	My Job is well within the scope of my abilities					
2	I feel that I am overly qualified for the job I am doing					
3	I feel confident that my skills and abilities equal or exceed those of my colleagues					
4	I could have handled a more challenging job than the one I am doing					

(F) This section collects information to measure the extent to which employees are able to adjust their approach to meet customer demands.

N	Adaptability	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1	Every customer requires a unique approach					
2	When I feel that my approach is not working, I can easily change to another approach					
3	I find it easy to adapt my style to certain customers					
4	I vary my approach from situation to situation					

Appendix 3: Studies examining leadership styles and service quality. (Created by the researcher)

Author (s)	Year	Leadership Style (s)	Outcome
Lee, Cheng, Yeung and Lai	2011	Transformational leadership	Intellectual stimulation dimension of transformational leadership style has a significant impact on service quality in the banking sector
Jabnoun and Rasasi	2005	Transformational and transactional leadership styles	A positive relationship exists between all the dimensions of transformational leadership style and service quality. There was also the presence of a positive relationship between service quality and only the contingent reward dimension of transactional leadership. Active exception and passive avoidant were found to have no positive effect on service quality.
Pahi and Hamid	2015	Full range leadership model (transactional, transformational and laissez faire)	A positive relationship exists between both transactional and transformational leadership styles and employee commitment to service quality while a negative relationship exists between laissez faire and employee commitment to service quality.
Hashim & Mahmood	2011	transformational	Transformational leadership style was revealed to positively and significantly influence employee commitment to service quality among academic staff in Malaysian universities
Hashim & Mahmood	2012	Transformational and transactional	Academic staff commitment to service quality was found to be positively influenced by both transformational and transactional leadership styles of university deans.
Jamaludin, Hashim & Mahmood	2015	Transactional leadership	There is a presence of a positive relationship between academic staff commitment to service quality and transformational leadership style
Clark, Hartline and Jones	2009	Empowering, directive and participative leadership	Empowering leadership style can create a transformational climate that influences employee's commitment to service quality
Yee, Lee, Yeung, Cheng	2013	Transformational and transactional	Transactional leadership style tends to be less effective than transformational leadership style in influencing employee attitude in high contact service organisations
Schaubroeck, Lam and Peng	2016	Ethical and transformational	Transformational leadership positively influences co-workers service quality
Ismail and colleagues	2009	Transformational leadership	The relationship between empowerment and the two transformational leadership dimensions of intellectual stimulation and

			individualised consideration is positively and significantly related with service quality
Liao & Chuang	2007	Transformational leadership	Existence of a positive relationship between managers transformational leadership and employee service performance
Popli & Rizvi	2017	Transformational, transactional and Laissez faire leadership	Transactional and transformational leadership have indirect positive influence on employee service orientation. Employee engagement mediates these relationships. whereas a direct negative relationship exists between laissez faire style of leadership and service orientation
Koyuncu & colleagues	2014	Servant leadership	Existence of a positive and significant relationship between each dimension of servant leadership and each dimension of SERVQUAL
Ling and colleagues	2015	Servant leadership	Servant leadership cascade through organisational hierarchy to positively influence frontline employees service-oriented behaviours and service quality in the hotel sector
Wang and colleagues	2007	Servant leadership	Servant leadership cascade through organisational hierarchy to positively influence frontline employees service performance in the banking sector
Linuesa-Langreo and colleagues	2017	Servant leadership	No direct relationship exists between servant leadership and customer service performance